

International Scientific Conference

APPLIED RESEARCH. GLOBAL SOLUTIONS

Istanbul, Turkey - December 17, 2025

International Scientific Conference

**APPLIED RESEARCH.
GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

Part 1

Istanbul, Turkey – December 17, 2025

Proceedings of the International Science Conference
“APPLIED RESEARCH. GLOBAL SOLUTIONS”
(December 17, 2025). Istanbul. Turkey. Part 1.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.36.21.145

Science Conference Proceedings combine materials of the conference – research papers and thesis reports of scientific workers. They examine technical, juridical and sociological aspects of research issues. Some articles deal with theoretical and methodological approaches and principles of research questions of personality professionalization.

Authors are responsible for the accuracy of cited publications, facts, figures, quotations, statistics, proper names and other information.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.36.21.145

©Scientific publishing house Infinity, 2025
©Group of authors, 2025

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

- Light – Emitting Diodes and their application
Alakbarov Aydin S., Bayramli Razim B., Amirova Fidan Elchin 4
- Stress-strain state of a polar orthotropic annular disk of a power profile with a rigid central core rotating around diameter
Karalevich Uladzimir Vasil'evich 10
- Discoveries in mesotronics and high energy physics: a tribute to the jubilee of Professors Igor V. Minin and Oleg V. Minin
Huan Tang, Renxian Li 25

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

- Sorption method for industrial water purification
Ybraimzhanova Laura Kairoldayevna, Bektenov Nessipkhan Abzhaparovich . 40

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

- 16-membered antiparasitic macrolides in the focus for repurposing in oncology (mini-review)
Dzhafarov Mamedsalim Khanguseyn oglu, Zavarsin Igor Viktorovich 52
- Nutrition of the white carp in some reservoirs of the stavropol territory
Karnaukhov Gennady Ivanovich, Yatchenko Vladislav Nikolaevich 59
- The clinical significance of the medicinal properties of peonies
Lyapina Lyudmila Anisimovna, Uspenskaya Marianna Sergeevna, Murashev Vladimir Vladimirovich 63

EARTH SCIENCES

- The main patterns of manganese geochemistry
Yudovich Yakov Elievich, Ketris Marine Petrovna 72
- The Main Patterns of Titanium Geochemistry
Yudovich Yakov Elievich, Ketris Marine Petrovna 105

LIGHT – EMITTING DIODES AND THEIR APPLICATION

Alakbarov Aydin S.

*Doctor of Sciences in Physics, Professor
Baku Engineering University*

Bayramli Razim B.

*PhD in Physics, Associate Professor
Baku Engineering University*

Amirova Fidan Elchin

*MSc in Physics
Sumgayit State University*

Today, it is impossible to imagine the lighting system of various objects, cars, smartphones and televisions without light-emitting diodes (LEDs). As a light source, LEDs offer advantages over their counterparts in terms of low energy consumption, miniaturization, reliability and long lifespan. However, many users don't have detailed information about the discovery of the LED, its working principle, the quantities by which it is characterized as an optoelectronic device and its broader areas of application. Namely, these aspects are described by schematic diagrams, characteristics and figures in the article.

Keywords: *light-emitting diode, semiconductor materials, p-n junction, radiative recombination, band gap*

A light-emitting diode (LED) is a semiconductor device that emits light when current flows in the forward direction. LEDs are characterized by various colors, shapes, powers and applications. LED was invented by H. Round in 1907, and the physical basis of its working principle is the phenomenon of radiative recombination.

The first practical semiconductor diode emitting red light was invented by N. Holonyak in 1962. Today, diodes in various colors such as white, blue, green, yellow etc. have been invented and are used in a wide range of applications [1].

LEDs consist of p-type and n-type semiconductor layers. A p-n junction is created between these layers, where recombination of electrons and holes occurs. The recombination process is accompanied by the emission of light. The color of the emitted light depends on the width of the band gap of the semiconductor from which the diode is made.

Figure 1. Structural description of a light-emitting diode

In filament bulbs, light is emitted under the influence of heat when electric current passes through a tungsten wire and the efficiency of such light sources is $\eta < 15\%$. However, in a p-n junction in light diodes, a light source is radiative recombination of electrons and holes and the efficiency is $\eta > 50\%$ [2].

The working principle of a LED can be explained as follows:

As mentioned, there is a p-n junction between the semiconductor layers in a LED. If a current flows through this system in the forward direction, at the contact of two semiconductors, electrons move from the n-type semiconductor to the p-type semiconductor and holes move in the opposite direction. A photon is generated when electrons combine with holes in a p-type semiconductor and the same phenomenon occurs when holes combine with electrons in a n-type semiconductor (Fig. 1). The frequency of the emitted photons is directly proportional to the height of the potential barrier.

Currently, LEDs are being produced that cover all colors, (ultraviolet, all colors of the rainbow, infrared). The color of a LED depends on the wavelength of the photon emitted by the p-n junction. For example, the wavelength of the photon emitted by a red-emitting light-emitting diode covers the interval $\lambda = (610 \pm 760) \text{ nm}$. The wavelength, in turn, depends on the semiconductor material from which the LED is made [3]:

- GaS — infrared emission;
- $Ga_{1-x}Al_xAs$ — red emission;
- $Ga_{1-x}P_xAs$ — orange emission;
- $SiG:InGaN$ — yellow emission;
- $Ga_{1-x}P_xN_x$ — green emission;

As shown in list, the invented LEDs emit electromagnetic waves corresponding to the large wavelengths of the visible region of the spectrum. Problems arose with the emission of blue and ultraviolet waves. It is well known that to create pixels

that can produce white light and in general color images, light sources that emit red, green and blue light are needed.

Figure 2. Current-Voltage Characteristic of a Light-Emitting Diode

In 1992, Japanese physicist I. Akasaki invented the homogeneous p-n junction LED and was awarded the Nobel Prize in 2014. This diode was grown on a sapphire substrate and the waves it emitted fell into the blue and ultraviolet regions of the spectrum.

In 1993, another Japanese scientist, S. Nakamura, invented a low-cost diode that emitted blue light using *GaN* [4]. Nakamura was awarded the Nobel Prize in 2014 for this invention, which laid the foundation for new technology in the development of optoelectronics.

The band gap of the semiconductor materials from which LEDs are made and the wavelength of the light emitted from it, are determined by studying their current-voltage characteristics (Fig. 2).

If we increase the voltage between the anode and cathode, we will notice that the current intensity increases gradually at first and then sharply. Depending on the material of the LED (the wavelength of the light it emits), the current flowing through the p-n junction at the same voltage takes on different values.

At the moment when the LED is brightly lit, the wavelength of the emitted by the diode can be found from the expression

$$\lambda = \frac{hc}{eU}$$

by extrapolating a straight line from the sharp increase in the curve to the abscissa axis and taking into account the value of the intersection point of the line with the voltage axis in the formula:

$$\frac{hc}{\lambda} = eU$$

Here, $h = 6.625 \cdot 10^{-34} C \cdot sec$ — Planck's constant, $c = 3 \cdot 10^8 C m/sec$ is the speed of the light in vacuum, $e = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C$ is the elementary charge.

In the same way, the band gap width of the material from which the LED (p-n junction) is made can be determined from

$$Eg = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$$

Figure 3. Pixel structure

In terms of applications, LEDs are used to illuminate rooms, auditoriums of various sizes, streets and avenues and in pixels on advertising and educational boards, monitors, displays, televisions and telephone screens. LEDs are inorganic light-emitting diodes that perform these functions.

A pixel (short for picture element) is the smallest logical or physical element of a two-dimensional digital image and forms the matrix of displays. In color monitors, each pixel consists of three subpixels — red, green and blue LEDs arranged

in a specific order (Fig. 3). A single pixel on cathode-ray tube monitors may be composed of dozens of triads [5].

The image displayed on the screen depends on the number of pixels per unit area or their pitch — the distance between two neighboring points. Depending on the conditions in which the monitors are used, the range is between $P0.9 \div P16 \text{ mm}$

LED lamps have the following advantages over filament lamps and gas-discharge lamps:

- High brightness — the brightness of the LEDs is 6000 nits, 12 times higher than the maximum brightness of the Sun (about 500 nits). For this reason, large auditoriums are illuminated with LED systems;
- Modularity — the possibility of designing various displays in different shapes;
- No image distortion — images on information panels remain unchanged for hours;
- Light transmission — color shades remain unchanged during the transmission of information;

Figure 4. Image display on LED and OLED screens

In 1993, the use of organic material in a based p-n junction that emits blue light by Japanese physicist S. Nakamura (now a professor at the University of California, Santa Barbara) led to an increase in the quality and low cost of LED lighting systems.

OLED (Organic Light Emitting Diode) is a high-quality display technology that ensures independent emission of each pixel.

Displays made from OLED light-emitting diodes are used in smartphones, tables, e-books, digital cameras, in-vehicle computers, smartwatches, etc. [6].

OLED displays have the following advantages over their counterparts:

- High quality of the image;

- Displays that can be bent and twisted;
- The image is visible at large angles;
- Fast image rendering on the display;
- The only drawback of OLED systems is the short lifespan of the pixels.

Over time, the brightness and color of the image degrade, a phenomenon known as “burn-in”. Currently, new technologies and algorithms are being developed to overcome this drawback. The comparison of LED and OLED displays can also be made based on the image above (Fig. 4).

References

1. Akasaki I., Amano H., Itoh K., Koide N., and Manabe K. “ based UV/blue light-emitting devices” and Related Compounds conference, *Inst. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 129, 851 (1992).
2. Nuese C. J., Tietjen J. J., Gannon J. J., and Gossenberger H. F. “ Optimization of electroluminescent efficiencies for vapor-grown diodes” *J. Electrochem Soc.: Solid State Sci.* 116, 248, (1969).
3. Emerson D., Abare A., Bergmann M., Slater D., and Edmond J. “Development of deep UV III_{0.5}ItN optical sources “ 7th International Workshop on Wide Bandgap III_{0.5}ItNitrides, Richmond VA, March, 2002.
4. Rea, Mark S., ed. *The IESNA Lighting Handbook, Ninth Edition. Illuminating Engineering Society of America: New York, NY, 2000.*
5. Herniter, Mark E., *Multisim 7: A Modern System for Computer Simulation and Analysis of Electronic Device Circuits. (Translated from English) by Osipov, A.I–Moscow; DMK- Press Publishing House, 2006.*
6. Kaptsov V. A., Deinego V. N. *Evolution of artificial lighting: a hygienist’s perspective. Russian Academy of Sciences, 2021.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.15.37.146

UDC 539.3

STRESS-STRAIN STATE OF A POLAR ORTHOTROPIC ANNULAR DISK OF A POWER PROFILE WITH A RIGID CENTRAL CORE ROTATING AROUND DIAMETER**Karalevich Uladzimir Vasil'evich***Professor**International Center for Modern Education (ICME),**Prague, Czech Republic*

Abstract. *The paper provides an exact solution to the planar problem of elasticity theory for a polar-orthotropic annular disk of a power-law profile with a rigid central core rotating at a constant angular velocity ω_0 around the diameter. A system of partial differential equations is written for the radial $\sigma_r(r, \theta)$, tangential $\sigma_\theta(r, \theta)$ and shear stress $\tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta)$ components. Decomposing the stress components along the angular coordinate θ into finite trigonometric Fourier series containing two terms, we obtain two systems of ordinary differential equations for radial stress components. From the first system of differential equations describing the axisymmetric deformation of a polar-orthotropic disk of a power profile, we find exact solutions for the stress $\sigma_r^{(0)}(r), \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)$ and radial displacement $u_0(r)$ components. The operator method is used to solve the second system of differential equations describing the symmetric deformation of a polar-orthotropic disk of a power profile rotating around a diameter. Exact solutions for stress components $\sigma_r^{(2)}(r), \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r), \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}$, radial displacement $u_2(r)$, and tangential displacement $v_2(r)$ are given. The integration constants are determined from the boundary conditions.*

Keywords: *Fourier series; operator method; polar-orthotropic disk of a power profile; radial, tangential and shear stress components; radial and tangential displacement components; system of ordinary differential equations; system of partial differential equations.*

Introduction

The stress-strain state of a polar orthotropic annular disk of a power-law profile with a rigid central core rotating at a constant angular velocity ω_0 around the diameter is investigated. This rotation of the disk occurs in flowmeters of liquids and gases; agitators in food and chemical industries.

The disk is made of a material with cylindrical anisotropy, and the axis of anisotropy coincides with the geometric axis of the disk, and at each point of the body there are three mutually orthogonal planes of elastic symmetry, the so-called cylindrical orthotropy. In the case of a planar problem, the disk is polar-orthotropic with respect to its elastic properties.

The inner radius of the annular disk is denoted by r_0 , and the outer one by R . The thickness of the disk varies along the radius r according to the power law:

$$h(r) = h_0 \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^\alpha, \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \text{where } h_0 \text{ is the thickness of the disk on the inner contour}$$

of the radius r_0 . Since the thickness of the disk rushes to infinity in the center of the disk, in a real design, a hard core of radius r_0 is inserted in the center of the disk. A thick-walled metal ring or a solid metal disk can be used as a hard core. The outer contour of the disk will be assumed to be free from external effort's, and the inner contour of the disk is bonded to a rigid core so that there is no movement of points of the inner contour.

The basic equations of the plane problem of elasticity theory for a polar-orthotropic disk of a power profile rotating around a diameter, and their solutions

We introduce a cylindrical coordinate system r, θ, z , placing the origin at the intersection of the anisotropy axis with the median plane of the disk. The axis of rotation lies in the median plane of the disk and passes through its center, i.e. coincides with the diameter of the disk.

Let us isolate from the disk by two meridional planes forming angles θ and $\theta + d\theta$ with the coordinate plane rz , and by two cylindrical surfaces of radius r and $r+dr$, normal to the median plane, an infinitesimal element of the disk. Let's write down the equilibrium equations of this element in the efforts [1]:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial N_r}{\partial r} r + \frac{\partial N_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} - N_\theta \right) + q_r(r, \theta) = 0, \\ \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial N_{r\theta}}{\partial r} r + \frac{\partial N_\theta}{\partial \theta} + N_{r\theta} \right) + q_\theta(r, \theta) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where the normal ones are $N_r(r, \theta) = h(r)\sigma_r(r, \theta)$ – radial effort, $N_\theta(r, \theta) = h(r)\sigma_\theta(r, \theta)$ – tangential effort and $N_{r\theta}(r, \theta) = h(r)\tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta)$ – shear effort; $\sigma_r(r, \theta)$ $\sigma_\theta(r, \theta)$ – normal radial and tangential stresses, respectively; $\tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta) = \tau_{\theta r}(r, \theta)$ – shear stresses; $q_r(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{2}h(r)\rho\omega_0^2 r \cdot (1 + \cos 2\theta)$, $q_\theta(r, \theta) = -\frac{1}{2}h(r)\rho\omega_0^2 r \cdot \sin 2\theta$ – radial and tangential components of the inertial

load on the disk rotating around the diameter, respectively; ρ - density of the disk material. Let us imagine the equations of equilibrium (1) in stresses for a disk of a power profile rotating around a diameter:

Let us imagine the equations of equilibrium (1) in stresses for a disk of a power profile rotating around a diameter:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{(1-\alpha)\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 r}{2}(1 + \cos 2\theta), \\ \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{(2-\alpha)\tau_{r\theta}}{r} = \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 r}{2} \sin 2\theta. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Hooke's law for a plane stressed state of a polar orthotropic body is [2]:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_r(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{E_r} \sigma_r(r, \theta) - \frac{\nu_{\theta r}}{E_\theta} \sigma_\theta(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{E_\theta} (k^2 \sigma_r(r, \theta) - \nu_{\theta r} \sigma_\theta(r, \theta)), \\ \varepsilon_\theta(r, \theta) = -\frac{\nu_{r\theta}}{E_r} \sigma_r(r, \theta) + \frac{1}{E_\theta} \sigma_\theta(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{E_\theta} (-\nu_{r\theta} \sigma_r(r, \theta) + \sigma_\theta(r, \theta)), \\ \gamma_{r\theta}(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{G_{r\theta}} \tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta), \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_r(r, \theta)$ $\varepsilon_\theta(r, \theta)$ are the normal radial and tangential components of the deformation, respectively; $\gamma_{r\theta}(r, \theta)$ – shear deformations; E_r, E_θ - Young's modulus of tension (compression) of a polar-orthotropic body in the direction of the axes r and θ , respectively; $\nu_{r\theta}, \nu_{\theta r}$ - Poisson's ratio; $G_{r\theta}$ - shear modulus.

For a polar-orthotropic body, the equality is valid: $\frac{\nu_{r\theta}}{E_r} = \frac{\nu_{\theta r}}{E_\theta}$.

We denote the components of the displacement vector \vec{U} in the radial direction by $u(r, \theta)$, and in the tangential direction by $v(r, \theta)$.

The relationship of the deformation components $\varepsilon_r(r, \theta), \varepsilon_\theta(r, \theta), \gamma_{r\theta}(r, \theta)$ with the components $u(r, \theta), v(r, \theta)$ of the displacement vector \vec{U} is given by the Cauchy differential relations [2]:

$$\varepsilon_r(r, \theta) = \frac{\partial u(r, \theta)}{\partial r}, \quad \varepsilon_\theta(r, \theta) = \frac{u(r, \theta)}{r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v(r, \theta)}{\partial \theta}, \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma_{r\theta}(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u(r, \theta)}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial v(r, \theta)}{\partial r} - \frac{v(r, \theta)}{r}.$$

By excluding the components $u(r, \theta)$ and $v(r, \theta)$ displacement vectors \vec{U} from the relations (5), we obtain the equation of compatibility of deformations in polar coordinates [2]:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_r}{\partial \theta^2} + r \frac{\partial^2 (r \varepsilon_\theta)}{\partial r^2} - \frac{\partial^2 (r \gamma_{r\theta})}{\partial r \partial \theta} - r \frac{\partial \varepsilon_r}{\partial r} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Substituting the right-hand sides of expressions (3) for the strain components in equation (5), we obtain the stress compatibility equation:

$$\left(\nu_\theta \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_r}{\partial r^2} - \frac{k^2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_r}{\partial \theta^2} + (k^2 + 2\nu_\theta) \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_\theta}{\partial r^2} - \frac{\nu_\theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + (2 + \nu_\theta) \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{E_\theta}{G_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r \partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} \right) = 0. \quad (6)$$

The boundary conditions will be written as:

$$\begin{cases} u(r_0, \theta) = 0, \quad v(r_0, \theta) = 0, \\ \sigma_r(R, \theta) = 0, \quad \tau_{r\theta}(R, \theta) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

We will look for solutions of differential equations (2), (6) in the form of expansions by the angular coordinate of the stress components into finite Fourier series.

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_r(r, \theta) = \sigma_r^{(0)}(r) + \sigma_r^{(2)}(r) \cos 2\theta, \\ \sigma_\theta(r, \theta) = \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r) + \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r) \cos 2\theta, \\ \tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta) = \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) \sin 2\theta. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Substituting expansions (8) into equations (2) and (6), we obtain the following systems of equations for radial stress components $\sigma_r^{(0)}(r), \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r), \sigma_r^{(2)}(r), \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r), \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r)$:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{d\sigma_r^{(0)}(r)}{dr} + \frac{(1-\alpha)}{r} \sigma_r^{(0)}(r) - \frac{1}{r} \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 r}{2}, \\ & \left(\nu_{\theta r} \frac{d^2 \sigma_r^{(0)}(r)}{dr^2} + (k^2 + 2\nu_{\theta r}) \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\sigma_r^{(0)}(r)}{dr} \right) - \left(\frac{d^2 \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)}{dr^2} + (2 + \nu_{\theta r}) \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)}{dr} \right) = 0; \end{aligned} \right. \quad (9)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{d\sigma_r^{(2)}(r)}{dr} + \frac{(1-\alpha)}{r} \sigma_r^{(2)}(r) - \frac{1}{r} \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r) + \frac{2}{r} \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 r}{2}, \\ & \frac{d\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r)}{dr} + \frac{(2-\alpha)}{r} \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) - \frac{2}{r} \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r) = \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 r}{2}, \\ & \left(\nu_{\theta r} \frac{d^2 \sigma_r^{(2)}(r)}{dr^2} + (k^2 + 2\nu_{\theta r}) \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\sigma_r^{(2)}(r)}{dr} + \frac{4k^2}{r^2} \sigma_r^{(2)}(r) \right) - \left(\frac{d^2 \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r)}{dr^2} + (2 + \nu_{\theta r}) \times \right. \\ & \left. \times \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r)}{dr} + \frac{4\nu_{\theta r}}{r^2} \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r) \right) + 2 \frac{E_\theta}{G_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{d\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r)}{dr} + \frac{1}{r^2} \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (10)$$

We introduce a new variable $t = \mathbf{h} x$, where $x = \frac{r}{R}$, $x \in [\delta, 1]$, $\delta = \frac{r_0}{R}$. The systems of differential equations (9) and (10) are written as:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{d\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt} + (1-\alpha)\sigma_r^{(0)}(t) - \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(t) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ & \left(\nu_{\theta r} \frac{d^2 \sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt^2} + (k^2 + \nu_{\theta r}) \frac{d\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt} \right) - \left(\frac{d^2 \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(t)}{dt^2} + (1 + \nu_{\theta r}) \frac{d\sigma_\theta^{(0)}(t)}{dt} \right) = 0; \end{aligned} \right. \quad (11)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{d\sigma_r^{(2)}(t)}{dt} + (1-\alpha)\sigma_r^{(2)}(t) - \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(t) + 2\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ & \frac{d\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt} + (2-\alpha)\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) - 2\sigma_\theta^{(2)}(t) = \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ & \left(\nu_{\theta r} \frac{d^2 \sigma_r^{(2)}(t)}{dt^2} + (k^2 + \nu_{\theta r}) \frac{d\sigma_r^{(2)}(t)}{dt} + 4k^2 \sigma_r^{(2)}(t) \right) - \left(\frac{d^2 \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(t)}{dt^2} + (1 + \nu_{\theta r}) \times \right. \\ & \left. \times \frac{d\sigma_\theta^{(2)}(t)}{dt} + 4\nu_{\theta r} \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(t) \right) + 2 \frac{E_\theta}{G_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{d\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt} + \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (12)$$

First, we find a general solution to the system of differential equations (11).

From the first equation, we express $\sigma_\theta^{(0)}(t)$ in terms of $\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)$ and its derivative:

$$\sigma_{\theta}^{(0)}(t) = \frac{d\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt} + (1-\alpha)\sigma_r^{(0)}(t) + \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}. \quad (13)$$

Substituting expression (13) into the second equation of system (11) yields an inhomogeneous ordinary differential equation of the 3rd order with constant coefficients for the voltage component $\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)$:

$$\frac{d^3\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt^3} + (2-\alpha)\frac{d^2\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt^2} + [(1-\alpha) - (k^2 + \alpha\nu_{\theta r})]\frac{d\sigma_r^{(0)}(t)}{dt} = -(3 + \nu_{\theta r})\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t}. \quad (14)$$

The general solution of the inhomogeneous differential equation (14) is:

$$\sigma_r^{(0)}(t) = C_1^{(0)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(0)}t} + C_2^{(0)} \cdot e^{\lambda_2^{(0)}t} + C_3^{(0)} - \frac{(3 + \nu_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + \nu_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \quad (15)$$

where $C_1^{(0)}, C_2^{(0)}$ are the integration constants, which are determined from the boundary conditions;

the constant $C_3^{(0)}$ is found from the condition of uniqueness of the radial deformation $\varepsilon_r^{(0)}(r)$;

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \lambda_1^{(0)} = \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} - 1\right) + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\alpha}{2} + \nu_{\theta r}\right)^2 + (k^2 - \nu_{\theta r}^2)}, \\ \lambda_2^{(0)} = \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} - 1\right) - \sqrt{\left(\frac{\alpha}{2} + \nu_{\theta r}\right)^2 + (k^2 - \nu_{\theta r}^2)} \end{array} \right. \text{ - the roots of the characteristic equation:}$$

$$\lambda^{(0)2} + (2-\alpha)\lambda^{(0)} + [(1-\alpha) - (k^2 + \alpha\nu_{\theta r})] = 0.$$

Substituting expression (15) into formula (13), we find the tangential stress $\sigma_{\theta}^{(0)}(t)$

$$\sigma_{\theta}^{(0)}(t) = [\lambda_1^{(0)} + (1-\alpha)]C_1^{(0)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(0)}t} + [\lambda_2^{(0)} + (1-\alpha)]C_2^{(0)} \cdot e^{\lambda_2^{(0)}t} + (1-\alpha)C_3^{(0)} - \frac{(k^2 + 3\nu_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + \nu_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}. \quad (16)$$

Returning to the variable r, we obtain the solution of the system of equations (11) in the form:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \sigma_r^{(0)}(r) &= C_1^{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_1^{(0)}} + C_2^{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_2^{(0)}} + C_3^{(0)} - \frac{(3 + \nu_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + \nu_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2, \\ \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r) &= [\lambda_1^{(0)} + (1 - \alpha)] C_1^{(0)} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_1^{(0)}} + [\lambda_2^{(0)} + (1 - \alpha)] C_2^{(0)} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_2^{(0)}} + (1 - \alpha) C_3^{(0)} - \\ &\quad - \frac{(k^2 + 3\nu_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + \nu_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (17)$$

The radial and tangential displacements are represented as expansions of the angular coordinate θ into the following finite Fourier series:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} u(r, \theta) &= u_0(r) + u_2(r) \cos 2\theta, \\ v(r, \theta) &= v_2(r) \sin 2\theta. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (18)$$

The components of normal radial $\varepsilon_r(r, \theta)$, tangential deformations $\varepsilon_\theta(r, \theta)$, and the shear deformation component $\gamma_{r\theta}(r, \theta)$ are also represented as finite Fourier series:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \varepsilon_r(r, \theta) &= \varepsilon_r^{(0)}(r) + \varepsilon_r^{(2)}(r) \cos 2\theta, \\ \varepsilon_\theta(r, \theta) &= \varepsilon_\theta^{(0)}(r) + \varepsilon_\theta^{(2)}(r) \cos 2\theta, \\ \gamma_{r\theta}(r, \theta) &= \gamma_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) \sin 2\theta. \end{aligned} \right. \quad (19)$$

Substituting expansions (18), (19) into the Cauchy differential relations (4) and the equations of Hooke's law (3) leads to the following systems of equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \varepsilon_r^{(0)}(r) &= \frac{du_0(r)}{dr} = \frac{1}{E_\theta} [k^2 \cdot \sigma_r^{(0)}(r) - \nu_{\theta r} \cdot \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)], \\ \varepsilon_\theta^{(0)}(r) &= \frac{u_0(r)}{r} = \frac{1}{E_\theta} [-\nu_{\theta r} \cdot \sigma_r^{(0)}(r) + \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)]; \end{aligned} \right. \quad (20)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \varepsilon_r^{(2)}(r) &= \frac{du_2(r)}{dr} = \frac{1}{E_\theta} [k^2 \cdot \sigma_r^{(2)}(r) - \nu_{\theta r} \cdot \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r)], \\ \varepsilon_\theta^{(2)}(r) &= \frac{u_2(r)}{r} + \frac{2v_2(r)}{r} = \frac{1}{E_\theta} [-\nu_{\theta r} \cdot \sigma_r^{(2)}(r) + \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(r)], \\ \gamma_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) &= \frac{dv_2(r)}{dr} - \frac{v_2(r)}{r} - \frac{2u_2(r)}{r} = \frac{1}{G_{r\theta}} \cdot \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r). \end{aligned} \right. \quad (21)$$

From the second equation of the system (20), we determine the radial displacement $u_0(r)$ in the disk:

$$u_0(r) = \frac{r}{E_\theta} [-v_{\theta r} \cdot \sigma_r^{(0)}(r) + \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)] \quad (22)$$

Substituting the expressions for the stress components $\sigma_r^{(0)}(r), \sigma_\theta^{(0)}(r)$ from (17) into formula (22), we obtain:

$$u_0(r) = \frac{R}{E_\theta} \left\{ \left[(\lambda_1^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] C_1^{(0)} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{\lambda_1^{(0)}+1} + \left[(\lambda_2^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] C_2^{(0)} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{\lambda_2^{(0)}+1} + \left[(1 - \alpha) - v_{\theta r} \right] C_3^{(0)} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \right\} - \frac{(k^2 - v_{\theta r}^2)}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + v_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^3}{2E_\theta} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^3. \quad (23)$$

For the unambiguity of the solution for radial deformation $\varepsilon_r^{(0)}(r)$, it is necessary to set the constant $C_3^{(0)}$ equal to zero. The constants $C_1^{(0)}, C_2^{(0)}$ are determined from the boundary conditions:

$$u_0(r_0) = 0, \quad \sigma_r^{(0)}(R) = 0. \quad (24)$$

Satisfying the found solutions (17), (23) to the boundary conditions (24), we obtain a system of algebraic equations for finding unknown constants $C_1^{(0)}, C_2^{(0)}$:

$$C_1^{(0)} + C_2^{(0)} = \frac{(3 + v_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + v_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2}, \quad (25)$$

$$\left[(\lambda_1^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_1^{(0)}} \cdot C_1^{(0)} + \left[(\lambda_2^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_2^{(0)}} \cdot C_2^{(0)} = \frac{(k^2 - v_{\theta r}^2)}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + v_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \delta^2.$$

The solution of the system of algebraic equations (25) is:

$$\begin{cases} C_1^{(0)} = - \frac{\left\{ \left[(\lambda_2^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_2^{(0)}} - \left(\frac{k^2 - v_{\theta r}^2}{3 + v_{\theta r}} \right) \delta^2 \right\}}{\left\{ \left[(\lambda_1^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_1^{(0)}} - \left[(\lambda_2^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_2^{(0)}} \right\}} \cdot \frac{(3 + v_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + v_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2}, \\ C_2^{(0)} = \frac{\left\{ \left[(\lambda_1^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_1^{(0)}} - \left(\frac{k^2 - v_{\theta r}^2}{3 + v_{\theta r}} \right) \delta^2 \right\}}{\left\{ \left[(\lambda_1^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_1^{(0)}} - \left[(\lambda_2^{(0)} - v_{\theta r}) + (1 - \alpha) \right] \delta^{\lambda_2^{(0)}} \right\}} \cdot \frac{(3 + v_{\theta r})}{[(9 - k^2) - \alpha(3 + v_{\theta r})]} \cdot \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2}. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Let us proceed to finding a solution to an inhomogeneous system (12) of differential equations with constant coefficients. Let us apply the operator method of integrating systems of differential equations. It is a modification of the Gauss method for solving systems of linear algebraic equations [3].

We denote:

$$\sigma_r^{(2)}(t) = x_1(t), \quad \sigma_\theta^{(2)}(t) = x_2(t), \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)} = x_3(t);$$

$$D^0 = 1, \quad D^1 = \frac{d}{dt}, \quad D^2 = \frac{d^2}{dt^2}, \quad D^m D^n = D^{m+n} = D^n D^m,$$

where D is the differentiation operator. The system (12) is written in the following form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [D^1 + (1 - \alpha)D^0]x_1(t) - D^0x_2(t) + 2D^0x_3(t) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ 0 \cdot x_1(t) + 2D^0x_2(t) - [D^1 + (2 - \alpha)D^0]x_3(t) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ [v_{\theta r}D^2 + (k^2 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4k^2D^0]x_1(t) - [D^2 + (1 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4v_{\theta r}D^0]x_2(t) + \\ + 2\frac{E_\theta}{G_{r\theta}}(D^1 + D^0)x_3(t) = 0. \end{array} \right. \quad (27)$$

The system of algebraic equations (27) is represented in matrix form:

$$A(D)X(t) = F(t),$$

where

$$A(D) = \begin{pmatrix} [D^1 + (1 - \alpha)D^0] & -D^0 & 2D^0 \\ 0 & 2D^0 & -[D^1 + (2 - \alpha)D^0] \\ [v_{\theta r}D^2 + (k^2 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4k^2D^0] & -[D^2 + (1 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4v_{\theta r}D^0] & 2\frac{E_\theta}{G_{r\theta}}(D^1 + D^0) \end{pmatrix} -$$

the main matrix of the system,

$$X(t) = \begin{pmatrix} x_1(t) \\ x_2(t) \\ x_3(t) \end{pmatrix} - \text{vector column of unknown quantities,}$$

$$F(t) = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t} \\ -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - \text{vector column of inertial loads on the disk.}$$

Let's make up an extended matrix $(A(D)|F)$ of the system and, by elementary transformations over it, bring it to a trapezoidal matrix:

$$(A(D)|F) = \begin{pmatrix} [D^1 + (1-\alpha)D^0] & -D^0 & 2D^0 \\ 0 & 2D^0 & -[D^1 + (2-\alpha)D^0] \\ [v_{\theta r}D^2 + (k^2 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4k^2D^0] & -[D^2 + (1+v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4v_{\theta r}D^0] & 2\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}}(D^1 + D^0) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{c} -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t} \\ -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t} \\ 0 \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{ccc|c} [D^1 + (1-\alpha)D^0] & -D^0 & 2D^0 & -0,5\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t} \\ 0 & 2D^0 & -[D^1 + (2-\alpha)D^0] & -0,5\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t} \\ 0 & K_{32}(D) & K_{33}(D) & 3(k^2 + v_{\theta r})\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t} \end{array} \right) \sim$$

$$\sim \left(\begin{array}{ccc|c} [D^1 + (1-\alpha)D^0] & -D^0 & 2D^0 & -0,5\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t} \\ 0 & 2D^0 & -[D^1 + (2-\alpha)D^0] & -0,5\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t} \\ 0 & 0 & L_{33}(D) & 3[3(k^2 - 1) + \alpha(1 + v_{\theta r})]\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t} \end{array} \right),$$

where

$$K_{32}(D) = -[D^1 + (1-\alpha)D^0] \cdot [D^2 + (1+v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4v_{\theta r}D^0] + D^0 \cdot [v_{\theta r}D^2 + (k^2 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4k^2D^0] =$$

$$= -\{D^3 + (2-\alpha)D^2 - [(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - ((1-\alpha) + 4v_{\theta r})]D^1 - 4[(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - v_{\theta r}]D^0\},$$

$$K_{33}(D) = 2\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}}(D^1 + D^0) \cdot [D^1 + (1-\alpha)D^0] - 2D^0 \cdot [v_{\theta r}D^2 + (k^2 + v_{\theta r})D^1 + 4k^2D^0] =$$

$$= 2\left\{ \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - v_{\theta r} \right) D^2 + \left[(2-\alpha) \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - v_{\theta r} \right) + (1-\alpha)v_{\theta r} - k^2 \right] D^1 + \right.$$

$$\left. + \left[(1-\alpha) \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - v_{\theta r} \right) + (1-\alpha)v_{\theta r} - 4k^2 \right] D^0 \right\},$$

$$L_{33}(D) = 2D^0 \cdot K_{33}(D) + [D^1 + (2-\alpha)D^0] \cdot K_{32}(D) = -\{D^4 + 2(2-\alpha)D^3 + [(\alpha^2 - 5\alpha + 5) - (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 4\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right)]D^2 + (2-\alpha)\left[(1-\alpha) - (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 4\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right)\right]D^1 + 4\left\{(1-\alpha)\left[k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}\right] + \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right)\right\} - 3k^2\}D^0\}.$$

Using the last transformed matrix, we will restore the system of differential equations for the desired unknowns $\sigma_r^{(2)}(t)$, $\sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$, $\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)$:

(28)

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\sigma_r^{(2)}(t)}{dt} + (1-\alpha)\sigma_r^{(2)}(t) - \sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t) + 2\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ 2\sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t) - \frac{d\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt} - (2-\alpha)\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) = -\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \\ \frac{d^4\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt^4} + 2(2-\alpha)\frac{d^3\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt^3} + [(\alpha^2 - 5\alpha + 5) - (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 4\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right)]\frac{d^2\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt^2} + (2-\alpha)\left[(1-\alpha) - (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 4\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right)\right]\frac{d\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)}{dt} - 4\left\{(1-\alpha)\left[k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}\right] + \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right)\right\} - 3k^2\}\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) = -3[3(k^2 - 1) + \alpha(1 + v_{\theta r})]\rho\omega_0^2 R^2 \cdot e^{2t}. \end{cases}$$

The last equation of the system of ordinary differential equations (28) has the following solution:

$$\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) = C_1^{(2)} e^{\lambda_1^{(2)} t} + C_2^{(2)} e^{-\lambda_1^{(2)} t} + C_3^{(2)} e^{\lambda_2^{(2)} t} + C_4^{(2)} e^{-\lambda_2^{(2)} t} - A \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} e^{2t}, \quad (29)$$

where $C_i^{(2)}(i = \overline{1,4})$ are arbitrary constants determined from boundary conditions;

$$A = \frac{[3(k^2 - 1) + \alpha(1 + v_{\theta r})]}{\left[(3-\alpha)(4-\alpha) - (2-\alpha)(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 2(3-\alpha)\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right) + 2k^2\right]},$$

$\lambda_i^{(2)}(i = \overline{1,2})$ - the roots of the characteristic equation:

$$\lambda^4 + 2(2-\alpha)\lambda^3 + \left[(\alpha^2 - 5\alpha + 5) - (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 4 \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r} \right) \right] \lambda^2 + (2-\alpha) \left[(1-\alpha) - (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 4 \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r} \right) \right] \lambda - 4 \left\{ (1-\alpha) \left[(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) + \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r} \right) \right] - 3k^2 \right\} = 0. \quad (30)$$

An algebraic equation of the 4th degree (30) for an unknown quantity λ is reduced by substitution to a biquadrate equation for the quantity μ :

$$\mu^4 - \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 \right) + (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) + 4 \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r} \right) \right] \cdot \mu^2 + \left[\frac{\alpha^2}{4} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)^2 + \left(3 + \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \cdot (k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) + \alpha^2 \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r} \right) - 12\alpha v_{\theta r} \right] = 0. \quad (31)$$

The roots of the biquadrate equation (31) are:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mu_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 + \psi \right) + \sqrt{\psi^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 \right) \psi + (1-\alpha)^2} \right]}, \\ \mu_{3,4} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 + \psi \right) - \sqrt{\psi^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 \right) \psi + (1-\alpha)^2} \right]}, \end{array} \right.$$

$$\text{where } \psi = \left[(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) + 4 \left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r} \right) \right].$$

The roots $\lambda_1^{(2)}$, $\lambda_2^{(2)}$ of the characteristic equation (30) are equal to:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_1^{(2)} = -\left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) + \mu_1 = -\left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 + \psi \right) + \sqrt{\psi^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 \right) \psi + (1-\alpha)^2} \right]}, \\ \lambda_2^{(2)} = -\left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) + \mu_3 = -\left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 + \psi \right) - \sqrt{\psi^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} - \alpha + 1 \right) \psi + (1-\alpha)^2} \right]}. \end{array} \right. \quad (32)$$

Substituting the solution (29) for the tangential stress $\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)$ into the second equation of the system (28), we find the tangential stress $\sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$:

$$\sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t) = \gamma_1^{(2)} C_1^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(2)} t} + \gamma_2^{(2)} C_2^{(2)} \cdot e^{-\lambda_1^{(2)} t} + \gamma_3^{(2)} C_3^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_2^{(2)} t} + \gamma_4^{(2)} C_4^{(2)} \cdot e^{-\lambda_2^{(2)} t} - B \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot e^{2t}, \quad (33)$$

where

$$\gamma_1^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2}[\lambda_1^{(2)} + (2-\alpha)], \gamma_2^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{2}[\lambda_1^{(2)} - (2-\alpha)], \gamma_3^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2}[\lambda_2^{(2)} + (2-\alpha)], \gamma_4^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{2}[\lambda_2^{(2)} - (2-\alpha)],$$

$$B = \frac{\left[(6-\alpha)(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - (3-\alpha)\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right) - \alpha(5-\alpha)v_{\theta r} \right]}{\left[(3-\alpha)(4-\alpha) - (2-\alpha)(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 2(3-\alpha)\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right) + 2k^2 \right]}.$$

We substitute the solutions for tangential stress $\sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$ and shear stress $\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t)$ into the first equation of the system (28). As a result, we obtain an inhomogeneous differential equation of the 1st order for radial stress $\sigma_r^{(2)}(t)$:

$$\frac{d\sigma_r^{(2)}}{dt} + (1-\alpha)\sigma_r^{(2)}(t) = \sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(t) - 2\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(t) - \frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot e^{2t} = (\gamma_1^{(2)} - 2)C_1^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(2)}t} + (\gamma_2^{(2)} - 2)C_1^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(2)}t} + (\gamma_3^{(2)} - 2)C_1^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(2)}t} + (\gamma_4^{(2)} - 2)C_1^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(2)}t} + (2A - B - 1)\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot e^{2t}. \tag{34}$$

The solution of the inhomogeneous ordinary differential equation (34) is:

$$\sigma_r^{(2)}(t) = \beta_1^{(2)}C_1^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_1^{(2)}t} + \beta_2^{(2)}C_2^{(2)} \cdot e^{-\lambda_1^{(2)}t} + \beta_3^{(2)}C_3^{(2)} \cdot e^{\lambda_2^{(2)}t} + \beta_4^{(2)}C_4^{(2)} \cdot e^{-\lambda_2^{(2)}t} + C_5^{(2)} \cdot e^{(\alpha-1)t} + J\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot e^{2t}, \tag{35}$$

where

$$\beta_1^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{[\lambda_1^{(2)} - (2+\alpha)]}{[\lambda_1^{(2)} + (1-\alpha)]}, \beta_2^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{[\lambda_1^{(2)} + (2+\alpha)]}{[\lambda_1^{(2)} - (1-\alpha)]}, \beta_3^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{[\lambda_2^{(2)} - (2+\alpha)]}{[\lambda_2^{(2)} + (1-\alpha)]}, \beta_4^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{[\lambda_2^{(2)} + (2+\alpha)]}{[\lambda_2^{(2)} - (1-\alpha)]},$$

$$J = \frac{\left[(6-\alpha) - 3\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right) - \alpha v_{\theta r} \right]}{(3-\alpha) \left[(3-\alpha)(4-\alpha) - (2-\alpha)(k^2 + \alpha v_{\theta r}) - 2(3-\alpha)\left(\frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} - 2v_{\theta r}\right) + 2k^2 \right]}.$$

The expressions for the stress components in the variable r will take the form: (36)

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sigma_r^{(2)}(r) = \beta_1^{(2)}C_1^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \beta_2^{(2)}C_2^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \beta_3^{(2)}C_3^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_2^{(2)}} + \beta_4^{(2)}C_4^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-\lambda_2^{(2)}} + C_5^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\alpha-1} + J\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2, \\ \sigma_{\theta}^{(2)}(r) = \gamma_1^{(2)}C_1^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \gamma_2^{(2)}C_2^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \gamma_3^{(2)}C_3^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_2^{(2)}} + \gamma_4^{(2)}C_4^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-\lambda_2^{(2)}} + (2A - B)\frac{\rho\omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2, \end{array} \right.$$

$$\left(\tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(r) = C_1^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_1^{(2)}} + C_2^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-\lambda_1^{(2)}} + C_3^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda_2^{(2)}} + C_4^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-\lambda_2^{(2)}} - A \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^2}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2, \right.$$

Let's find the components of displacements $u_2(r), v_2(r)$ from the system of equations of Hooke's law (21).

Integrating the first equation of the system (21), we obtain the expression for the radial displacement $u_2(r)$:

$$u_2(r) = \frac{R}{E_\theta} \left[\alpha_1^{(2)} C_1^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1+\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \alpha_2^{(2)} C_2^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1-\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \alpha_3^{(2)} C_3^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1+\lambda_2^{(2)}} + \alpha_4^{(2)} C_4^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1-\lambda_2^{(2)}} + \frac{k^2}{\alpha} C_5^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^\alpha + C_6^{(2)} \right] + I \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^3}{6E_\theta} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^3, \quad (37)$$

where

$$\alpha_1^{(2)} = \frac{(k^2 \beta_1^{(2)} - \nu_{\theta r} \gamma_1^{(2)})}{(1 + \lambda_1^{(2)})}, \alpha_2^{(2)} = \frac{(k^2 \beta_2^{(2)} - \nu_{\theta r} \gamma_2^{(2)})}{(1 - \lambda_1^{(2)})}, \alpha_3^{(2)} = \frac{(k^2 \beta_3^{(2)} - \nu_{\theta r} \gamma_3^{(2)})}{(1 + \lambda_2^{(2)})}, \alpha_4^{(2)} = \frac{(k^2 \beta_4^{(2)} - \nu_{\theta r} \gamma_4^{(2)})}{(1 - \lambda_2^{(2)})},$$

$$I = [k^2 J - \nu_{\theta r} (2A - B)].$$

Let us substitute the solution (37) for the radial displacement $u_2(r)$ into the second equation of the system (21) and determine the tangential displacement $v_2(r)$:

$$v_2(r) = -\frac{R}{E_\theta} \left[\kappa_1^{(2)} C_1^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1+\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \kappa_2^{(2)} C_2^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1-\lambda_1^{(2)}} + \kappa_3^{(2)} C_3^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1+\lambda_2^{(2)}} + \kappa_4^{(2)} C_4^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1-\lambda_2^{(2)}} + \frac{1}{\alpha} (k^2 + \alpha \nu_{\theta r}) C_5^{(2)} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^\alpha + C_6^{(2)} \right] - [(k^2 + 3\nu_{\theta r})J - (3 + \nu_{\theta r})(2A - B)] \frac{\rho \omega_0^2 R^3}{12E_\theta} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^3, \quad (38)$$

where

$$\kappa_1^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_1^{(2)} + \nu_{\theta r} \beta_1^{(2)} - \gamma_1^{(2)}), \kappa_2^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_2^{(2)} + \nu_{\theta r} \beta_2^{(2)} - \gamma_2^{(2)}), \kappa_3^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_3^{(2)} + \nu_{\theta r} \beta_3^{(2)} - \gamma_3^{(2)}),$$

$$\kappa_4^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_4^{(2)} + \nu_{\theta r} \beta_4^{(2)} - \gamma_4^{(2)}).$$

The third equation of the system of equations of Hooke's law (21) will be identically fulfilled if the unknown constants $C_5^{(2)}, C_6^{(2)}$ in expressions (37) and (38) for

the displacement components $u_2(r), v_2(r)$ are set equal to zero. The remaining constants $C_i^{(2)}$ ($i = \overline{1;4}$) for a particular disk are usually determined numerically from boundary conditions:

$$\begin{cases} u_2(r_0) = 0, v_2(r_0) = 0, \\ \sigma_r^{(2)}(R) = 0, \tau_{r\theta}^{(2)}(R) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Note. The case of positive roots μ_1 and μ_3 the bi-quadratic equation (31) is considered above. The solution of the plane problem of elasticity theory for a power-law disk rotating around a diameter will be expressed in hyperbolic functions. If the roots μ_2 and μ_4 the biquadrature equation (31) are negative, then the solution of the plane problem of elasticity theory will be expressed in trigonometric functions.

In [4], we investigated the stress state of a continuous polar orthotropic disk of constant thickness rotating around a diameter, as a special case of a power-law disk with a degree of $\alpha = 0$.

Conclusion

The formulas obtained in this article (17), (23), (36), (37), (38) The stress-strain state of a polar orthotropic disk of a power-law profile with a central rigid core rotating around a diameter is described. The calculation results can be used in the design of working bodies of mechanical flowmeters of liquids and gases, industrial agitators in food and chemical industries, rotors of central stands.

References

1. Kovalenko A.D. *Plates and shells in turbomachine rotors*. Kiev: Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR. 1955.
2. Lehnitsky S.G. *Anisotropic plates*. Moscow: Gostekhizdat. 1958.
3. Alsevich L.A., Cherenkova L.P. *Practicum on differential equations*. Minsk.: Higher School, 1990.
4. Karalevich U.V. *The stress state of a polar-orthotropic disk rotating around a diameter*. *Theoretical and Applied Mechanics (Minsk)*, 1987, vol. No. 14, pp. 77-80.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.16.73.107

DISCOVERIES IN MESOTRONICS AND HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS: A TRIBUTE TO THE JUBILEE OF PROFESSORS IGOR V. MININ AND OLEG V. MININ

Huan Tang

Renxian Li

Doctor (PhD), Associate Professor

School of Physics, Xidian University, Xi'an, China

ABSTRACT. *This March 2025, Professors Igor V. Minin and Oleg V. Minin, Doctors of Physics, correspondent members of Russian Academy of Metrology, outstanding scientists in the field of diffractive optics, mesotronics, terahertz photonics and calculation experiment technology, has marked their 65-th anniversary. This article gives a brief review of their life-time achievements in science and education, who in their scientific work followed the principle of Nikola Tesla: “My main goal was to point out new phenomena and spread the ideas, which will become the starting points for new research”. We briefly analyze the jubilee’s contribution to the development of mesotronics, including photonics, diffractive optics, high-quality real time THz and millimeter wave imaging, Sorlet-Minin-Webb reference phase, shock waves, cumulative jets, field localization by mesoscale particles, unconventional timevariant Fano resonances in a freezing droplets, and generation of extremal magnetic fields, etc.*

Keywords: *diffractive optics; nanophotonics; mesotronics; subwavelength focusing; optical forces, terajet; acoustic jet; photonic hook, hypercumulation*

1. INTRODUCTION

On March 22 born Goethe, Nobel Prize Laureates Robert A. Millikan, Burton Richter, Prof. Boris Luk'yanchuk. On March 22, 2025, we also celebrating 65th birthday of outstanding scientists, teachers, twins and friends, doctors of Technics, professors, corresponding members of the Russian Academy of Metrology Igor Vladilenovich Minin and Oleg Vladilenovich Minin (Figure 1).

This short article is about the scientific results and life of the jubilees, analyzing O. V. Minin's and I. V. Minin's contribution to the creation of new directions in science — mesotronics, 3D diffraction optics of millimeter and THz waves, real-time 3D high-quality THz and millimeter wave imaging, hypercumulations

and plasma physics, subwavelength structured light — photonic hook, nanoparticle manipulation, superresonance, acoustic jet, giant magnetic field generation, and etc. in their unusual scientific trajectory. They also significantly contributed to science popularization in Russia and World, fulfilling the vital task of making scientific knowledge accessible and understandable to the lay public.

Figure 1. Twins, professors Igor V. Minin (left) and Oleg V. Minin (right): from 1962 to 2025.

2. MILESTONES

Oleg and Igor Minin graduated in 1976 with honors from high school and enrolled at the Physical Department of the Novosibirsk State University which they graduated in 1982. I. V. Minin defended his thesis for the degree of candidate of physics and mathematics on radiophysics, including quantum physics at St. Petersburg Electrotechnical Institute in 1986. O. V. Minin defended his thesis for the degree of candidate of physics and mathematics on radiophysics, including quantum physics in Tomsk Institute of Atmospheric Optics, in 1987. At the same time, from 1981 to 1982 they part-time worked as the laboratory assistants at the Institute of Applied Physics (IAP, Novosibirsk). Overall, up to date Profs. Minin has published more than 450 academic papers (many of them are pioneering and define the current state of the relevant areas of fundamental science) in prestigious journals in physics, with a wide range of topics mentioned above. The results of the thesis in 1982, 1988, 1991 formed the basis of the monographs (in Russian), later also translated to English [1–3]. These works were awarded by the Minister of Defense of the Russian Federation (for the best scientific work during 1997–2000). Now, Profs. Minin authored several highly appreciated and widely used textbooks, including 22 monographs (12 in Russian, 9 in English and 1 in Chinese — it was the first Chinese physics textbook in this field, adopted in the universities, extending its readership Russia) and more than 200 author's certificates and patents.

After defending their theses, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin worked in IAP as assistants and senior researchers. In 1991, they received a certificate of associate professors. In March 2004, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin defended their doctoral thesis at the Novosibirsk State Technical University (on the same day) and received degrees of Doctor of Technical Sciences equivalent to a Habilitation degree. Students overwhelmingly adored Professors for their clear explanations and profound insights and rated them as the most popular teachers at NSTU for many successive years. Many of colleagues rightfully commemorate their devoted and dedicated contribution to mesotronics, their readiness to always motivate, inspire, help and support all their colleagues and collaborators. In addition, they are members of the several editorial boards of scientific journals, experts of the Russian Science Foundation, Federal experts in scientific fields, experts of the COST 284 “Innovative Antennas for Emerging Terrestrial & Space-based Applications”, IASTED, and awarded with medals named after A. Nobel and V. I. Vernadsky. The biographical data of Profs. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin were included into Marquis Who’s Who in the World.

I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin have established strong research foundations in different fields of physics having a global priority including millimeter wave and THz real-time imaging and 3D diffractive optics, high-energy physics and hypercumulations, terajet, acoustic jet, photonic and acoustic hook and particle manipulation. They have been awarded a lectureship in different physical area at Doiche Aerospace, DaimlerChrysler AG, Technische Universitat Munchen (Germany), MMW State Key Lab, Nanjing, Harbin Institute of Technology, Beijing Institute of Technology, Capital Normal University (China), Samsung Electronics (Korea), National University of Singapore, Universidad Technica Federico Santa Maria (Chile), and many institutes as invited professors.

3. MAIN SCIENTIFIC RESULTS

Diffractive optics and real-time 3D millimeter wave imaging. An ancient Chinese poet told about fighting helpless problem cause “When all those around me are drunk, I alone am sober”. In the world of science a few decades ago, there were also a lone twins who pursued the field of millimeter wave and THz 3D real-time imaging and optical resolution in the presence of interference noise despite derisions and suspicions. In one of their first works [4] they studied the informative properties of a short-focus zone plate in the millimeter band for imaging systems and for the first time proposed a two-component diffractive lens with a wide field of view [5]. They showed that the synthesis task of even the Fresnel zone plate does not have a unique solution and introduced a new free parameter — the reference radius (called later as Soret-Minin-Webb reference phase) [6,7], which later became known as the reference phase, which allows controlling the quality of focusing [8–15]. Metalenses with a wideband response and low side lobes based

on the fishnet metamaterial by combining the zoning, reference phase, and phase reversal techniques were offered and investigated. The metalenses allow to reduce chromatic aberrations of the focus. New types of diffraction lenses, antennas and antenna arrays for communication systems for the first time were proposed and investigated [16–27]. In particular: correction of dispersion distortion of femtosecond pulses by using the non-planar surface of diffractive lens [19], array of hexagonal Fresnel lens antennas [21], zoning rule for designing Square Fresnel zone plate [22], Fresnel zone plate antenna with hexagonal-cut zones [25], a square Fresnel zone plate with zone rotation principle [2,21,22] with chiral sidelobes, etc. To view three-dimensional space in real-time, the frequency properties of diffraction optics were used for the first time — the dependence of the focal length on the wavelength, later called diffraction tomography [18]. Unique methods for suppressing specular reflections and interference noise in real-time three-dimensional image systems were first proposed, developed and investigated [1,18]. The prototype of such a system made it possible to obtain images in the millimeter band with a quality comparable to optical and was awarded LaserFocusWorld Magazine Diploma (2003) for a series of publications in the field of information and communication technologies and the fight against terrorism. In early 1980, under the guidance of professors V. F. Minin and V. Meriakri (Institute of Radio Engineering and Electronics, Moscow), pioneering studies were begun to construct images of biological objects in the millimeter range and to study the spectral properties of materials, including explosives [28].

I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin were the first to propose a zone plate with a focal length shorter than the wavelength provide superresolution with a minimum size of about a third of the wavelength [29] which was later experimentally confirmed [30]. It has been demonstrated that a similar effect of 3D subwavelength focusing can be achieved using three-dimensional surfaces [31]. To this end, the new flat-ring 3D diffractive lens design was offered which has important constructional and technological advantages. It was shown that it can be easily fabricated at the microwave, higher terahertz and optical frequencies as a planar multilayer package of dielectric rings embedded in a low-permittivity substrate. It was shown that by choosing free parameters in the synthesis of diffraction lenses based on photonic crystals, their focusing properties can be controlled [32–33]. Moreover, it was demonstrated that a photonic crystal lens with defect provides subwavelength localization of the field up to hundredths of a wavelength [34]. Chiral focus diffraction lenses and phase-only chiral binary square axicon have been also proposed by I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin and investigated [35–36] for optical trapping of nanoparticles and biological object manipulations. Based on these knowledge's they show theoretically and experimentally that only a multilevel angular phase contour in the near-field is needed to create structured orbital angular momentum light in the far-field, exploiting the reciprocal nature of angular momentum and angle [37]. In other

words, they showed that it is sufficient to have only three phase levels instead of a continuous phase variation for the generation of a fundamental OAM mode with a high modal purity [37].

Plasma physics, Shock wave and Hypercumulations. New effects of plasma properties with condensed dispersion phase initiated in the air by moving hypervelocity body and plasma antenna formed due to chemoionization of combustion products have been discovered [38,39]. Also the pioneering works in hypercumulation effect allowed to develop the concept of acceleration of microparticles to hypervelocity during ablative acceleration of a metal foil [40,41]. Steve Jobs told “The idea is the most expensive item in the world”. Methods developed by I. V. Minin and O.V. for diffraction optics design made it possible for the first time to focus shock waves in water in an arbitrary region [42–45]. The main processes that proceed during the generation of a shaped-charge jet were described by the M. A. Lavrentyev-Birkhoff (the USSR- the USA) theory as a model of plane stationary impingement of incompressible fluid jets at angles less than 180 degrees. It is a well-known fact confirmed by the almost 100-year practice of designing shaped charges. Under the scientific leadership of Prof. Vladilen F. Minin, we have succeeded to create a fundamentally new field of a numerous family of shaped charges with shaped-charge jets as rods having maximum velocities, the same as those related to the classical shaped-charge effect and insignificant slug (if any). It was found that the maximum jet velocity is not limited by the gas-dynamic limit and, for example, for aluminum or copper liners and conventional explosives, can exceed 20 km/s with a material density in the jet of the order of the density of the liner material and under normal conditions, which is not achievable in classical cumulation [46–51]. The results were summarized in the monograph (in Russian [52]) recently translated to Chinese [53]. In astrophysics a highly collimated cumulative jets were also observed to originate from active nuclei galaxies and young stellar objects. These results also give insight into shock physics.

Involving the physics of crystals in the physics of cumulation, the creation of anisotropic claddings, can provide an increase in the penetration depth of the barrier, eliminate the strong dependence of the properties of the cumulative jet on the grain size in the cladding [51–53]. Impact craters formed by meteorites were also investigated. It is shown that their formation is described by the hydrodynamic flows of such a collision, taking into account the shape of meteorites and the physical characteristics of meteorites and planetary soil at the point of collision. For the contribution to the theory of hypercumulation, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin were awarded the medal of the Russian National Committee on Theoretical and Applied Mechanics named after Rakhmatulin in 2013.

Photonics and Plasmonics at the Mesoscale (Mesotronics). After the discovery in the late 90s of the effect of subwavelength localization of optical radiation

using mesoscale dielectric particles of a cylindrical and spherical shape by B. Lukiyanchuk et al, later called the “photonic nanojet” effect [54], I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin transferred this effect to the terahertz band [55–58]. They were first able to show that this effect is valid for particles of an arbitrary three-dimensional shape, and not just cylinders or spheres [59–64]. Moreover, for the first time, the possibility of subwavelength localization of radiation was shown not only in the transmission mode but also in the reflection mode [65–66]. These studies, in particular, made it possible to propose a new type of optical traps [67] and waveguides [68]. It was shown for the first time that the simple placement of a mesoscale particle, forming a terajet, at the focus of imaging systems allows one to increase both the resolution of the system and the contrast of the image without changing the radiation frequency used [69].

I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin proposed and investigated various methods for increasing the degree of localization of the field using particle-lenses of different shapes based on pupil mask [70–72], graded-index [73], artificial [74] and nanostructured materials [75]. They discovered and studied the effect of anomalous apodization for particle-lens [70–72]. For the first time, for the purposes of subwavelength localization of radiation, dielectric particles with a refractive index near unity were investigated both in the transmission [76] and reflection [77] modes. It was shown that it is possible to adapt the developed methods for the formation of photonic jets for two-dimensional diffraction gratings [78–80]. The result of these works, in particular, was the development of a terahertz microscope [69,81], the concept of optical vacuum cleaner and the principle of optomechanical manipulation of nanoparticles [82] and physical principles of development of the State standard of biological cell polarizability [83]. Studies of the characteristics of terajets in the far-field made it possible for the first time to develop a mesoscopic dielectric cuboid antenna at millimeter-wave and THz (5G) band [84].

Recently, a new type of curved light beam beside the Airy type beam, so-called photonic hook, based on mesoscale Janus particles, has discovered by I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin [64]. Photonic hooks are unique, and intriguing phenomena as their radius of curvature is several times smaller than their wavelength [85,86]. This is the first time that such a small curvature radius of electromagnetic waves has been recorded. The physical properties of photonic hook show important application prospects in the fields of integrated optics, optical imaging, nonlinear optics, etc. The unique application of generating optical force for transporting nanoparticle along a curvilinear trajectory is especially attractive for subwavelength optical micromanipulation of nanoparticles and cell redistribution [87], and lab-on-a-chip system.

A new physical effect — high order Fano resonances for internal Mie modes in low losses dielectric spheres and “super-resonances” with the ability to create highly localized fields with enhancement values on the level of 105, both, inside the particle

and outside in the near field region provides magnetic nanojets with giant magnetic fields, and which is attractive for many applications, were also studied [88]. We also discovered an astonishing large ‘heart-like’ multi-time circulation of Poynting vector 3D field-lines with giant angular variation and circulation range [88].

Photonic hook phenomenon was further extended to the fields of surface plasmons and acoustic waves [89,90]. The principles of the formation of a photonic jet and terajets were transferred to the field of surface plasmon waves. In particular, the possibility of increasing the propagation length of a surface plasmonic wave by several times was demonstrated [91–92] along with new types of plasmonic lenses [93]. A conical two-dimensional plasmonic-zone plate lens was proposed to realize far-field super-resolution focusing by exciting SPPs and enabling them to couple with radiating propagation modes [94]. O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin are pioneers in the field of the effect of the acoustic jet (acoustojet), which is an acoustic analogue of the phenomena of a photonic nanojet and terajet [95–98], as well as acoustic hook [90]. They have also demonstrated the effects of anomalous apodization for acoustic particle lenses [99], as well as the possibility of subwavelength focusing by a cubic lens with a photonic crystal structure [100]. The ability to control the focusing properties of an acoustic zone plate, including the formation of a Bessel beam and reference phase method, has been demonstrated by O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin in [101–103]. New methods for manipulating nanoparticles in droplets have been developed by them as well [104–105].

4. CONCLUSION

Bernhard Baruch claim: “Millions saw the apple fall but Newton was the one who asked why”. Altogether, they vigorously continued the journey into the exciting field of photonics which they called ‘Mesotronics’—the field which became their favorite one in the last time and brought them a lot of enjoyment, new friends, more fame and new scientific links. Among the latest discoveries of Profs. Minins, we note: the superresonance effect [106], new optical toime-domain effects in freezing water droplets [107–109], including the generation of strong magnetic fields, the formation of a photonic jet from a sphere with an index greater than 2, covered with graphene [110], manipulation of microparticles [111] and surface structuring based on a photonic hook [112], astrophysics and high-energy physics [113] and many others. In conclusion, we wish Profs. Igor V. Minin and Oleg V. Minin ongoing scientific endeavors, inexhaustible energy, good health and new creative achievements for the benefit of their country and international scientific community!

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the the Xidian University Specially Funded Project for Interdisciplinary Exploration (TZJHF202524).

REFERENCES

1. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Diffractional Optics of Millimetre Waves*. CRC Press, 2004. — 396 p.
2. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Basic Principles of Fresnel Antenna Arrays*. Springer, 2008.
3. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Three Dimensional Fresnel Antennas 3D*, In: *Advances on Antennas, Reflectors and Beam Control, Research Signpost, Kerala, India, 115–148, 2005*.
4. Baibulatov F. K., Minin I. V., Minin O. V. “Investigation of the focusing properties of the Fresnel zonel plate”. *J. of Communications Technology and Electronics*, 30(9), 1032–1037 (1985).
5. Minin I. V. and Minin O. V. “A wide-angular multicomponent diffraction microwaves lens”. *J. of Communications Technology and Electronics*, 31(4), 801–807 (1986).
6. Minin I. V. and Minin O. V. “Optimization of focusing properties of diffraction elements”. *Sov. Letters to the J. Tech. Phys.* 15(23), 29–33 (1989).
7. Minin I. V. and Minin O. V. “Control of focusing properties of diffraction elements”. *Sov. J. Quantum Electron.* 20(2), 195–196 (1990).
8. S. Stout-Grandy, A. Petosa, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, J. S. Wight. “A Systematic Study of Varying Reference Phase in the Design of Circular Fresnel Zone Plate Antennas”. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 54(12), 3629 (2006).
9. G. W. Webb, I. V. Minin, and O. V. Minin. “New technique to combat multipath fading in wireless networks”, *Proc. SPIE 6248, 62480P*, 24–27 (12 May 2006).
10. G. Webb, I. V. Minin, and Minin O. V. “New technique to suppress sidelobe clutter in perimeter security systems”. *International Journal of High Speed Electronics and Systems*, 12(2), 367 (2007).
11. Stout-Grandy, S.M., Petosa, A., Minin, I.V., Minin, O.V., Wight, J.S. “Recent Advances in Fresnel Zone Plate Antenna Technology”. *Microwave Journal*, paper 6902 (2008).
12. G. W. Webb, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. “Variable Reference Phase in Diffractive Antennas: Review, Applications, New Results”. *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, 53(2), 77–94 (2011).
13. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. “Reference phase in diffractive lens antennas: a review”. *Journal of Infrared, Millimeter, and Terahertz Waves*, 32(6), 801 (2011).
14. V. Pacheco-Peña, M. Navarro-Cía, B. Orazbayev, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin and M. Beruete. “Zoned Fishnet Lens Antenna with Optimal Reference Phase for Side Lobe Reduction”, *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 63(8), 3710 (2015).
15. V. Pacheco-Peña, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, and M. Beruete. “Phase Reversal Technique Applied to Fishnet Metalenses”. *Int. J. of Antennas and Propagation*, Article ID 9461858 (2018).

16. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Elements of diffraction quasioptics: the principal properties". *Optoelectronics, Instrumentation and Data Processing*, 3, 63–68 (1994).
17. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Elements of diffraction quasioptics: the main applications". *Optoelectronics, Instrumentation and Data Processing*, 5, 113–122 (1994).
18. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "System of microwave radiovision of three-dimensional objects in real time", *Proc. SPIE 4129*, (6 July 2000).
19. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Correction of dispersion distortion of femto-second pulses by using the non-planar surface of diffractive optical elements". *Chinese Optics Letters*, 8, 1–3 (2004).
20. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Reduction of the zone shadowing effect in diffractive optical elements on curvilinear surfaces". *Optoelectronics, instrumentation and data processing*, 40, 3 (2004).
21. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, A. Petosa, S. Thirakoune. "Array of Hexagonal Fresnel Zone Plate Lens Antennas". *IEE Electronics Letters*, 42(15), 834 (2006).
22. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin, A. Petosa, S. Thirakoune. "Improved Zoning Rule for Designing Square Fresnel Zone Plate Lenses". *Microwave and Opt. Tech. Lett.*, 49(2), 276 (2007).
23. S. Stout-Grandy, A. Petosa, A., I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, J. Wight. "Novel Reflector Backed Fresnel Zone Plate Antenna". *Microwave and Opt. Tech. Lett.*, 49(12), 3096 (2007).
24. S. Stout-Grandy, A. Petosa, A., I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, J. Wight. "Investigation of Low Profile Fresnel Zone Plate Antennas". *Microwave and Opt. Tech. Lett.*, 50, 2039–2043 (2008).
25. S. Stout-Grandy, A. Petosa, A., I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, J. Wight. "Fresnel zone plate antenna with hexagonal-cut zones". *Microwave and Opt. Tech. Lett.*, 50, 672 (2008).
26. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Active MMW/Terahertz Security System Based on Bessel Beams". *ISRN optics*, Article ID 285127 (2013).
27. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Millimeter wave binary photon sieve Fresnel zone plate: FDTD analysis". *Progress In Electromagnetics Research Letters*, 43, 149 (2013).
28. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "System of microwave radiovision of three-dimensional objects in real time", *Proc. SPIE 4129*, (6 July 2000); doi: 10.1117/12.390666.
29. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, N. Gagnon, A. Petosa. "Investigation of the resolution of phase correcting Fresnel lenses with small values of F/D and subwavelength focus". *Computer Optics*, 30(65) (2006).
30. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Experimental verification 3D subwavelength resolution beyond the diffraction limit with zone plate in millimeter wave". *Microwave and Opt. Technol. Lett.*, 56(10), 2436 (2014).
31. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "3D diffractive lenses to overcome the 3D Abbe subwavelength diffraction limit". *Chinese Optics Letters*, 12(6), 060014 (2014).

32. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, Y. R. Triandaphilov, V. V. Kotlyar. "Subwavelength diffractive photonic crystal lens". *Progress In Electromagnetics Research B*, 257 (2008).

33. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, Y. R. Triandaphilov, V. V. Kotlyar. "Focusing Properties of Two Types of Diffractive Photonic Crystal Lens". *Optical Memory & Neural Networks*, 17(3), 244 (2008).

34. Y. Li, Y. Fu, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. "Ultra-sharp nanofocusing of graded index photonic crystals-based lenses perforated with optimized single defect," *Optical Materials Express*, 6(8) (2016).

35. A. Vijayakumar, I. V. Minin, J. Rosen, and O. V. Minin. "Experimental demonstration of Square Fresnel zone plate with chiral side lobes," *Appl Optics*, 56(13) (2017).

36. B. Vinoth, A. Vijayakumar, M. Rai, J. Rosen, C.-J. Cheng, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, "Binary square axicon with chiral focusing properties for optical trapping," *Opt. Eng.* 59(4), 041204 (2019).

37. A. Vijayakumar, C. Rosales-Guzman, M. R. Rai, J. Rosen, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, and A. Forbes. "Generation of structured light by multilevel orbital angular momentum holograms." *Opt. express*, 27(5), 6459–6470 (2019).

38. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "The influence of the grain size of microstructure of the surface layer material of a hypersonic body on the properties of air plasma". *Computer Optics*, 20, 93–96 (2000).

39. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "The influence of the grain size of microstructure of the surface layer material of a hypersonic body on the properties of air plasma". *The 10th Electromagnetic Launch Technology Symposium, Institute for Advanced Technology, San Francisco, California, USA, April 25–28, (2000).*

40. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Cumulative plasma jet formation for acceleration of macroparticles." *9th Korean-Russian Int. Symp. on Science & Technology (KORUS 2005), June 26 ~ July 2, Novosibirsk, Russia (2005)*

41. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Physics of Hypercumulative Plasma Jet Formation by Ablatively-Driven Implosion of Hollow Cones." *American Journal of Modern Physics*. 2(6), 299 (2013).

42. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "The Dynamics of shock wave focusing with the elements of diffraction quasioptics." *Book of abstracts the 18th Int. Symp. on SW. Sendai July 21–26 (1991).*

43. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "The calculation experiment technology." *Proc. of the 2nd Int. Symp. on Intence Dynamics loading and its effects Chengdu, China June 9–12 (1992).*

44. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "The numerical experiments on dynamics of shock wave interaction with regular and quasiregular diffraction gratings." *Proc. of the 2nd Int. Symp. on Intence Dynamics loading and its effects Chengdu, China June 9–12 (1992).*

45. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Generation of strong shock waves at the action of ring modulated laser beam radiation on the target." *9th Korean-Russian Int. Symp. on Science & Technology (KORUS 2005)*, June 26 ~ July 2, Novosibirsk, Russia (2005).

46. Minin I. V. and Minin O. V. "Analytical and computation experiments on forced plasma jet formation." *Proc. of the Int. Symp. on Intense Dynamic Loading and Its Effects*. Chengdu, China, June 9–12, 588–591 (1992).

47. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Physics of hypercumulation and combined shaped charges. *Proc. 11TH Int. Conf. on Actual Problems of Electronic Instr. Eng. (APEIE) — 30057, 2rd — 4th October; 34–52 (2012)*.

48. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Criterion of a Jet Formation on the Axisymmetrical Shaped Charge." *Int. J. of Modern Applied Physics*, 2(3), 130 (2013).

49. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. "Explosive Synthesis of Diamond-Like Boron-Nitride." *Int. J. of Modern Applied Physics*, 2(3), 167 (2013).

50. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. "Hypervelocity fragment formation technology for ground-based laboratory tests." *Acta Astronautica*, 104(1), 77 (2014).

51. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. "Some Possibilities of Hypercumulative Regime of Jet Formations." *Applied Mechanics and Materials* 782, 42 (2015).

52. V. F. Minin, I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. *Physics of hypercumulations and combined shaped charges*. Novosibirsk, 2013 (in Russian).

53. 米宁B.Ф., 米宁И.В., 米宁O.B. *超聚能和组合聚能射孔弹物理学*, National Defense Industry Press, 2019.

54. B. S. Lukiyanchuk, R. Paniagua-Domínguez, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin and W. Zengbo. "Refractive index less than two: photonic nanojets yesterday, today and tomorrow invited.." *Optical material express*, 7(6), 1820–1847 (2017).

55. V. Pacheco-Pena, M. Beruete, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. "Terajets produced by 3D dielectric cuboids." *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 105, 084102 (2014).

56. V. Pacheco-Peña, M. Beruete, I. V. Minin, and O. V. Minin. "Multifrequency focusing and wide angular scanning of terajets." *Opt. Lett.*, 40(2), 245 (2015).

57. N. P. Hai-Huy, S. Hisatake, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, T. Nagatsuma. "Three-dimensional direct observation of Gouy phase shift in a terajet produced by a dielectric cuboid." *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 108(19) (2016).

58. H. Pham, S. Hisatake, O. V. Minin, T. Nagatsuma and I. V. Minin. "Asymmetric Phase Anomaly of Terajet Generated from Dielectric Cube under Oblique Illumination." *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 110(20), 201105 (2017)

59. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, Geintz Y. E. „Localized EM and photonic jets from non-spherical and non-symmetrical dielectric mesoscale objects: brief review." *Annalen der Physik (AdP)*, 527(7–8), 491 (2015)

60. I. Mahariq, I. Giden, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, and H. Kurt. "Strong electromagnetic field localization near the surface of hemicylindrical particles." *Opt. and Quant. Electron.* 49, 423 (2017).

61. Yu. E. Geints, Oleg V. Minin and Igor V. Minin. "Systematic study and comparison of photonic nanojets produced by dielectric microparticles in 2D- and 3D- spatial configurations." *J. of Optics*, 20, 065606 (2018).

62. Y. Geints, I. V. Minin, E. Panina, A. Zemlyanov, and O. V. Minin. "Comparison of photonic nanojets key parameters produced by nonspherical microparticles". *Opt. and Quant. Electron.* 49, 118 (2017).

63. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, L. Yue. "Electromagnetic properties of the pyramids from the photonics position." *Russian Physics Journal*, 62(10), 12–18 (2019).

64. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Diffraction optics and nanophotonics: Resolution below the diffraction limit*, Springer, 2015

65. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, V. Pacheco-Peña, and M. Beruete. "Localized photonic jets from flat, three-dimensional dielectric cuboids in the reflection mode." *Opt. Lett.*, 40(10), 2329 (2015).

66. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, and I. Nefedov. "Photonic jets from Babinet's cuboid structures in the reflection mode." *Opt. Lett.*, 41(3) (2016).

67. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, V. Pacheco-Peña, M. Beruete. "Subwavelength, standing-wave optical trap based on photonic jets." *Quantum Electronics*, 46(6), 555–557 (2016).

68. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, V. Pacheco-Peña, M. Beruete. "All-dielectric periodic terajet waveguide using an array of coupled cuboids." *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 106, 254102 (2015).

69. H.-H. N. Pham, S. Hisatake, O. V. Minin, T. Nagatsuma and I. V. Minin. "Enhancement of Spatial Resolution of Terahertz Imaging Systems Based on Terajet Generation by Dielectric Cube," *APL Photonics* 2, 056106 (2017).

70. L. Yue, B. Yan, J. Monks, Z. Wang, N. Tung, V. Lam, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. "Production of photonic nanojets by using pupil-masked 3D dielectric cuboid," *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 50, 175102 (2017).

71. L. Yue, B. Yan, J. Monks, Z. Wang, N. Tung, V. Lam, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. "A millimetre-wave cuboid solid immersion lens with intensity-enhanced amplitude mask apodization." *J. of Infrared, Millimeter, and Terahertz Waves*, 39(6), 546–552 (2018).

72. L. Yue, B. Yan, J. N. Monks, Z. Wang, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. "Intensity-enhanced apodization effect on an axially illuminated circular-column particle-lens." *Annalen der Physik*, 530(2), 1700384 (2017).

73. C.-Y. Liu, T.-P. Yen, O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin. "Engineering photonic nanojet by a graded-index micro-cuboid." *Physica E*: 98, 105–110 (2018).

74. O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin. "Terahertz artificial dielectric cuboid lens on substrate for super-resolution images." *Opt. and Quant. Electronics* 49, 326–9 (2017).

75. Y. Cao, Z. Liu, O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin. “Deep subwavelength-scale light focusing and confinement in nanohole-structured mesoscale dielectric spheres.” *Nanomaterials*, 9(2), 186 (2019).

76. C.-Y. Liu, O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin. “Periodical focusing mode achieved through a chain of mesoscale dielectric particles with a refractive index near unity.” *Optics Communications* 434, 110–117 (2019).

77. L. Yue, B. Yan, J. N. Monks, R. Dhama, Z. Wang, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. “Photonic jet by a near-unity-refractive-index sphere on a dielectric substrate with high index contrast.” *Annalen der Physik* 1800032 (2018).

78. C.-Y. Liu, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. “First experimental observation of array of photonic jets from saw-tooth phase diffraction grating.” *EPL*, 123, 54003 (2018).

79. Yu. Geints, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin. “Apodization — assisted subdiffraction near-field focusing in 2D phase diffraction grating.” *Annalen der Physik*, 531(7), 1900033 (2019).

80. Y. E. Geints, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin and A. A. Zemlyanov. “Self-images contrast enhancement for displacement Talbot lithography by means of composite mesoscale amplitude-phase masks.” *J. of Optics*, 22(1), 015002 (2019).

81. N. Chernomyrdin, A. Kucheryavenko, G. Kolontaeva, G. Katyba, P. Karalkin, V. Parfenov, A. Gryadunova, N. Norkin, O. Smolyanskaya, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, V. Karasik, K. Zaytsev. “A potential of terahertz solid immersion microscopy for visualizing sub-wavelength-scale tissue spheroids.” *Proc. SPIE* 10677, 106771Y (24 May 2018).

82. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, Y. Cao, Z. Liu, Y. Geints, and A. Karabchevsky. “Optical vacuum cleaner by optomechanical manipulation of nanoparticles using nanostructured mesoscale dielectric cuboid.” *Scientific Reports* 9:12748 (2019)

83. G. V. Shuvalov, K. V. Generalov, V. M. Generalov, M. V. Kruchinina, E. S. Koptev, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. “Physical principles of development of the State standard of biological cell polarizability.” *Russian Physics Journal*, 60(11), 1901 (2018).

84. Y. Samura, K. Horio, V. Antipov, S. Shipilov, A. Ereemeev, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, and S. Hisatake. “Characterization of Mesoscopic Dielectric Cuboid Antenna at Millimeter-wave Band.” *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, 18(9), 1828 (2019).

85. L. Yue, O. V. Minin, Z. Wang, J. Monks, A. Shalin and I. V. Minin. “Photonic hook: A new curved light beam.” *Opt. Lett.*, 43(4), 771–774 (2018).

86. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, G. M. Katyba, N. V. Chernomyrdin, V. N. Kurlov, K. I. Zaytsev, L. Yue, Z. Wang, and D. N. Christodoulides. “Experimental observation of a photonic hook.” *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 114(3), 031105 (2019); I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, L. Yue, Z. Wang, V. S. Volkov, and D. N. Christodoulides. “Photonic hook — a new type of subwavelength self-bending structured light beams: a tutorial review.” *ArXiv: 1910.09543* (2019).

87. A. S. Ang, A. Karabchevsky, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, S. V. Sukhov, and A. S. Shalin. "Photonic Hook based optomechanical nanoparticle manipulator." *Scientific Reports* 8:2029 (2018).

88. Z. Wang, B. Luk'yanchuk, L. Yue, R. Paniagua-Domínguez, B. Yan, J. Monks, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, S. Huang and A. A. Fedyanin. "High order Fano resonances and giant magnetic fields in dielectric microspheres." *Scientific Reports* 9:20293 (2019); L. Yue, B. Yan, J. Monks, R. Dhama, C. Jiang, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin & Z. Wong. "Full three-dimensional Poynting vector flow analysis of great field-intensity enhancement in specifically sized spherical-particles." *Scientific Reports* 9, 20224 (2019).

89. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, D. S. Ponomarev, and I. A. Glinsky. "Photonic hook plasmons: a new curved surface wave." *Annalen der Physik*, 1800359 (2018).

90. C. Rubio, D. Tarrazó-Serrano, O. V. Minin, A. Uris, and I. V. Minin, "Acoustical hooks: a new subwavelength self-bending beam," *Results in Physics*, 16, 102921 (2020).

91. V. Pacheco-Peña, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin and M. Beruete. "Comprehensive analysis of photonic nanojets in 3D dielectric cuboids excited by surface plasmons." *Annalen der physic*, 1–9 (2016).

92. V. Pacheco-Peña, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin and M. Beruete. "Increasing Surface Plasmons Propagation via Photonic Nanojets with Periodically Spaced 3D Dielectric Cuboids." *Photonics* 3, 10 (2016).

93. Minin I. V. and Minin O. V. "3D Diffractive Focusing of Surface Plasmon Polariton Waves." *J. of Electromagnetic Analysis and Appl.*, 2(2), 116 (2009).

94. R. G. Mote, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin. "Focusing behavior of 2-dimensional plasmonic conical zone plate." *Opt. Quant. Electron.* 49, 271 (2017).

95. O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin. "Acoustojet: acoustic analogue of photonic jet phenomenon based on penetrable 3D particle." *Opt. Quant. Electron.* 49, 54 (2017).

96. C. Rubio, D. Tarrazó-Serrano, O. V. Minin, A. Uris, I. V. Minin. "Sound focusing of wavelength scale gas-filled flat lens." *EPL*, 123, 64002 (2018).

97. S. Perez-Lopez, J. M. Fuster, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin and P. Candelas. "Tunable subwavelength ultrasound focusing in spherical lenses using liquid mixtures." *Sci. Rep.* 9, 13363 (2019).

98. S. Perez-Lopez, P. Candelas, J. M. Fuster, C. Rubio, O. V. Minin and I. V. Minin. "Liquid-liquid core-shell configurable mesoscale spherical acoustic lens with subwavelength focusing." *Appl. Phys. Express* 12, 087001 (2019)

99. C. Rubio, D. Tarrazó-Serrano, O. V. Minin, A. Uris, I. V. Minin. "Enhancement of pupil-masked wavelength-scale gas-filled flat acoustic lens based on anomaly apodization effect." *Physics Letters A*, 383(5), 396 (2019).

100. S. Castiñeira-Ibáñez, D. Tarrazó-Ibáñez, P. Candelas, O. V. Minin, C. Rubio and I. V. Minin. "3D sound wave focusing by 2D internal periodic structure of 3D external cuboid shape." *Results in Physics* 15, 102582 (2019).

101. Daniel Tarrazo-Serrano, Sergio Castieira-Ibanez, Oleg V. Minin, Constanza Rubio, and Igor V. Minin. "Tunable depth of focus of acoustical pupil masked Soret Zone Plate." *Sensors & Actuators: A. Physical*, 286 (2019).

102. Daniel Tarrazo-Serrano, Constanza Rubio, Oleg V. Minin, Pilar Candelas, Igor V. Minin. "Manipulation of focal patterns in acoustic Soret type ZP lens by using reference radius/phase effect." *Ultrasonics* 91, 237–241 (2019).

103. D. Dolmatov, D. Tarrazó-Serrano, G. Filippov, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, and D. Sednev. "Application of Phase-Reversal Fresnel Zone Plates for Improving The Elevation Resolution in Ultrasonic Testing with Phased Arrays. *Sensors*," 19, 5080 (2019).

104. X. Qi, Q. Tang, P. Liu, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, J. Hu. "Controlled concentration and transportation of nanoparticles at the interface between an ordinary substrate and droplet." *Sensors & Actuators: B.*, 274, 381–392 (2018).

105. Q. Liu, J. Hu, I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. "High-performance ultrasonic tweezers for manipulations of motile and still single cells in a droplet." *Ultrasound in Medicine and Biology*, 45(11), 3018–3027 (2019).

106. I. V. Minin and O. V. Minin. *The Superresonance: The Discovery That Was Not Done More Than One Hundred Years Ago. Atmospheric and Oceanic Optics* 37(3), 293–301 (2024).

107. O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, and Y. Cao. "Time Domain Self—bending Photonic Hook Beam Based on Freezing Water Droplet." *Sci. Rep.* 13, 7732 (2023).

108. O. V. Minin, Y. Cao and I. V. Minin. *Future Green Technology: A Freezing Water Micro-Droplet as an Optical Switch Based on a Time-Domain Photonic Hook. Nanomaterials* 13, 2168 (2023).

109. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, S. Zhou and B. S. Luk'yanchuk. *High order Fano resonance in the time domain for a freezing water microdroplet. Sci Rep* 14, 24118 (2024).

110. A. G. Paddubskaya, A. V. Novitsky, O. V. Minin, and I. V. Minin. *Fano-resonant mechanism of terajet formation using graphene-covered high index mesoscale spheres. Optics Letters* 49(18), 5175–5178 (2024).

111. W.-Y. Chen, T.-Y. Hung, Y.-K. Hsieh, L. P.-H. Li, Y.-B. Chen, O. V. Minin, I. V. Minin, C.-Y. Liu. *Numerical and experimental demonstrations of optical trapping and manipulation of a selective red blood cell using a photonic hook based on broken symmetry tapered fiber probe. Opt Las Tech* 180, 111520 (2025).

112. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin, *Experimental Demonstration of the Microprocessing of the Polystyrene Surface Using a Photonic Hook. JEPT Letters* 120(2), 146–150 (2024).

113. Baranov, P.F.; Zatonov, I.A. "Some pioneering research in laboratory simulation of scaled astrophysical phenomena by Russian physicists". *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1709, 012003 (2020).

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.17.96.090

UDC 544.77.

SORPTION METHOD FOR INDUSTRIAL WATER PURIFICATION

Ybraimzhanova Laura Kairoldayevna

Master of Technical Sciences, Lecturer

*Zhetysu University named after I. Zhansugurov, Taldykorgan,
Kazakhstan*

Bektenov Nessipkhan Abzhaparovich

Doctor of Chemical Sciences, Professor

Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-1427-438X

Abstract. Derivatization of effective and economically beneficial sorbents for wide application is relevant in this research direction. Changing the structure of sorbents for treatment industrial effluents and various wastewaters is especially in demand in science and industry. Natural ion-exchange sorbents make possible to solve two related problems at once: treatment industrial effluents of enterprises and improvement the state of the environment from pollutants. Modification of ion exchangers of natural sorbents brings to improvement of sorption and kinetic characteristics, especially promising natural highly permeable cross-linked polyelectrolyte with big rate of absorption of large ions. Modification of these minerals with a surface layer of copolymers with epoxy groups obtained by curing a mixture of phosphoric acid and phosphoric acid allows to get new cheap sorption materials for purifying water from heavy metals, mainly lead cations Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} . The work being carried out was conditioned by the need to clean industrial effluents of the Tekeli Mining and Processing Complex from Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} cations which are classified as heavy metals, exhibiting mutagenic, carcinogenic properties. In addition, ions built into biogenic forms have the ability to accumulate locally in natural objects, thereby being a strong ecotoxicant.

Goal: to improve the sorption properties of natural zeolite sorbent by modifying the ion exchange structure regarding Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} ions and to solve the problem of new highly-efficient sorbents for wastewater treatment.

Objects: The Shankhanai natural zeolite and its modified acrylamide and phosphoric acid forms.

Results. Sorbents modified with phosphoric acid and phosphoric acid were obtained based on the Shankhanai natural zeolite. The optimal pH conditions for sorption of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} ions have been established in static conditions. Using modified natural zeolite in the range pH 7–9, the extraction of lead and copper ions occurs by 90–92% compared to the original zeolite. Modified natural zeolite can be used as a sorption material for treatment of industrial effluents and wastewater.

Index Terms — the Shankhanai natural zeolite, sorbent, cation, sorption, phosphoric acid.

INTRODUCTION

Lead ions are persistent ecotoxicants with low speed removal from ecosystems and human body. Significant bioaccumulation led to inclusion of lead and copper ions Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} to European Union checklists according to directive EU 2013/39 [1, 2] under control regulations on heavy ions metals content in the environment objects. Concentration of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} in rivers water may differ from 0.1 to 100 $\mu\text{g/l}$, with the average value usually not exceeding 10 $\mu\text{g/l}$, for copper from 0.01 to 70 $\mu\text{g/l}$, the average value 7 $\mu\text{g/l}$. In stagnant water bodies this value is lower and amounts to 4.5 $\mu\text{g/l}$ for Pb^{2+} and 2.0 for Cu^{2+} [3]. Permissible content of Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} in drinking water is in the range 1–60 $\mu\text{g/l}$ depending on the region, wherein in Europe and Russia it does not exceed 20–25 $\mu\text{g/l}$ [4].

Taking into account the amount of consumed water, physicochemical adsorption is the most attractive cleaning approach, owing to wide assortment of developed sorbents, low power consumption and high efficiency [5, 6]. Conventional wastewater treatment plants are effective for organic matters, but removing heavy metals ions does not always happen completely, which makes additional treatment and water quality control necessary. Synthetic ion exchange materials are effective sorbents for Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} , as well as for all heavy metals, and modified ion exchangers become the most common [7]. The developed and widespread synthetic sorbents provide high removal speed, but their high cost is a disadvantage in the industrial scale. Thus, the search for an alternative in the form of economically beneficial natural sorbents with effortless modification of the surface with accessible reagents is an urgent necessity [8]. The researches demonstrated the efficiency of using absorbent carbon, carbon nanotubes, and natural and synthetic sorbents for this purpose [9, 10]. Usage of Kazakhstani natural deposits of zeolites provide new natural materials both for intensive development of fundamental research on sorbents and for practical application. The study of the chemical and phase composition of zeolite tuffs of the Shankhanai deposit showed the possibility of practical use of Kazakhstani zeolites [11]. It has been established that such zeolites,

where the main component is montmorillonite (60-70%) $Al_2[Si_4O_{10}](OH)_2 \cdot nH_2O$, which is a sheet silicate with an expanding structural cell and has high swelling, is an effective adsorbent for polluted water cleaning [12]. For example, to remove heavy metal ions from water it is recommended to use mesoporous zeolite sorbent faujasite, the surface of which is treated with alkali [13].

Scientists studied zeolite modified with a mixture of oxidized polyethylene and polypropylene, used for removal ions Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} from water [14]. The process of water purification from Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} using natural zeolite of the Muinak deposit (Karakalpakstan) has been studied in concentrations range in water 0.5–3.5 mEq/l. It has been established that surface modification with sulfuric acid brings to activation of functional groups and an increase in its efficiency [15]. These results indicate that modified natural zeolites are promising inexpensive materials for cleaning water from heavy metals [16].

Analytical methods of defining Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions involve usage of fiery and electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry with graphite furnace (GFAAS), atomic inductively coupled plasm of emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) with inductively coupled plasm (ICP-MS) [17–21]. These methods have sufficient sensitivity, but some of them are very expensive and not accessible for ordinary analytical laboratories. Low concentrations of lead and copper cations can be detected by method of fluorescent spectrometry [22] with a high degree of accuracy and repeatability, in a short analysis time [23]. Low for most methods level of toxic presence of metals does not match instrumental sensitivity that requires use preliminary concentration on sorbents. The spectrophotometric method is the most effective in terms of the ratio of sensitivity of analytical characteristics and use of labor intensity [24–27]. It is possible to increase the sensitivity of this kind by adding a selective organic reagent which converts the ion being determined into a chromogenic compound [28].

The object of our research is the assessment of change the sorption properties of the Mykry natural zeolite and its modification with double copolymer of glycidyl methacrylate (GMA), methyl methacrylate (MMA) and oxyethylene diphosphonic acid complexone (HEDP) regarding to Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} due to such factors as pH environment, ion concentration in solution and time contact.

Materials and methods

Review Stage

Zeolite from the Shankhanai deposit, Kerbulak district, Zhetysu Region, Republic of Kazakhstan. The study was carried out by preliminary grinding the mineral to a grain diameter of 0.4 mm. To increase the extraction capacity and selectivity of the natural Shankhanai zeolite, the sorbent was modified with a double

copolymer of glycidyl methacrylate (GMA), methyl methacrylate (MMA) and oxyethylene diphosphonic acid complexone (HEDP). 100 g of the resulting zeolite powder was added GMA weighing thirty g until the surface was completely covered, then 30 g of MMA was added in small portions and stirred for 10 minutes. The resulting mass was unloaded into porcelain cups and dried in the dryer closet for 10 hours at the temperature of 120°C. Then the mass was taken out and cooled at room temperature for 12 hours. The samples of the resulting modified zeolite were processed with 5% HCl solution to regenerate the chloride form, then brought to neutral pH by washing with water and treated with 5% solution of NaOH. The received modified zeolite was dried to constant weight in a muffle ovens at a temperature of 120°C. Anion exchange capacity of the product (SEC, mEq/g) was defined in static conditions 0.1 H each solution [29,30,34].

Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺ were defined using a spectrophotometer in solution after sorption connected with formation of the complex compound, which can be characterized by interaction of Pb²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions with sulfarsazen. This complex compound turned into yellow-orange [30,31,33,35]. Solutions of 10 mg/l Pb(NO₃) and 10 mg/l Cu(NO₃)₂, 0.05M Na₂B₄O₇, 0.1M HNO₃, 0.1M NaOH were used in the study. Basic salt solutions were prepared according to exact hanging, the solutions of smaller concentrations were added sequentially as dilution of original solutions directly before use. The solutions of 0.05% sulfarsazene were prepared by dissolving in 0.05 mol/l Na₂B₄O₇. For all solutions we used double-distilled water.

The static sorption capacity of the sorbent was calculated according to the formula [32,33,36]:

$$A(\text{Pb}^{2+}) = ((C_{\text{ref}} - C_{\text{equal}}))/m$$

where A (Pb²⁺) – sorbent capacity, mg/g; C_{ref} and C_{equal} – initial and equilibrium (residual) concentrations metal ions in solution, respectively, mg/l; V – solution volume, l; m – weight sorbent, G.

Extraction rate of metals ions (E,%) was calculated by formula:

$$E = \frac{(C_{\text{ref}} - C_{\text{equal}})}{C_0} * 100\%$$

where C_{ref} is the initial concentration of the metal ion in the solution, mg/l; C_{equal} (residual) concentration of metal ion in the solution, mg/l.

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out on spectrophotometer UV-1800 (Shimadzu, Japan). Optical density was measured at waves length 530 nm in cuvettes with a layer thickness of 1 cm. MultiBio RS-24 multirotator was used for mixing (BioSan, Latvia).

Final Stage

The sorption of Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions by natural zeolite and its modified acrylamide and phosphoric acid forms in the interval of pH from 1.68 before 12.45. Quantitative definition of lead and copper ions in aqueous solutions were carried out according to preliminary made graduated schedule. (figure 1). The research showed that maximum sorption capacity (figure 2) of the modified form (MF) in these conditions for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} is 0.7 mg/g, for natural zeolite (NZ) 0.3 mg/g at pH 6.80, in such conditions, the sorption of MF is higher than on NZ by 55%. At pH 9.3, the sorption on MF is 92% higher. Study of influence of pH on the amount of sorption of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} ions from water solutions on NZ and its MF depending on pH environment showed that the optimal acidity of the medium for lead and copper sorption is the pH range 6.80-9.3. If it is higher than this interval, then hydroxyl complex of lead ions appears, if it is below the interval, use of sulfarsazene brings to emergence of unstable composition complexes.

Figure 1. Calibration dependence for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} determination by sulfarsazene in aqueous solution

Duration of sorbent contact with Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} solution affects the degree of extraction (Figure 3). The sorption value increases with enhancing contact duration, then after 90 minutes it becomes constant. By the results of modification of the natural zeolite with acrylamide and phosphoric acid, it is shown the increase in sorption capacity for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} ions, which is manifested in change of sorption isotherms (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Comparative characteristics of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} sorption of natural zeolite (1) and its modified form (2) depending on pH medium

Figure 3. Comparative characteristics of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} sorption of natural zeolite (1) and its modified form (2) in a neutral medium depending on the contact time

Sorption capacity for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} significantly higher in comparison with NZ. The amount of sorbed Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} increases with enhancing concentration of the initial solution. At, Pb^{2+} concentration in the original solution is less 0.01 mol/l –1 almost complete sorption achieved Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} . The NZ isotherm sorption has an L-shape. A uniform surface filling and lack of competition of the solvent is

characteristic for class L isotherm. The process of reorientation of associates of lead and copper complexes is possible relatively to sorbent surface.

The MF sorption isotherm has an S-shape form with concave initial site. At increasing concentrations of sorbate in solution sorption capacity of the sorbent enhances, which is associated with change in the orientation of the adsorbed ions of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} relatively to the sorbent surface or with rapid transition to poly-molecular adsorption. Further the inflexion point follows, and the second plateau appears, which gives such isotherms characteristic S-shaped view. The reason is in strong interaction between adsorbed cations of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} with simultaneous weakening their interactions with the sorbent surface, in this case adsorbed cations of Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} strive to settle down on surfaces in the form of clusters. Experimental data and parameters of Langmuir isotherms for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} sorption, with samples of NZ and MF are presented in the table below

Table 1. Experimental data of , sorption with natural zeolite and its modified form samples and the results of their processing

Modified form			The Langmuir equation	
C, mol/l	Cs, mol/l	a, mol/g	1/Cs	1/a
0.05	0.06	0.26	17.41	3.88
0.10	0.08	0.72	12.19	1.38
0.25	0.46	4.38	2.18	0.23
0.50	0.49	5.32	2.04	0.19
0.75	0.50	6.87	2.01	0.15
1.00	0.22	8.21	4.45	0.12
Natural zeolite			The Langmuir equation	
C, mol/l	Cs, mol/l	a, mol/g	1/Cs	1/a
0.05	0.01	0.28	134,6	3.54
0.10	0.09	0.72	10,67	1.40
0.25	0.56	4.33	1,78	0.23
0.5	0.59	5.27	1,70	0.19
0.74	0.72	6.77	1,42	0.16
1.00	1.48	7.59	0,67	0.14

Figure 4. Isotherm of natural zeolite (a) and its modified form (b)

Figure 5. Parameters of the Langmuir isotherms for Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} sorption with samples of modified form (A) and natural zeolite (B)

Graphic and calculated data show an increase in sorption capacity of the modified zeolite, which is connected with increase the quantity of functional groups on sorbent surface

Conclusion

The modified natural sorbent has been obtained based on the Shankhanai natural zeolite and its modified acrylamide and phosphoric acid forms. Optimal pH has been established from 7 to 9 for purifying water from lead and copper ions. The pH medium plays an important role in the sorption of metal ions, since changes in its value improve dissociation of the functional groups of the ion exchanger. The sorption capacity of the ion exchanger is 41.22 mg/g, the degree of extraction reaches up to 92%. Thus, to achieve completeness of extraction it is necessary two times less modified sorbent in neutral environment and five times less in a slightly alkaline environment. The sorption time does not exceed 90 minutes. Modified natural zeolite can be effectively used as a sorption material for sewage water treatment.

With support: This article is published as part of a project funded by the research grant for young scientists for scientific and/or scientific-technical projects «Zhas Gylym» for the years 2025-2027, funded by the Committee of Science of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, under the IRN project: AP25796791 «Modification of natural zeolite with extracts to improve its sorption properties for the treatment of wastewater containing heavy metals».

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

1. Yan L. et al. Adsorption of acid dyes from aqueous solution by CTMAB modified bentonite: Kinetic and isotherm modeling. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 2015, vol. 211, pp. 1074–1081. DOI: 10.1016/j.molliq.2015.08.032.
2. Summary data on mineral resources. National Information Center for Mineral Resources. Statistical data and information on global supply, demand for sorbents and their movement. USA, 2022. Available at: <https://www.usgs.gov/centers/nationalminerals-information-center/potash-statistics-and-information> (accessed February 3, 2023).
3. Stepanov S., Strelkov A., Panfilova O. Removal of heavy metals from wastewater with natural and modified sorbents. *Magazine of Civil Engineering*, 2022, vol. 111, № 3, pp. 11110.
4. Kambarova E. A., Gavrilenko M. A., Bektenov N. A. Zeolites modified with polyethylene polyamine and epoxy resin for the extraction of lead ions from wastewater. *Journal article, Bulletin of Tomsk Polytechnic University, Geo Assets Engineering*, 2021, vol. 332, № 1, pp.7–13.
5. Wang Q, Zhu S, Xi C, Zhang F (2022). A review: adsorption and removal of heavy metals based on polyamide-amines composites. *Front Chem*, 04 March 2022 Sec. Green and Sustainable Chemistry Volume 10–2022 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2022.814643>
6. Jiang N. High-silica zeolites for adsorption of organic micro-pollutants in water treatment: A review *Water research*. 2018, vol. 144, pp. 145–161. DOI:10.1016/j.watres.2018.07.017.
7. Mohamed A. Tagoon, Saifeldin M. Siddeeg, Norah Salem Alsaiari, Wissem Mnif and Faouzi Ben Rebah(2020). Effective Heavy Metals Removal from Water Using Nanomaterials: This article belongs to the Special Issue Gas, Water and Solid Waste Treatment Technology A Review Processes 2020, 8(6), 645; <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr8060645>.

8. Scandelay A. P. J. et al. Intensification of supercritical water oxidation (ScWO) process for landfill leachate treatment through ion exchange with zeolite. *Waste Management*, 2020, vol.101, pp. 259–267. DOI:10.1016/j.wasman.2019.10.005.
9. Radhakrishnan K., Sivanesan S., Panneerselvam P. Turn-On fluorescence sensor based detection of heavy metal ion using carbon dots graphitic-carbon nitride nanocomposite probe. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 2020, vol. 389, pp. 112204. DOI:10.1016/j.jphotochem.2019.112204.
10. Sulaiman K. O., Sajid M., Alhooshani K. Application of porous membrane bag enclosed alkaline treated Y-Zeolite for removal of heavy metal ions from water. *Microchemical Journal*, 2020, vol. 152, pp. 104289. DOI:10.1016/j.microc.2019.104289.
11. Tarighat M. A. Orthogonal projection approach and continuous wavelet transform-feed forward neural networks for simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of some heavy metals in diet samples. *Food Chemistry*, 2016, vol. 192, pp. 548–556. DOI:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.07.034.
12. Strelkov A. K., Stepanov S. V., Panfilova O. N., Arbuzov A. V. Post-treatment of wastewater from heavy metals with natural and modified clay-containing sorbents. *Water Supply and Sanitary Engineering*, 2021, № 5, pp. 30–37. DOI: 10.35776/VST.2021.05.03.
13. Adryshev A. K., Uzdenbayeva Zh. K. Purification of industrial wastewater from polymetallic processing plants using natural sorbents bentonites from the Tagansk deposit [Text] Abstracts of reports. conf. "INTEKHMET-2008". Saint-Petersburg, 2008, pp. 108–109.
14. Ybraimzhanova L. K., Bektenov N. A., Sadykov K. A. Synthesis of new ion exchange materials on the base of epoxyacrylates [Text]. *News of the national academy of sciences of the republic of Kazakhstan series chemistry and technology*, 2020, V. 6, pp. 15–21.
15. Savichev O. G., Jan H., Chzhou D. Hydrogeodynamic and hydrogeochemical conditions of self-purification of the waters of the Ob swamp (Western Siberia). *Izvestiya Tomsk Polytechnic University. Georesource engineering*, 2022, vol. 333, № 4, pp. 115–125. DOI: 10.18799/24131830/2022/4/3656.
16. Ntwampe IO (2023) Adsorption efficiency of bentonite clay and *Parrotia persica* during acid mine drainage treatment for the removal of turbid material. *Mine Water Environ* 42:348–357. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10230-023-00936-4>
17. Bektenov N. A., Ergozhin E. E., Ybraimzhanova L. K., Masalimova B. K. Study of the sorption capacity of rhenium ions by new modified ion exchangers. *10th International Symposium on Engineering and Rhenium — Science and Technology. Conference (sectional report), October 3–6, Moscow, Russia, 2018, pp. 337–342.*

18. Shcherbakova E. V. *Chemisorption mineral and matrix technology for purification and regeneration of polluted waters with hydrolyzed aluminosilicates [Text]: thesis of Ph.D.: 25.00.36. Saint-Petersburg, 2004. 273 p.*

19. Koshelev A. V. et al. *Development of technology for obtaining sorbents based on bentonite clays for water purification systems. Water and Ecology, 2018, vol.74, pp. 32–39.*

20. Battalova Sh. B. *Catalysts and adsorbents based on bentonites from the Tagansk deposit and possible areas of their application. Bentonites. M., Nauka, 1980. 197 p.*

21. Surendra B. S., Veerabhadraswamy M. *Microwave assisted modification of bentonite clay: characterization and solvent-free synthesis of Schiff's bases. J. Org. Inorg. Chem., 2017, vol. 3, № 1, p 3.*

22. Ybraimzhanova L. K., Bektenov N. A., Tasmagambet A. T., Bazilbaev S. M. *Organomineral sorbents based on natural sorbents and their application. XI International Scientific and Practical Conference "Global Science and Innovations 2020. Central Asia" within the framework of the publication of the International Scientific Journal "Global Science and Innovations 2020. Sentral Asia", December 17, 2020. Nursultan (Astana), pp. 23–27.*

23. Tohdee K. L. Kaewsichan, Asadullah Asadullah. *Enhancement of adsorption efficiency of heavy metal Cu (II) and Zn (II) onto cationic surfactant modified bentonite. Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering, 2018, vol.6, № 2, pp. 2821–2828. DOI: 10.1016/j.jece.2018.04.030.*

24. Bagherifam S, Brown TC, Fellows CM, Naidu R, Komarneni S (2022) *Highly efficient removal of antimonite (Sb(III)) from aqueous solutions by organoclay and organozeolite: Kinetics and Isotherms. Appl Clay Sci. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2022.106004>*

25. Kravchenko M. M., Adryshev A. A., Uzdenbayeva Zh. K. *Bentonites and zeolite tuffs are effective sorbents for purification of industrial wastewater from polymetallic processing plants. Bulletin of EKSTU named after. D.Serikbayev, Ust-Kamenogorsk, 2008, pp. 102–107.*

26. Tahir S. S., Roof N. *Removal of a cationic dyes from aquatic solutions by adsorption onto bentonite clay. Chemosphere, 2006, vol. 63, № 11, pp. 1842–1848.*

27. Zhu X., Lan L., Xiang N., Liu W., Zhao Q., Li H. *Thermodynamic studies on the adsorption of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Cd²⁺ on to amine-modified bentonite. Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop, 2016, vol. 30, № 3, pp. 357–367.*

28. Radhakrishnan K., Sivanesan S., Panneerselvam P. *Turn-On fluorescence sensor based detection of heavy metal ion using carbon dots graphitic-carbon nitride nanocomposite probe. Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry, 2020, V. 389, pp. 112204. DOI:10.1016/j.jphotochem.2019.112204.*

-
29. Jetimov M. A. *The use of natural mineral sorbents for purification of drinking water from microbiological contaminants. Theoretical and applied issues of science and education*. Tombov, January, 2015. pp. 47–51. ISSN 978-5-906766-80-9/
30. Jetimov M., Yessengabylov I., Maymekov Z., Tokpanov E., Sydykbayeva S., Imangazinova Zh., Issayeva G. *Sorption characteristics of zeolite and bentonite natural adsorbents modified complex. Of the national academy of sciences of the republic of Kazakhstan. Series of geology and technical sciences*, 2020, vol. 4, № 442, pp. 138–146. DOI: 10.32014/2020.2518-170X.94.
31. Jambers Scandelai A. P., Zotesso J. P., Jegatheesan V., Cardozo-Filho L., Tavares C. *Intensification of supercritical water oxidation (ScWO) process for landfill leachate treatment through ion exchange with zeolite. Waste Management*, 2020, vol. 101, pp. 259–267.
32. Ahmed AM, Ayad MI, Eledkawy MA, Darweesh MA, Elmelegy EM (2021) *Removal of iron, zinc, and nickel-ions using nano bentonite and its applications on power station wastewater. Heliyon*7: e06315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06315>
33. Talio M. C. et al. *Sequential determination of lead and cobalt in tap water and foods samples by fluorescence // Talanta*. — 2014. — V. 127. — P. 244–249.
34. Tarighat M. A. *Orthogonal projection approach and continuous wavelet transform-feed forward neural networks for simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of some heavy metals in diet samples // Food Chemistry*. — 2016. — V. 192. — P. 548–556.
35. GOST 20255.1–89. *Ionites. Method for determining static exchange containers*. — M.: Standardinform, 2002. — 5 With.
36. Rosenstein C., Hirsch S. *Chemical analysis of plating solutions // Metal Finishing*. — 2004. — V. 102. — № 4. — P. 447–490.
-

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.18.23.029

16-MEMBERED ANTIPARASITIC MACROLIDES IN THE FOCUS FOR REPURPOSING IN ONCOLOGY (MINI-REVIEW)

Dzhafarov Mamedsalim Khanguseyn oglu

Doctor of Biological Sciences, Candidate of Chemical Sciences, independent researcher

Zavarsin Igor Viktorovich

Doctor of Chemical Sciences, Head of Laboratory

N. D. Zelinsky Institute of Organic Chemistry,

Russian Academy of Sciences

Abstract. *This mini-review briefly summarizes the literature on the repurposing of known drugs in oncology. Particular attention is paid to the prospects of ivermectin and other innovative developments in the 16-membered antiparasitic macrolide series. It is concluded that continued research is needed both in terms of repurposing ivermectin in oncology and identifying a lead compound among modified ivermectin derivatives and other 16-membered avermectin-type macrolides.*

Keywords: *Antitumor agents, parasiticides, repurposing, avermectins, ivermectin, semisynthetic 16-membered macrolides, lead compound.*

Introduction: Cancer is a group of diverse diseases in humans [1] and animals [2] with polyvariant etiology [3] and the common feature of malignant neoplasm [4]. Despite advances in cancer prevention and treatment, millions of human [5] and animal [6] deaths are recorded annually.

In modern oncology practice, cytotoxic, cytostatic, and hormonal drugs are of exceptional importance. However, drug therapy is associated with the development of multidrug resistance [10], which, combined with the general trend of progress in the development of more effective, less toxic, and relatively inexpensive drugs, motivates regular updates to the range of anticancer drugs [11].

The aim of this study is to provide a brief overview of the repurposing of known drugs in oncology, with an emphasis on the prospects of ivermectin and other 16-membered avermectin-type macrolides.

Research Objects and Methods: The study was conducted based on an analysis of available data in scientific papers (articles, monographs, manuals, and reference books) on the repurposing of known drugs, including ivermectin and other

16-membered antiparasitic macrolides. Data were collected by searching online resources (e-library, cyberleninka, pubmed, Google Scholar, and the websites of various journals included in the reference list).

Research Results and Discussion. An analysis of the literature shows that large-scale research is being conducted in laboratories in many countries, including Russia, to develop new technologies for the prevention and treatment of cancer [12–14]. One such research area is the repurposing of known drugs in the search for more effective medications [15].

Drug repurposing is a promising alternative to the traditional pharmaceutical development approach, aimed at using licensed drugs for new indications [16]. Information on the current status of drug repurposing is available on the ReDO (The Repurposing Drugs in Oncology) website in open access mode [<http://apps.chiragjpgroup.org/repoDB/>]. The advantage of this approach is a significant reduction in pharmaceutical development costs compared to de novo development, which requires an average of 13 years of research and approximately \$2–3 billion to bring to market [17], as well as the risk of failure in the future. “Repurposing” reduces the time to practical implementation of a drug to 6 years [16], even if in some cases modification of the drug composition and molecular structure of the substance is required [17], the invention of a new delivery system [18] or a combination of drugs [19].

The modern nomenclature of chemotherapeutic drugs includes many repurposed drugs: N-analogues of “garlic gas” — representatives of the historically first class of antitumor agents — chlorambucil and others (prescribed for leukemia), the sedative thalidomide (for multiple myeloma), white arsenic [(arsenic(III) oxide)] — known since ancient times — against acute promyelocytic leukemia, and others [20].

Currently, various pharmacotherapeutic groups are being considered for the prevention and treatment of malignant neoplasms. Of particular interest is the highly effective parasiticide ivermectin (Campbell W. C., Omura S.; Nobel Prize, 2015), which has a broad nematocidal and insectoacaricidal spectrum of action [21].

Ivermectin is a 22,23-dihydro derivative of avermectin B1 (a mixture of the major component B1a and the minor B1b), one of four two-component fractions of the 8-component avermectin complex produced by the wild strain of the actinomycete *S. avermitilis* (Fig. 1) [22]. Numerous milbemycins (*S. hygroscopicus*) related to avermectins are also known [22].

Substance Substituents	A1a	A1b	B1a	B1b	A2a	A2b	B2a	B2b
R^5	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H
R^{26}	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃
X	-CH=CH-	-CH=CH-	-CH=CH-	-CH=CH-	$\begin{matrix} \text{OH} \\ \text{H}_2\text{C}-\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2 \end{matrix}$			

Figure 1. Native avermectins of the actinomycete *S. avermetilis*.

The generally accepted antiparasitic therapeutic dose of ivermectin is 0.2–0.3 mg/kg, but may vary upwards or downwards depending on the parasite species, the animal, and the route of administration (oral, injection, or topical). Higher doses of 0.4 mg/kg are used to treat human lymphatic filariasis [23], while prolonged-release preparations for sheep use 1.0–1.2 mg/kg (subcutaneous, injection solution), etc. [24]. Ivermectin is a safe drug: at doses 40 times higher than the therapeutic dose, no signs of toxicity appear [23]. However, ivermectin and other substances in this class are not identical, and variations in substituents in different regions of the pentacyclic pharmacophore core are reflected in their physicochemical properties and, consequently, biological activity. Specifically, it has been established that for the G3 strain of the malaria mosquito *Anopheles gambiae sensu stricto*, the median lethal concentration of substances in the blood increases in the series ivermectin–epinomectin–selamectin–moxidectin: 22.4, 23.6, 277, and 278 ng/ml [25].

Ivermectin and its analogs are also known to have modulating effects on various biotarget receptors (Table 1). Furthermore, the cytotoxic activities of ivermectin, considered a multi-target antitumor agent, and other 16-membered antiparasitic macrolides differ depending on the structure of the active ingredients and the type of cancer (Table 2).

Table 1. Comparison of the modulating effects of the most well-known avermectin-like substances on target proteins [26]

Target proteins	Modulating effects of avermectins
GluCl	IverM* > other analogues
GlyR	IverM = AbaM = DoraM = EmaM > EprinoM
P2X4	IverM = AbaM >> DoraM > EmaM
GIRK	IverM = AbaM > DoraM = EprinoM
FXR	IverM = AbaM = DoraM >>> EprinoM

* M — the ending «mectin»

GluCl — glutamate-gated Cl⁻ anion channel, specific to vertebrates, the main target of antiparasitic action;

GlyR — glycine receptors;

P₂X₄ — ATP-gated cation channel;

GIRK — G protein-coupled receptor;

FXR — farnesoid X receptor.

Table 2. Antitumor effect of ivermectin in in vivo experiments on various types of malignant neoplasms [27].

Malignant neoplasm		Cell line	Dose, mg/kg	Effects
Leukemia	Mouse	MDAY-D2	3*	Tumor volume and mass reduction by up to 70% in all 3 models
	Human	OCI-AML2 K562	5 6.	
Breast cancer		MDA-MB-231-GFP	2.4	Tumor size and mass reduction
Human glioblastoma		U87 T98G	40	No reduction in body weight was observed in mice, but tumor growth was significantly suppressed.
Human colon cancer		DLD1 CC14 HT29	10	Inhibition of DLD 1 tumor growth. Suppression of HT29 tumor growth. No effect on CC14 tumor growth.
Human glioma		U87MG	10	Reduces tumor size by up to 50% at a dose of 10 mg/kg.
other cancers				

* - Intraperitoneal injection

In *in vitro* experiments, we found that the cytotoxic dose (CTD50) of avermectin B1 derivatives — ivermectin, sumectin (avermectin B1 hemisuccinate), and avermectin B1 ethyl hemisuccinate — against the Hep-2 cell culture (epidermoid carcinoma of the larynx) was 15.3; 20.1, and 216.3 µg/ml, respectively, and against the A549 cell culture (lung carcinoma) it was 77.1, 37.6, and 1000 µg/ml [28]. However, some modified ivermectin derivatives, under the working title “acanceromectins,” were many times more toxic than ivermectin against the A549 cell culture (research is ongoing).

To identify a lead compound among ivermectin derivatives, in addition to high efficacy, it is also necessary to consider changes in side effects associated with the modulation of various off-target receptors (see Table 1), including GABAA receptors, particularly during the perinatal period of development or childhood in humans [29], and in some dogs (collies and related breeds) with a blood-brain barrier defect [30] (research is ongoing).

Conclusion. Thus, the conducted analysis of the literature data shows that the list of antitumor agents used in practical oncology includes several repurposed chemotherapeutic agents. Many well-known drugs from various pharmacological groups, including ivermectin, are under consideration. Further research is required both on the clinical antitumor efficacy of ivermectin and on the identification of a lead compound among 16-membered avermectin-like macrolides.

References.

1. *TNM Atlas: Illustrated Guide to the TNM Classification of Malignant Tumours* / Ed.: J. D. Brierley, H. Asamura, E. Van Eycken, B. Rous — John Wiley & Sons Ltd., 2021. — 432 p.
2. *Withrow & MacEwen's Small Animal Clinical Oncology* / Eds.: Vail D. M., Thamm D. H., Liptak J. M. 6th ed. Elsevier, 2019. P. 85.
3. *Weinberg R. A. The Biology of Cancer. 2nd Ed.* — N.-Y. & L.: Taylor & Francis Group, 2014. 963 p.
4. *Jacob M., Varghese J., Weil A. P. Cancer: An Overview. Chapter 56 / Harper's Illustrated Biochemistry. 32nd Edition. Ed.: P. J. Kennelly, K. M. Botham, O. P. McGuinness, V. W. Rodwell, P. A. Weil.* — N-Y: McGraw Hill, LLC, 2023. p. 689–716.
5. *GBD 2023 Cancer Collaborators. The global, regional, and national burden of cancer, 1990–2023, with forecasts to 2050: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2023 // Lancet. 2025. V. 406. № 10512. P. 1565–1586.*
6. *Knottenbelt D. C., Patterson-Kane J. C., Snalune K.L Clinical Equine Oncology.* — Elsevier Ltd., 2015. P. 3–7.

7. Luo H, Sun Y, Xu T. Application status and research progress of targeted therapy drugs for hormone receptor-positive breast cancer // *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2025, 12: 1513836.
8. Fan T, Zhang M, Yang J, Zhu Z, Cao W, Dong C. Therapeutic cancer vaccines: advancements, challenges, and prospects // *Signal Transduct Target Ther*. 2023, 8(1): 450.
9. Xu J, Tang Z. Progress on angiogenic and antiangiogenic agents in the tumor microenvironment // *Front Oncol*. 2024, 14: 1491099.
10. Wu E, Wu Z, Yang CY, Qi D, Hu X, Li W. Editorial: Managing cancer metastasis by tackling anticancer drug resistance // *Front Pharmacol*. 2024, 15: 1432248.
11. Edaibis R, Akel R, Shin JA. Beyond small molecules: advancing MYC-targeted cancer therapies through protein engineering // *Transcription*. 2025, 16(1): 67–85.
12. Kaur R, Bhardwaj A, Gupta S. Cancer treatment therapies: traditional to modern approaches to combat cancers // *Mol Biol Rep*. 2023, 50(11): 9663–9676.
13. Aldrich LN, Burdette JE, Carcache de Blanco E, Coss CC, Eustaquio AS, Fuchs JR, Kinghorn AD, MacFarlane A, Mize BK, Oberlies NH, Orjala J, Pearce CJ, Phelps MA, Rakotondraibe LH, Ren Y, Soejarto DD, Stockwell BR, Yalowich JC, Zhang X. Discovery of Anticancer Agents of Diverse Natural Origin // *J Nat Prod*. 2022, 85(3): 702–719.
14. Lourenço AM, Ferreira LM, Branco PS. Molecules of natural origin, semi-synthesis and synthesis with anti-inflammatory and anticancer utilities // *Curr Pharm Des*. 2012;18(26):3979–4046.
15. Das V. New use of Old Drugs: Repurposing of Non-oncology Drugs for Cancer and Oncology Drugs for other Human Diseases // *Anticancer Agents Med Chem*. 2023, 23(10):1103.
16. Weth, F.R., Hoggarth, G.B., Weth, A.F. et al. Unlocking hidden potential: advancements, approaches, and obstacles in repurposing drugs for cancer therapy // *Br J Cancer* 130, 703–715 (2024).
17. Zhang Z, Zhou L, Xie N, et al. Overcoming cancer therapeutic bottleneck by drug repurposing // *Signal Transduct Target Ther*. 2020, 5(1): 113.
18. Latif K, Ullah A, Shkodina AD, et al. Drug reprofiling history and potential therapies against Parkinson's disease // *Front Pharmacol*. 2022, 13: 1028356.
19. Huang H, He Q, Guo B, Xu X, Wu Y, Li X. Progress in Redirecting Antiparasitic Drugs for Cancer Treatment // *Drug Des Devel Ther*. 2021, 15: 2747–2767.
20. Chu E., DeVita V. T., Jr. Physicians' Cancer Chemotherapy Drug Manual 2021. — Jones & Bartlett Learning, 2022. — 837 p.
21. Menchikov L. G., Dzhafarov M. Kh., Zavarzin I. V. Avermectin chemistry: recent advances // *Russ Chem Rev*, 2022, 91, RCR5051,
22. Dzhafarov M.Kh., Vasilevich F. I., Mirzaev M. N. Production of avermectins: biotechnologies and organic synthesis // *Sel'skokhozyaistvennaya Biologiya [Agricultural Biology]*, 2019, V. 54, № 1, p. 199

23. Campbell W. C. Ivermectin as an antiparasitic agent for use in humans // *Annu Rev Microbiol.* 1991; 45: 445–74.

24. Lifschitz A, Nava S, Miró V, Canton C, Alvarez L, Lanusse C. Macrocyclic lactones and ectoparasites control in livestock: Efficacy, drug resistance and therapeutic challenges // *Int J Parasitol Drugs Drug Resist.* 2024, 26: 100559.

25. Butters MP, Kobylinski KC, Deus KM, da Silva IM, Gray M, Sylla M, Foy BD. Comparative evaluation of systemic drugs for their effects against *Anopheles gambiae* // *Acta Trop.* 2012, 121(1): 34–43.

26. Chen IS, Kubo Y. Ivermectin and its target molecules: shared and unique modulation mechanisms of ion channels and receptors by ivermectin // *J Physiol.* 2018, 596(10): 1833–1845.

27. Lotfalizadeh N, Gharib A, Hajjafari A, Borji H, Bayat Z. The Anticancer Potential of Ivermectin: Mechanisms of Action and Therapeutic Implications. *Journal of Lab. Animal Research.* 2022, 1(1): 52–59 //

28. Dzhamalov M.Kh., Pozyabin S. V., Shtro A. A., Galochkina A. V., Nikolaeva Yu. V., Chernoburova E. I., Zavarzin I. V. Cytotoxic properties of Avermectin B1 hemisuccinate / Collection of abstracts of the 8th Interdisciplinary Conference “Molecular and Biological Aspects of Chemistry, Pharmaceutics and Pharmacology” / — M.: “Pero”, 2023. — p. 196 (in Russian).

29. Chandler RE. Serious Neurological Adverse Events after Ivermectin — Do They Occur beyond the Indication of Onchocerciasis? // *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2018, 98(2): 382–388.

30. Mealey KL, Bentjen SA, Gay JM, Cantor GH. Ivermectin sensitivity in col-lies is associated with a deletion mutation of the *mdr1* gene // *Pharmacogenetics.* 2001, 11(8): 727–33

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.36.48.137

NUTRITION OF THE WHITE CARP IN SOME RESERVOIRS OF THE STAVROPOL TERRITORY

Karnaukhov Gennady Ivanovich

*Candidate of Biological Sciences, Head of Laboratory
Azov-Black Sea Branch of FSBSI of VNIRO*

Yatchenko Vladislav Nikolaevich

*Chief Specialist
Azov-Black Sea Branch of FSBSI of VNIRO*

Annotation. *The research was carried out in three reservoirs of the Stavropol Territory (Volchye Vorota, Mokraya Buffaloe. Refusenik). The composition of microalgae in reservoirs does not remain constant by season. Seasonality is clearly evident in the development of phytoplankton. The maximum development of phytoplankton is noted in the summer due to the massive development of green and blue-green algae. The increase in phytoplankton productivity is due to the high availability of biogenic elements and more intensive warming of the water column. Information about the daily feeding rhythm of the white carp is provided. The intestinal content was assessed, and the feeding spectrum of silver carp in the studied reservoirs was determined. The average residual production of phytoplankton has been determined for each reservoir. Suggestions have been made for the optimal volumes of annual stocking of the reservoir with white silver carp fry.*

Keywords: *Reservoirs, white silver carp, food base, daily feeding rhythm, feeding spectrum, residual production of phytoplankton.*

In the Stavropol Territory, there are significant areas of water bodies with a well-developed forage base and favorable hydrological and hydrochemical conditions, which can be used for the development of pasture fish farming based on the “release-and-catch” principle. The formation of ichthyocenoses, with the aim of fully utilizing the forage resources of the water body by fish, determines the main direction for solving issues related to increasing the overall fish productivity. By consuming actively reproducing phytoplankton, which is not utilized by the local ichthyofauna, the white silver carp is able to rapidly increase its mass, converting biogenic substances into valuable animal protein. In the comprehensive development of reservoirs, the issues of trophic relationships between hydrobionts, including

fish, play an important role. In this context, the use of the food base, the rhythm, and the spectrum of nutrition become particularly significant.

The microalgae flora of the reservoirs is very similar in terms of the number of divisions and orders, as indicated by the slight variation in the coefficient of variation. This value increased as the taxonomic rank decreased. The greatest variability between the reservoirs was observed in terms of the number of intraspecific taxa.

The similarity coefficient of the algal flora of the studied reservoirs is quite high and is 0.51 according to Serensen (the Volkiye Vorota reservoir and the Otkaznenskoye reservoir), 0.42 (the Volkiye Vorota reservoir and the Mokraya Buivola reservoir), and 0.37 (the Mokraya Buivola reservoir and the Otkaznenskoye reservoir).

The production properties of the studied reservoirs, in terms of the vegetation conditions of phytoplankton, as a potential source of food for white silver carp, allow them to be classified as high-yielding [1]. The reservoirs are characterized by shallow depths, which allows the entire water column to be well warmed. They are rich in biogenic elements, which contributes to the intensive development of phytoplankton. The algal flora of these reservoirs is relatively poor in terms of species diversity, but rich in terms of quantity.

During the year, the biomass of the microalgae community in the studied reservoirs undergoes significant seasonal changes. The study of the dynamics of algal flora development allowed us to determine the trophic status of the reservoirs. Additionally, this knowledge provided insights into the similarities between these reservoirs.

The analysis of the seasonal dynamics of phytoplankton in three reservoirs in the Stavropol Territory revealed the following patterns:

1. Green, blue-green, and euglenoid algae are the most abundant and diverse during the summer season.

2. With a decrease in water temperature to 10–12 °C, diatoms begin to dominate.

3. The peak of the abundance and species diversity of microalgae of all groups in the reservoirs occurs at the end of summer. The exception is golden algae, which are absent in summer samples.

4. Throughout the growing season, representatives of the groups: Chlorophyta, Cyanophyta and Bacillariophyta are found in the phytoplankton community.

The diet of white silver carp is closely related to the development of phytoplankton and water temperature. In the conditions of southern Russia, white silver carp begin to feed on phytoplankton at the age of 2–3 weeks, and 25-g silver carp consume only microalgae.

It should be noted that the diet of different age groups of white silver carp does not differ. Silver carp actively consume algae of the genera *Navicula*, *Monoraphidium*, and *Scenedesmus*. The average degree of intestinal filling during the growing season is 3 points in the Volchye Vorota and Otkaznenskoye reservoirs, and 4 points

in the Mokraya Buivola reservoir. The daily feeding rhythm of two-year-old silver carp in the studied reservoirs has three peaks with slight fluctuations: in the morning from 6:00 a.m. to 8:00 a.m., in the middle of the day from 1:00 p.m. to 3:00 p.m., and in the evening from 6:00 p.m. to 8:00 p.m.

However, increased feeding intensity is observed only during the day, and at night, the white silver carp's feeding activity decreases significantly or stops altogether.

During the spring season, the white silver carp's feeding activity is not very active, primarily due to the insufficient development of phytoplankton. The average intestinal content during the spring season in the Otkaznoye reservoir is no more than 2.1 points, in the Volchye Vorota reservoir it is 2.6 points, and in the Mokraya Buivola reservoir it is 3.1 points.

In the digestive tract of fish with an average weight of 1132.5 g, caught in April in the Volchye Vorota reservoir, the average weight of algae in the food ball did not exceed 0.67 g. The food spectrum was dominated by euglenoid and diatoms. As the water temperature increased and phytoplankton began to develop, green algae began to predominate in the food ball. In June, the average mass of algae in the digestive tract of silver carp with an average mass of 1324 g increases to 27.8 g, which is about 2.1 % of the body weight.

The maximum stomach content was observed in the summer-autumn period in the following reservoirs: Otkaznenskoye — 3.8 points, Volchye Vorota — 3.7 points, and Mokraya Buivola — 4.2 points. During this period, the white silver carp's diet is dominated by green, diatoms, and euglen algae. The average mass of the food ball varies slightly between the reservoirs: In the Otkaznenskoye reservoir, the average fish weight is 41.2 g \pm 1.02 g, while in the Volchye Vorota reservoir, the average fish weight is 40.3 g \pm 1.23 g, and in the Mokraya Buivola reservoir — 48.9 g \pm 2.11 g with an average fish weight of 1613.9 g \pm 161.5 g.

Blue-green algae, such as *Anabaena variabilis*, *Oscillatoria ornate*, *Merismopedia tenuissima*, and *Microcystis aeruginosa*, account for up to 17.6% of the food ball in Lake Mokraya Buivola, 12.4% in the Otkaznenskoye reservoir, and 8.2% in the Volchye Vorota reservoir.

White silver carp filters out the cells of blue-green algae, but their shells are almost completely destroyed in the intestines. After passing through the fish's digestive system and being partially processed, the cyanobacteria enter the water body as large, well-formed particles. In the late 1960s, the radiocarbon method was used to determine that white silver carp only absorbs 8–16% of green and blue-green algae [2].

In autumn, when the water temperature drops to 15 °C, the feeding intensity gradually decreases. The average mass of the food ball in mid-October is 8.2 g \pm 0.9 g in the Otkaznenskoye reservoir, with an average fish mass of 2854 g \pm 248.9 g,

9.7 g in the Volchye Vorota reservoir, with an average fish mass of 2868 g±287.6 g, and 10.6 g in the Mokraya Buivola reservoir, with an average fish mass of 2060 g±196.9 g. Euglena and diatoms begin to dominate in the diet.

In general, the volume of feed resources in reservoirs for phytoplankton is quite significant and can meet the nutritional needs of a significant number of silver carp. Materials from hydrobiological surveys were used to assess the feed capacity of reservoirs for juvenile silver carp. For the Volchye Vorota reservoir (with an aqua-territory area of 500 ha), with an average phytoplankton biomass of about 2.3 g/m³ during the growing season, its annual residual production will be about 1,664 tons, which can meet the nutritional needs of 800,000 white silver carp juveniles weighing more than 25 g. For the Otkaznenskoye reservoir (water area 1600 ha), with a phytoplankton biomass of 1.9 g/m³, the production will be 5358 tons, which will be sufficient to feed 2.8 million specimens of white silver carp. In the Mokraya Buivola reservoir (with an aqua-area of 700 ha), the biomass of the algocenosis does not exceed 1.4 g/m³, which will produce 1311 tons of products, which will be available for 650 thousand specimens of white silver carp.

Thus, pasture farming of white silver carp in reservoirs involves constant monitoring of the fish's condition, nutrition, and growth, as well as the development of the natural food supply. The obtained data on nutrition showed that white silver carp primarily consume green, blue-green, and euglen algae during the summer, while diatoms and euglen algae begin to dominate in the autumn. The average intestinal content during the growing season is more than 3 points. The development of phytoplankton in reservoirs is at a fairly high level and can provide a significant amount of white silver carp with feed resources.

References

1. Karnaukhov G. I., Sklyarov V. Ya. *Increasing the efficiency of using water bodies in the Stavropol Territory. Fish Farming. No. 3–4, 2013. — pp. 33–34.*
2. Panov D. A., Sorokin Yu. I., Motenkova L. G. *Experimental study of the nutrition of juvenile silver carp. Issues of Ichthyology. Vol. 9, issue 1(54), 1969. pp. 138–152.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.35.26.075

THE CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF PEONIES

Lyapina Lyudmila Anisimovna

Doctor of Biological Sciences, Full Professor, Chief Researcher of the Laboratory

Uspenskaya Marianna Sergeevna

Candidate of Biological Sciences, Senior Research Officer

Murashev Vladimir Vladimirovich

Candidate of Biological Sciences, Leading Researcher Lomonosov Moscow State University, Faculty of Biology, Moscow, Russia

Abstract. Arterial and venous thrombosis remains a pressing issue today. The particular danger of intravascular thrombus formation is that it typically occurs unexpectedly. Nearly 25 million people die annually from vascular thrombosis: more than 18 million from arterial thrombosis (myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke, mesenteric thrombosis, etc.), and 7 million from pulmonary embolism [10]. Therefore, one of the key challenges in modern physiology, medicine, and pharmacology is the development of highly effective drugs with a broad spectrum of action and minimal side effects. The search for non-toxic substances that restore metabolism in organs and tissues and simultaneously normalize the functions of a number of body systems is undoubtedly urgent [7]. The scientific problem, which the publication aims to solve, encompasses a set of our own studies and literature analysis in two related fields — the physiology and biochemistry of blood coagulation, as well as plant growing, which is expressed in new approaches to the creation of highly effective anticoagulants of plant origin, identifying the mechanisms of their action on a number of body systems — hemostatic, endothelial, as well as on carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. The universality of the regulatory action of a natural anticoagulant of animal origin — heparin, aimed at regulating the reactions of many body systems, is known. Our contribution to the development of this field of science is, firstly, in proving the similarity of heparin-like low molecular weight anticoagulants of plant origin from peonies and low molecular weight heparin of animal origin; secondly, in presenting evidence of their preventive and therapeutic action in experimental models of metabolic syndrome,

diabetes mellitus and endothelial dysfunction complicated by thrombosis; Thirdly, establishing therapeutic doses of anticoagulant heparin-like compounds of plant origin. This brings us closer to understanding the general patterns of regulation of normal hemostasis in the human body and the restoration of its normal status under the influence of plant-based heparin-like drugs in various pathological conditions. The effectiveness of these compounds lies in the ability to optimize the body's existing reserves and correct pathologically altered functions. Achieving the full spectrum of antithrombotic action of drugs based on plant-based heparin-like substances from peonies will optimize approaches to treating diseases caused by thrombosis, hyperlipidemia, hyperglycemia, and endothelial dysfunction. The use of direct-acting plant anticoagulants to correct metabolic disorders in the body, accompanied by disruptions in blood clotting and vascular tone, is scientifically significant, as it allows us to identify the pathways and mechanisms of their action in the body and offer clinicians and pharmacologists effective and safe means for restoring the body's defenses against thrombotic and thrombohemorrhagic conditions [9].

Keywords: *hemostasis, blood clotting, peony root extracts, peony species, anticoagulant activity, heparinoid, antithrombotics.*

Funding. This study was conducted in connection with an assignment from Lomonosov Moscow State University.

Since 1967, the Botanical Garden of the Biology Department of Lomonosov Moscow State University has been introducing wild peony species. The collection, which includes both herbaceous and shrubby species, currently numbers over 10. Based on many years of research, their morphogenetic characteristics, adaptive and reproductive potential have been studied, and cultivation techniques and propagation methods have been developed. This allowed for a search among various peonies for species and varieties containing components with anticoagulant-fibrinolytic properties.

The medicinal properties of wild peonies have been known for several millennia BC. In the Mediterranean, the herbaceous *P. officinalis* L. was widely used, while in China, *P. suffruticosa* Andrews was used.

Many peony species are used for medicinal purposes in folk medicine in Russia and neighboring countries. Extracts of *P. anomala* L. have a calming and anticonvulsant effect. An infusion of *P. kavachensis* Aznav. roots is used to treat stomach ailments, coughs, and rheumatism. The roots of *P. tenuifolia* L. are used as an infusion for heart disease. Elite medicinal plants from East Asian countries include *P. suffruticosae* Andrews and *P. lactiflora* Pall.

Modern research shows that the most common natural compounds found in almost all peony species are terpenes, which are responsible for the observed biological activity in vivo and in vitro [12].

At the Faculty of Biology of Moscow State University, staff from the B. A. Kudryashov Laboratory of Blood Defense Systems obtained aqueous root extracts from nine species of the genus *Paeonia* (the only genus of 33 known species in the family Paeoniaceae, native to Asia, Europe, and western North America). These extracts were found to contain biologically active components with anticoagulant effects. *P. lutea* has also been shown to have antidiabetic activity.

1. PEONIES AS ANTICOAGULANTS

It has been established that the roots of herbaceous peonies, along with steroids such as sitosterol, pentagalloyl glucose, and quinones, also contain mono- and triterpenoids, the presence of which can cause an anticoagulant effect. We also found the presence of a heparin-like substance in peonies in complex with a peptide, which also contributes to the manifestation of high anticoagulant activity in vitro.

The anticoagulant properties of peony root extracts were determined using activated partial thromboplastin time and recalcification time tests using conventional methods in normal rat plasma after the addition of 0.1 ml of peony root extract [12]. In vivo experiments were performed on albino mongrel rats weighing 180–200 g. All animal experiments were conducted in accordance with the ethical principles and documents recommended by the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals [1].

Extracts (using *P. lutea* as an example) were administered orally at a dose of 0.5 ml/200 g body weight daily for 7–8 days. Blood was collected from the animals' v. jugularis 20–24 hours after the last administration of the extract, using a 3.8% sodium citrate solution in a 9:1 ratio as a preservative. Aqueous and alcoholic extracts were prepared from the root bark of this peony, and both extracts were found to exhibit significant anticoagulant activity in vitro. A single intravenous administration of a 2% aqueous extract at a volume of 0.5 ml/200 g body weight to rats resulted in a 27% increase in anticoagulant activity in the animals' blood 10 minutes after injection. Anticoagulant activity in the activated partial thromboplastin time (APPT) test was increased by 1.2 and 1.4 times, respectively, after administration of the aqueous and alcoholic extracts.

Conclusion: Both aqueous and alcoholic extracts of peony roots exhibit anticoagulant properties in vitro and in vivo.

2. PEONIES AS ANTI-AGGREGANTS

Platelet aggregation was determined using a standard turbidimetric method in rat plasma enriched with platelets stimulated with 0.5–1.0 M ADP solutions after addition of the extract. The determination was carried out on a Russian aggregometer using the light scattering increment and was expressed in indices during the period of maximum process flow, as well as in relative percentages compared to the same parameters of control samples.

Peonies (*P. lutea*, *P. anomala*) have been shown to have the ability to reduce platelet aggregation. Here are examples of a study of the antiplatelet properties of extracts from the root bark of *P. lutea*. Two types of extracts were used: 2% aqueous and alcoholic, which, under in vitro conditions, along with high anticoagulant activity, exhibited reliable antiplatelet activity against platelets, with the activity of the alcoholic extract prevailing. Under in vivo conditions, 2% aqueous and alcoholic extracts of peonies, administered orally for 7–8 days daily in a volume of 0.5 ml / 200 g body weight of rats, led to an equally significant increase in all types of fibrinolysis and anticoagulant properties of rat plasma. The antiplatelet effect after oral administration of both extracts was detected only in the group of rats receiving the aqueous extract: a decrease in platelet aggregation 20–24 hours after the last administration of the extract was reliable and amounted to 41.5%. After administration of the alcoholic extract, the reduction in platelet aggregation was insignificant (up to 10%) [8]. *P. anomala* extracts also showed the ability to reduce platelet aggregation in vitro and in vivo. 2% extracts from whole *P. anomala* roots reduced platelet aggregation when administered intravenously to animals by 32–38% compared to plasma samples from control animals after administration of physiological NaCl solution [3, 4]. Animal-derived heparin had a similar effect at the specified dose, reducing or preventing platelet aggregation [11].

3. PEONIES AS FIBRINOLYTICS

The fibrinolytic properties of peony extracts were determined by their ability to induce lysis on unstabilized fibrin plates with the addition of β -aminocaproic acid, an inhibitor of enzymatic fibrinolysis, to the samples (to determine non-enzymatic or fibrin-depolymerization fibrinolytic activity) and in its absence (to determine total fibrinolytic activity). Tissue plasminogen activator activity was recorded by applying the extracts to standard fibrin plates: unheated (which detects the total activities of plasmin and tissue plasminogen activator) and heated at 86 °C for 30 min (which detects only plasmin activity). Tissue plasminogen activator activity was calculated from the difference in lysis zones on both fibrin plates [6]. Extracts from the roots of *P. lactiflora*, *P. lutea*, *P. anomala*, *P. suffruticosae*, and *P. officinalis* exhibited significant intrinsic total and non-enzymatic (fibrin depolymerization) fibrinolytic activity in vitro. These data indicate that peony extracts inhibited the coagulation reactions that convert fibrinogen to fibrin.

In vitro experiments, a fraction of peony roots (*P. suffruticosa*) containing heparin and peptide demonstrated high non-enzymatic fibrinolytic activity, while the peptide-free fraction of this peony demonstrated significantly lower activity. These data indicate that the fibrinolytic activity of peony preparations requires a complex nature of the heparin-like component with the peptide. Pure low-molecular-weight heparin of animal origin was also shown to exhibit no fibrin depolymerization activity.

Chronic oral administration of both *P. lutea* extracts was shown to result in equally significant increases in both total and non-enzymatic fibrinolytic potential in the blood of both experimental animals. However, tissue plasminogen activator activity was 1.7 times higher in the group of rats receiving the ethanol extract. These same animals also exhibited a more pronounced decrease in factor XIIIa activity in their blood plasma, by 53.9%, compared to the group of rats receiving the aqueous extract, where the decrease was only 29%. With chronic oral administration, both extracts exerted the most pronounced activating effect on enzymatic and non-enzymatic fibrinolysis. However, alcoholic extracts of peony should not be preferred, since, firstly, aqueous extracts from peony roots moderately enhance the anticoagulant-fibrinolytic properties of blood plasma and do not cause a sharp decrease in coagulation factors necessary for normal hemostasis. Secondly, aqueous extracts from peonies will not promote bleeding if overdosed.

4. PEONIES AS ANTITHROMBOTICS AND THROMBOLYTICS

Experimental studies have shown that peony root extracts possess not only high antithrombotic but also thrombolytic activity. These effects of peonies can also be explained by the ability of the preparations, when administered to the body, to form complexes with blood clotting factors (fibrinogen, thrombin, factor XIIIa), which reduced the level of clotting proteins in blood plasma and exhibited high anticoagulant activity.

An extract of *P. suffruticosa* roots, which exhibits the most significant anticoagulant and fibrinolytic activity, was administered orally at a dose of 0.3 ml daily for 10 days to the experimental group of rats. The control group of animals received 0.3 ml of distilled water instead of the extract. Blood was collected from the animals for analysis 24 hours after the last administration. The plasma of animals receiving the extract significantly increased in total and non-enzymatic fibrinolysis. Plasminogen activator activity and anticoagulant activity also showed a tendency to increase.

In another experiment, thrombus formation in the jugular vein was induced in healthy animals using the Wessler method. One group of animals (the experimental group) with newly formed thrombi was then injected intravenously with an extract of *P. suffruticosae* roots at a dose of 0.5 ml per 200 g of body weight, while the other group (the control group) received 0.5 ml of saline solution. The results showed that the time to restore blood flow in animals receiving the extract was half that of the control animals. In the control rats, complete restoration of blood flow was not observed even after 2 hours of observation. Accordingly, complete thrombus lysis in the control rats was not observed for more than 2.5 hours after thrombus formation, while in most experimental animals, complete lysis occurred 74.5 minutes after extract administration.

Thus, peony root extracts, when administered orally over a chronic period, increase the anticoagulant-fibrinolytic activity of the blood, thereby preventing

vascular thrombus formation when provoked, exhibiting an antithrombotic effect, and lysing newly formed thrombi in the bloodstream, exerting a thrombolytic effect by dissolving newly formed fibrin clots that lead to thrombus formation [2, 3, 4].

5. PEONIES AS LIPOLYTIC AGENTS

Seventy-five albino male rats weighing 180–200 g were used in the experiments. The animals were divided into three groups: the first group received a peony extract, the second received a solvent (16% ethyl alcohol), and the third received water. The test preparations were administered orally at a dose of 0.5 ml per 200 g of rat body weight, every 24 hours for 10 days. Blood for hemocoagulation analysis was collected from the v. jugularis 24 hours after the last administration. Twenty-four hours after the last administration of the alcoholic root bark extract (experiment), water (control 1), and 16% ethyl alcohol (control 2), all rats were intravenously administered a diabetogenic dose of alloxan at a dose of 37.5 mg per 1 kg of body weight. Experimental insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus was induced in animals fasted for 18–24 hours before administration of alloxan (Spofa, Czech Republic). Blood glucose concentrations were determined using the method of J.I.C. Kantorovich (1963), and immunoreactive insulin levels were measured using rio-INS-PS-5125–0 kits (Belarus) before alloxan administration and 2 and 7 days after alloxan administration. Survival of rats in the experimental and control groups was also monitored.

Twenty-four hours after 10-fold administration of peony root extract, total fibrinolytic activity, non-enzymatic fibrinolysis, and tissue plasminogen activator activity in plasma were significantly higher in the experimental group of rats than in the control group. However, the platelet aggregation index remained virtually unchanged from the control values. Using 16% alcohol as a control did not cause any changes in blood parameters 24 hours after the last 10-fold administration.

Intravenous administration of alloxan 24 hours after the end of chronic (10 days) oral administration of peony extract to the experimental group of rats resulted in a significant increase in blood glucose levels by almost 4 times on the second day after alloxan administration.

During this period, hyperglycemia was more pronounced in the control group of animals (glucose levels increased 6.2 times).

By the seventh day after alloxan administration, blood glucose levels in the experimental group of rats had normalized. During this same period, hyperglycemia persisted in the control group of rats, with glucose levels 1.8 times higher than in the experimental group. It should be noted that the alcoholic extract from the root bark of *P. lutea* protected the animals' bodies from the toxic effects of alloxan, as evidenced by 100% survival of the experimental rats versus 66% of the control animals by the end of the experiment. No significant differences in insulin levels were observed

between the experimental and control groups [5]. Thus, based on the in vivo experiment, it can be concluded that the alcoholic extract from the root bark of *P. lutea*, when administered chronically orally, exerted both a protective anticoagulant effect in the bloodstream and a protective antidiabetogenic effect, normalizing blood glucose levels. After just 5 uses of the peony extract, fibrinolytic (total, non-enzymatic, enzymatic) and anticoagulant activities significantly increased. The anticoagulant activity of plasma under the influence of peony is due to the presence of heparin-like polysaccharides. The increased enzymatic fibrinolysis in blood plasma is due to the fact that the peony preparation itself has plasminogen activator properties, while also releasing natural tissue plasminogen activator from the rats' vascular walls into the bloodstream. With 10-fold administration of the peony preparation, the plasma fibrinolytic level exceeded the control level. Against this background, the peony preparation protected the body from the toxic diabetogenic effect of alloxan. Specifically, by day 7 after alloxan administration, blood glucose levels in most animals were within normal limits, and 100% of the rats in the experiment survived.

6. PEONIES AS A SUBSTANCE IMPROVING ENDOTHELIAL FUNCTION

Thirty-two male Wistar laboratory white rats weighing 180–200 g were used in in vivo experiments. The rats were fed a standard laboratory diet and divided into two groups: an experimental group receiving a peony preparation and a control group receiving 0.85% NaCl. All preparations were administered orally at a dose of 0.1 ml daily, every 24 hours for 5 days. Blood was collected from the jugular vein 1 hour after the last administration using a 3.8% sodium citrate solution as a preservative at a blood-to-preservative ratio of 9:1. The blood was centrifuged at 2000 g for 15 minutes to obtain platelet-poor plasma. Anticoagulant activity in blood plasma was determined using the activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) and thrombin time (TT) tests on an ASK 2–01-Astra biochemical blood coagulation analyzer. Endothelial function markers were measured — tissue plasminogen activator (t-PA) activity on stabilized fibrin films, and plasma nitrate and nitrite concentrations were measured using the Griess method. Measurements were made using a Multiskan EX optical density meter for standard 300 μ L microwell plates (Labsystems, USA) at a wavelength of 402 nm. One hour after five oral doses of the peony preparation, a noticeable change in the studied parameters was observed, indicating hypocoagulation. Thus, anticoagulant activity in the experimental group increased by 50% compared to the control.

Vascular-endothelial function was significantly activated in the direction of anticoagulant mechanisms following administration of the peony preparation. Two hours after oral administration, an increase in endothelial function markers was observed in the blood: t-PA activity increased by 318% compared to the control, while total metabolite levels (nitrates and nitrites) increased by 127%.

Thus, oral administration of a heparinoid from peony roots (*P. lactiflora*) to animals leads to an increase in the anticoagulant-fibrinolytic potential of the blood with simultaneous activation of vascular-endothelial system markers. For example, administration of the peony preparation more than quadrupled the activity of the endothelial function marker tissue plasminogen activator in the bloodstream, indicating its high affinity for endothelial cells and its ability to interact with endothelial receptors, releasing plasminogen activators from the vessel wall into the bloodstream. The endothelial lining of blood vessels is known to regulate local processes of hemostasis, proliferation, blood cell migration into the vascular wall, and vascular tone. The endothelium produces various biologically active substances. These factors can enter the bloodstream not only upon endothelial stimulation but also upon its activation and damage. Levels of factors that are virtually nonexistent under normal conditions increase with endothelial activation. One of the key factors for angiogenesis is increased endothelial permeability, which is primarily associated with the action of NO. Increased vascular permeability is necessary for the release of plasma proteins, primarily fibrinogen, into the bloodstream, leading to the formation of a fibrin matrix for the subsequent migration of endothelial cells. Experiments conducted demonstrate activation of endothelial function by the increased release of nitric oxide metabolites under the influence of the plant heparinoid from peony: the concentration of tissue plasminogen activator increases, and anticoagulant activity is enhanced.

The results of these studies have been patented.

References

1. *European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and other Scientific Purposes (ETS No. 123), adopted at Strasbourg on 15 June 2006. Appendix A: Guidelines for the Care and Care of Laboratory Animals (Article No. 5 of the Convention) // Rus-LASA NP "Association of Specialists in Work with Laboratory Animals" — St. Petersburg: Working Group on Translations and Publishing of Thematic Literature, 2014. 100 p.*

2. Lyapina L. A., Novikov V. S., Pastorova V. E., Uspenskaya M. S., Smolina T. Yu., Lyapin G. Yu. *Anticoagulant from peony root extracts: production and properties // Izv. RAS. Biol. Ser. 1995. No. 2. — P. 249–251.*

3. Lyapina L. A., Ammosova Ya. M., Novikov V. S., Osipova N. N., Smolina T. Yu., Pastorova V. E., Uspenskaya M. S., Lyapin G. Yu. *On the nature of the anticoagulant obtained from peonies of central Russia // Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Ser. Biologicheskikh. 1997. No. 2. — P. 235–237.*

4. Lyapina L. A., Kondashevskaya M. V., Pastorova V. E., Uspenskaya M. S., Novikov V. S. *Antithrombotic effects of an extract from the roots of Paeonia lactiflora // Thrombosis, hemostasis and rheology.* 2000. No. 2 (2). — P. 37–38.

5. Lyapina L. A., Pastorova V. E., Novikov V. S., Uspenskaya M. S., Ziadetdinova G. A., Ulyanov A. M., Tarasov Yu. A. *Anticoagulant-fibrinolytic and hypoglycemic effects of preparations from higher plants // Vestn. Mosk. Univ. Ser. Biology.* 16. 2001. No. 1. — P. 54–58.

6. Lyapina L. A., Grigorieva M. E., Obergan T. Yu., Shubina T. A. *Theoretical and practical issues of studying the functional state of the blood anticoagulant system.* — Moscow: Advanced Solutions, 2012. — 160 p.

7. Lyapina M. G., Uspenskaya M. S., Murashev V. V., Lyapina L. A. *Peonies as healers: antithrombotic components.* Moscow: Lesnaya Strana, 2017. — 100 p.

8. Pastorova V. E., Lyapina L. A., Uspenskaya M. S., Ziadetdinova G. A. *Comparative study of the effect of aqueous and alcoholic extracts from the root bark of the peony P. lutea on hemostatic parameters of the blood // Bulletin of Exp. Biol. and Med.* 1999. No. 5. — P. 533–535.

9. Uspenskaya M. S., Lyapina L. A., Murashev V. V. *The king of flowers — a source of promising drugs.* Moscow: Kim L. A., 2023. — 117 p.

10. Shlapak I. P., Bondar M. V., Pilipenko M. M. *Diagnosis and intensive therapy of thromboembolism of the leg artery // Statements and difficulties in medical practice — Kiev, 2014. No. 1. — pp. 37–42.*

11. Brace L. D., Fareed I. *An Objective Assessment of the Interaction of Heparin and its Fractions with Human Platelets // Semin. Thromb. Hemost.* — 1985. V. 11. — P. 190.

12. Zhao Dan-Dan, Jiang Li-Li, Li Hong-Yi, Yan Peng-Fei, Zhang Yan-Long. *Chemical components and pharmacological activities of terpene natural products from the genus paeonia // Molecules.* 2016. 21(10): 1362.

THE MAIN PATTERNS OF MANGANESE GEOCHEMISTRY¹

Yudovich Yakov Elievich

Ketris Marine Petrovna

Russian Academy of Sciences

Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences,

Komi Scientific Center

Abstract. *The article presents the main conclusions of the Russian monograph “Geochemistry of Manganese”, published in 2014. The monograph summarizes the data of 41 published works (of which 34 are Russian and 7 are foreign, mostly books).*

Based on statistical processing of ~1400 sample averages (from ~92,000 analyses), new estimations of World averages (Clarke values) for Mn and Mn module ($MnM = Mn/Fe$) have been calculated for main rock groups. These include hyperbasites, basites, mesites (rocks of medium composition), acidites and alcaly igneous rocks; hydrothermalites, metamorphites and metasomatites, and some lithologies, such as terrigenous, cherty, carbonates, evaporates, concretions (= nodules), phosphates and carbonaceous biolithes — coals and black shales. The calculations allow to perform some new conclusions in Mn-geochemistry

The purpose of this article is to introduce the foreign reader to the geochemistry of manganese developed in Russia, which is largely unknown to scientists of the Free World.

Key words: *manganese, Mn module ($MnM = Mn/Fe$), geochemistry, igneous rocks, sedimentary rocks, biosphere, frequency diagrams, average content (= Clarke value), correlations of manganese*

Preface

In 2014, a major monograph “Geochemistry of Manganese” was published at the Institute of Geology of the Komi Scientific Center of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

¹ Funding: This research was carried out within the framework of the state assignment of the Institute of Geology (Syktyvkar), Russian Academy of Sciences, Ural Branch, Komi Scientific Center

There are four parts in this book: (1) manganese in endogenous formations (igneous rocks, hydrothermalites, metamorphites and metasomatites); (2) manganese in the biosphere (in living and organic matter, in soils, weathering crusts, waters and sediments); (3) manganese in rocks of the sedimentary shell (terrigenous and volcanogenic, siliceous, carbonate, nodular, phosphatic, evaporitic, as well as in carbonaceous bioliths — coals and black shales); (4) manganese as an indicator of lithogenesis processes (topo-, dynamo- and hydrophacies of sedimentogenesis, and then diagenesis).

The fourth part of the monograph is not original — it briefly reviews the results previously published by the authors (in particular, in the 2011 book “Geochemical Indicators of Lithogenesis” [25]), but the results of the first three parts are basically new — the result of statistical processing of a very significant number of manganese analyses in geological objects.

This review article presents only the main conclusions of these four parts of the monograph.

It should be noted that objects and processes in geochemistry in general, and in manganese geochemistry in particular, are by no means separated by a gap. In fact, they have vast areas of subject-logical overlap (which creates certain difficulties in classifying the collected materials) — Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Conceptual scheme of manganese geochemistry, shown using Euler circles. The areas of subject-logical overlaps are shaded.

1. Working methods

The monograph “Geochemistry of Manganese” is based on the processing of about 92 thousand chemical analyses of rocks (and less ores), in which the manganese content was given in the form of MnO and less often in the form of Mn. It is only in ore analyses that the form MnO₂ is sometimes determined; in such cases, we recalculated it to MnO.

The most important parameter in the geochemistry of manganese is the manganese module, which since the time of Norwegian geologist and petrographer J. Vogt is traditionally calculated not in the oxide, but in the atomic form $MnM = Mn/Fe$.

Therefore, we had to recalculate the analytical data provided in the usual silicate analysis in the form of MnO, FeO, Fe₂O₃ to calculate MnM into Mn and Fe. The silicate analysis data were processed using the lithochemistry technique [31], which is based on the chemical classification presented in Tables 1–3.

Table 1 Chemical classification of sedimentary rocks

Types	Subtypes	Classes
Silites HM < 0.30	Silites <i>Pseudo-silites</i> - MgO >3 %	Hyper-, super-, normal-, myosilites
Siallites and sipherlites HM = 0.31-0.55	<i>Siallites and sipherlites</i> <i>Pseudo-siallites</i> <i>and pseudo-siferlites</i> - MgO >3 %	Hyper-, super-, normo-, myosiallites
Hydrolysates HM > 0.55	<i>Pseudo-hydrolysates</i> MgO >3 %	Hypo- normo-, super-, hyperhydrolysates
Alkalites Na ₂ O+K ₂ O > 8 %		Na, K
Carbonatolites CO ₂ >20%	Ca+Mg+Fe+Mn Na	Ca, Mg, Ca-Mg, Mg(Fe), Ca-Fe-Mg-Mn etc
Evaporites SO ₃ >20 % Cl, Br, J, F >20 % NO ₃ >37 % B ₂ O ₃ >20 %	Sulfatolites Halolites Nitratolites Boritolites	Ca, Mg, K, Na, Ba, Sr Na, K, Mg, Ca Na, K Na, K, Mg, Ca
Phosphatolites P ₂ O ₅ >20 %		Ca, Al, Fe
Sulfidolites S >20 %		Fe, Cu, Zn, etc
Cahitolites Corg >15 %		O, H, N

Table 2. Siallite standard – divisions of siallites and siferlites

Klass	HM	TM	FeM*	FemM	NaKM	AM	AlkM
Hypo-	0.30-0.33	£0.030	£0.30	£0.10	£0.20	<0.20	<0.30
Normo-	0.34-0.48	0.030-0.070	0.30-0.55	0.11-0.20	0.21-0.40	0.20-0.35	0.30-1.50
Super-	0.49-0.55	1071-0.100	0.56-0.70	0.21-0.25	0.41-0.45	0.36-0.40	1.51-3.00
Hyper-	—	>0.100	0.71-0.75	>0.25	>0.45	>0.40	>3.00

*only for siallites

Table 3. Gradations of chemotypes that are not siallites or siferlites

Klass	HM	TM	FeM*	FemM	NaKM	AM	AlkM
Silites							
Hypo-	0.20-0.30	£0.020	£0.20	£0.03	£0.20	£0.05	£0.20
Normo-	0.11-0.20	0.21-0.80	0.21-0.70	0.04-0.10	0.21-0.50	0.06-0.20	0.21-0.80
Super-	0.051-0.10	0.081-0.120	0.71-1.0	0.11-0.15	0.51-0.70	>0.20	0.81-2.50
Hyper-	£0.05	>0.120	>1.0	>0.15	>0.70	—	>2/50
Hydrolisates							
Hypo-	0.56-0.85	£0.030	£0.30	£0.15	£0.05	£0.15	£0.20
Normo-	0.86-2.0	0.031-0.100	0.31-1.00	0.16-1.00	0.06-0.30	0.16-1.00	0.20-1.5
Super-	2.1-10	0.101-0.150	1.01-2.00	1.01-2.00	0.31-0.40	1.01-3.00	1.51-2.0
Hyper-	>10	>0.150	>2.00	>2.00	>0.40	>3.00	>2.0
Alkalites							
Hypo-		£0.010	£0.10	£0.05	£0.30	£0.10	£0.10
Normo-		0.011-0.050	0.11-0.40	0.06-0.20	0.31-0.70	0.11-0.40	0.11-1.0
Super-		0.051-0.100	0.41-0.50	0.21-0.30	0.71-1.00	0.41-0.60	1.01-3.0
Hyper-		>0.100	>0.50	>0.30	>1.00	>0.60	>3.0

Note: module formulas

HM — hydrolisate module	$(\text{TiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO} + \text{MnO}) / \text{SiO}_2$
TM — titanium module	$\text{TiO}_2 / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$
FeM — iron module	$(\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO} + \text{MnO}) / (\text{TiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)$
FemM — femic modul	$(\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO} + \text{MnO} + \text{MgO}) / \text{SiO}_2$
NaKM — module of normalized alkalinity	$(\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}) / \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$
AM — aluminum-silicon module	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 / \text{SiO}_2$
AlkM — alkaline module	$\text{Na}_2\text{O} / \text{K}_2\text{O}$

All calculations were performed in the office Excel spreadsheet program within the framework of a special algorithm — the so-called “Standard-YuK”, a detailed description of which can be found both in the monograph “Fundamentals of

Lithochemistry” [31] and on the website www.lithology.ru. The site administrator T. A. Sitnikov has made useful improvements to the “Standard-YUK”.

The samples of silicate analyses with calculated petrochemical modules entered in excel tables were subjected to statistical processing, including two types of calculations: (a) frequency graphs were plotted for the contents of manganese (MnO), iron ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3+\text{FeO}$) and manganese module (MnM) and median values (Me) and estimates of the mean standard deviation of the median (sMe) — based on the model of how it was done by us when calculating the Clarkes of black shales and coals [31–34]; (b) estimates of paired correlation coefficients (r) and regression equations for all other components and petrochemical modules were calculated for manganese (MnO) and manganese module (MnM).

In statistical processing of analytical data, we considered correlation significant only at levels no worse than 0.01 and 0.05; for example, $r_{0.01}$ is the designation of the correlation coefficient at the significance level of 0.01, i. e. with 99% “reliability”. We did not consider weaker correlations in order to avoid obtaining unreliable geochemical conclusions. Regression equations with a “two-sigma” confidence interval are plotted on correlation graphs (Fig. 2) [20]; it was built using a special utility (not available in the licensed Excel program) developed by T. A. Sitnikov [17].

Fig. 2. A typical example of a correlation graph.

Correlations of manganese in Paleozoic volcanic and hypabyssal rocks of the Baydaratsky-Miniseisky region of the Polar Urals.

FeM, TM — petrochemical modules [31]: femic and titanium (see above, Tables 2 and 3).

The inscription “2 sigma” in the lower right corner of the graphs means that the confidence interval for the regression equation (dotted line near the direct regression) has been calculated for two “sigma” — quadratic deviations.

2. Statistical estimation of manganese Clarkes

After the pioneering works of J. Vogt as early as the 19th century, when Vogt introduced such an important constant as the manganese modulus Mn/Fe into the geochemical literature, the Clarkes of manganese in igneous rocks were estimated by all the major geochemists of the 20th century: himself F. Clarke, V. I. Vernadsky, A. E. Fersman and A. P. Vinogradov.

However, the accumulation of analytical data required clarification of the figures obtained earlier — first of all, for sedimentary rocks, to which insufficient attention was paid in previous studies (and the number of analyses of sedimentary rocks for a long time was incomparably small compared to igneous ones).

In 1976, K. Wedepohl, in a report at the Sydney International Symposium, evaluated manganese Clarkes according to all available data at that time [40]. An important feature of Wedepohl’s calculations was the accounting of different genotypes of rocks. So, instead of one previous estimate for “shales”, Wedepohl gave two figures — for normal clay shales with $C_{\text{org}} < 1\%$, and for “bituminous” ones, i. e. for rocks that are commonly called “black shales”. The content of Mn in the “shales” and the values of the manganese modulus (MnM) turned out to be completely different: 600 and 150 ppm, 0.013 and 0.008, respectively.

Similarly, greywackes were isolated from sandstones, much richer in manganese (690 ppm) than others (310–88 ppm). The accumulated data allowed K. Wedepohl also give estimates for oceanic pelagic sediments, which turned out to be sharply enriched in manganese (6250 ppm Mn in the Pacific and 3680 ppm in the Indian and Atlantic Oceans).

The next major step in the Clarke geochemistry of manganese was the work of the A. B. Ronov team [15], in which Clarke estimates for such rocks as siliceous and evaporite appeared for the first time.

The most recent estimates of manganese Clarkes are the figures in the widely known “Compendium” of the American geochemist Y. Li [38].

However, the rapid increase in analytical information at the end of the last and the beginning of the current Millennium allows us to propose new estimates of manganese Clarkes, with great attention to the composition of sedimentary rocks.

Unlike our predecessors, when processing statistical aggregates, *we estimated Clarkes not as an arithmetic mean, but as a median mean*, since (especially with small samples) the estimation of the arithmetic mean is strongly influenced by single extreme contents (geochemical anomalies). For example, in 1976, having collected more than 19400 analyses, R. Le Maitre [37] estimated the average chemical composition of 38 groups of igneous rocks. However, our statistical processing of these data [29] has shown a fatal flaw in simple arithmetic (rather than median) averaging: with such a procedure, extreme figures dramatically distort the average values. For example, without two anomalous figures (dunites, MnO = 0.71 % and peridotites = 0.41 %), the MnM value in hyperbasites will be halved against the Clarke of the Earth's crust.

Another illustrative example is Clarke's assessment of manganese in siliceous rocks by A. B. Ronov et al. in 1990 [15]. For siliceous rocks of continents, the figure was 0.292 % MnO (= 0.22 % Mn), and for siliceous sediments of the 1st seismic layer of the ocean — 0.298 % MnO (= 0.23 % Mn). However, our Clarke estimate of manganese in silicites turned out to be much lower — 0.077±0.017 % MnO. The fact is that with a significant dispersion of Mn contents in silicites¹, the presence of strong anomalies in the aggregate overestimates Clarke's estimate in the form of an arithmetic mean; therefore, our Clark estimate of Mn in the form of a median seems more reliable.

In the calculations, we used the same methodology that was used in the estimates of black shale and coal Clarkes [32–34; 36]. The mean square deviation of the median was calculated as

$$\sigma_{Me} = (Q_3 - Q_1) / 2\sqrt{n},$$

where Q_3 and Q_1 are the third and first formula quarters of the frequency distribution, and n is the number of analyses.

In our calculations, n meant the number of sample averages plotted on a frequency histogram. An example of such diagrams is shown in Fig. 3.

In total, we have collected and statistically processed about 1400 sample averages, which corresponds to about 92 thousand rock analyses (Table 4).

¹ This is due to the fact that volcanogenic-sedimentary manganese deposits are located, as a rule, in siliceous strata (for example [4, 13]).

Fig. 3. An example of a frequency diagram used to calculate manganese Clarkes in magmatites of basic and medium composition

Table 4. Median manganese contents in the main types of rocks (Me ± 1sMe)

Material	Number of samples	Number of analyses	MnO, %	Mn, %	Fe ₂ O ₃ +FeO, %	MnM = Mn/Fe
Hyperbasites	26	3599	0.170 ± 0.013	0.131 ± 0.010	11.74 ± 0.98	0.0150 ± 0.0011
Basites	102	2828	0.170 ± 0.007	0.131 ± 0.005	10.27 ± 0.28	0.0170 ± 0.0003
Magmatites of medium composition	89	1370	0.110 ± 0.007	0.085 ± 0.006	5.79 ± 0.25	0.0190 ± 0.0006
Magmatites of acid composition	158	3502	0.050 ± 0.004	0.039 ± 0.003	2.70 ± 0.15	0.0190 ± 0.0008
Magmatites of alkaline composition	28	417	0.120 ± 0.025	0.092 ± 0.019	3.34 ± 1.40	0.0235 ± 0.0020
Hydrothermalites	84	1496	0.285 ± 0.008	0.219 ± 0.006	9.03 ± 1.75	0.0245 ± 0.0220
Metamorphites	75	1454	0.120 ± 0.013	0.092 ± 0.010	7.03 ± 0.52	0.0170 ± 0.0011

Material	Number of samples	Number of analyses	MnO, %	Mn, %	Fe ₂ O ₃ +FeO, %	MnM = Mn/Fe
Metasomites	96	1077	0.100 ± 0.014	0.077 ± 0.010	5.12 ± 0.85	0.0180 ± 0.0013
Aleuro-sandy rocks	92	8862	0.070 ± 0.006	0.054 ± 0.005	3.93 ± 0.19	0.0210 ± 0.0016
Aleuro-clay rocks	81	5969	0.080 ± 0.009	0.062 ± 0.007	5.97 ± 0.27	0.0155 ± 0.0021
Cherts	120	1972	0.100 ± 0.022	0.077 ± 0.017	8.05 ± 1.67	0.0180 ± 0.0023
Carbonate rocks	82	5529	0.110 ± 0.018	0.085 ± 0.014	1.60 ± 0.16	0.0917 ± 0.0164
Nodules	67	672	0.460 ± 0.080	0.354 ± 0.062	11.98 ± 2.88	0.0290 ± 0.0093
Black shales	87	1779	0.100 ± 0.012	0.077 ± 0.009	4.96 ± 0.49	0.0180 ± 0.0054
Hard coals	130	28978	0.0091 ± 0.0008	0.0070 ± 0.0006		
Brown coals	82	23060	0.0130 ± 0.0006	0.0100 ± 0.0005		

The work done allows us to draw several conclusions, including those that require a certain revision of previous estimates.

Let's consider the results obtained for large groups of endogenous and exogenous rocks.

3. Igneous rocks

Hyperbasites. Modal MnO contents fall within the range of 0.10–0.20%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is 0.17±0.01%, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = 0.13±0.01%. This figure coincides with Clarke's estimate of *Y. Li* for the "oceanic crust" (1300 ppm), but above of the Clarke by K. Wedepohl for hyperbasites (1050 ppm). With a median content of Fe = 8.45±0.77%, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is MnM = 0.016±0.001. And this value exactly coincides with the figures of *Y. Li* for oceanic crust and upper mantle, as well as to Wedepohl's — for hyperbasites.

Basites. The modal content of MnO falls within the range of 0.15–0.21%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is 0.17±0.01%, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = 0.13±0.01%. Thus, unexpectedly, the manganese Clarke in basites turns out to be the same as in hyperbasites. However, unlike the latter, this estimate is lower than that of Clarke figure by *Y. Li* for "basalts" (1550 ppm), *R. Le Maitre* for basic rocks (0.15%) and closer to the estimate by K. Wedepohl for "gabbro" (1390 ppm). With a median Fe content of 7.71±0.21%, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is MnM = 0.017±0.0003. This value is lower than

Clarke by *Y. Li* for “basalts”, but exactly coincides with the estimate of the MnM value for the “upper continental crust”, with the figure K. Wedepohl’s for “gabbro” and is close to the figure obtained by processing *R. Le Maitre’s* data (0.016).

Rocks of medium composition (= mesites). It is necessary to note a characteristic feature of rocks of medium composition — their independent, intermediate character between acidic and basic rocks. This is especially pronounced in the grandiose Okhotsk-Chukotsky volcanic belt [9], where “pure” andesites are relatively few, and either andesi-basalts or andesi-dacites predominate (both are either normal or to varying degrees alkalinized), and among the intrusive ones there are not so much diorites or syenites as grano-diorites or grano-syenites.

This circumstance makes statistical processing difficult (it is not always clear where to include this or that analysis). Modal MnO contents fall into a narrow range of 0.10–0.12%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is $0.11\pm 0.01\%$, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = $0.085\pm 0.01\%$. Although this is noticeably lower than Clarke’s estimate by *Y. Li* and K. Wedepohl for “andesites” (1100 and 1160 ppm), and below the figure of *R. Le Maitre* for rocks of medium composition (0.12%), but with a median Fe content = $4.47\pm 0.19\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.019\pm 0.001$, which coincides with the figure *Y. Li* for “andesites”, and *R. Le Maitre’s* estimate (0.020), but much lower than the corresponding figure by K. Wedepohl (0.025). All this suggests that Wedepohl’s estimate of the MnM value for rocks of medium composition was overestimated.

Rocks of acidic composition. Modal MnO contents fall within a wide range of 0.02–0.06%, and the total median content ($\pm 1s_{Me}$) is $0.050\pm 0.004\%$, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = $0.039\pm 0.003\%$. This is exactly in line with Clarke’s assessment by *Y. Li* for “granites” (390 ppm) and the same (!) figure by K. Wedepohl for “grano-diorites”, but has nothing to do with the figure obtained according to *R. Le Maitre* (0.08%). With a median content of Fe = $2.05\pm 0.11\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.019\pm 0.001$. And this value almost coincides with the figure by *Y. Li* for granites (0.018), and with the figure by *R. Le Maitre* (0.020), but much higher than the corresponding figure by K. Wedepohl (0.015). Once again, we have to doubt the reliability of *K. Wedepohl’s* assessment.

Alkaline rocks. Unfortunately, the materials we collected on the petrochemistry of alkaline rocks turned out to be very scarce. The variance of the MnO content turned out to be so significant that it required the use of a logarithmic scale on a frequency histogram; modal MnO contents fall into a wide range of 0.05–0.20%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is $0.12\pm 0.03\%$, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = $0.092\pm 0.02\%$. Due to the small statistics, this figure cannot be considered a full-fledged Clarke estimate of alkaline rocks.

In any case, it is much lower than the figures by K. Wedepohl for trachytes (1240 ppm), phonolites and nepheline syenites (1470 ppm). With a median content of $Fe = 3.93 \pm 1.03\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.024 \pm 0.002$, which, although higher than our figures for all other igneous rocks, is significantly lower than the figures by K. Wedepohl for the above-mentioned alkaline effusions (0.034) and intrusives (0.047–0.045).

R. Le Maitre's data allow us to give a separate assessment for two groups of alkaline and sub-alkaline rocks — basic and medium composition. With the equality of the average Mn contents (0.19 and 0.20%), but with a significantly higher Fe content of the former, the corresponding estimates of the MnM value are completely different: 0.017 and 0.036. In general, there is no doubt that during the formation of sodium alkaline rocks, a strong separation of manganese from iron occurs.

The main conclusions on the geochemistry of manganese in igneous rocks are as follows.

(a) The most important feature of manganese geochemistry in the magmatic process (in any trend of magmatic differentiation) is the close correlation of Mn-Fe due to the isomorphism of Mn(II) and Fe(II) in dark-colored minerals.

(b) The Mn-Fe correlation generates the stability of the manganese modulus $MnM = Mn/Fe$, the average values of which by types of igneous rocks are peculiar geochemical constants (Clarke's of MnM) with a relatively small dispersion. Therefore, any increase in the variance of the MnM value associated with the appearance of abnormally low or abnormally high MnM values for this type of rock serves as a signal of the heterogeneity of the studied set of analyses [29].

Either the aggregate is heterogeneous (heterogeneous formations are improperly combined), or igneous rocks have undergone superimposed processes with selective removal or introduction of manganese (removal or introduction of iron occurs much less frequently — and only in a reducing environment).

(c) Correlations of (MnO, MnM) — MgO and (MnO, MnM) — MgO/CaO are often recorded in basites and hyperbasites, most likely reflecting the processes of fluid magmatic differentiation [12]. At the same time, the correlation for manganese is usually direct, and for the manganese module it is inverse. This means that as the MgO in the melts decreases, rocks that are increasingly poor in manganese crystallize, with a shift in the Mn/Fe ratio in favor of manganese. However, real magmatic processes are much more complicated than this simple scheme, since it is often observed that these correlations change to opposite ones, which may be due to different differentiation mechanisms — for example, crystallization (gravitational) — instead of (or after) fluid [12].

(d) In the prevailing *calcareous-alkaline trend of differentiation* of basalt magmas, as the content of dark-colored minerals (carriers of manganese and iron)

decreases in rocks, the contents of Mn and Fe decrease, but the MnM value usually increases, which reflects a more intensive accumulation of Mn in residual differentiates than Fe.

In these processes, the antagonism (negative correlation) of manganese with alkalis, especially with potassium, is often manifested. However, with the alkaline trend of differentiation of basalt magmas, manganese seems to enrich potassium differentiates. Therefore, the general rule is the accumulation of manganese in potassium lamprophyres and lamproites. In accordance with the ideas of *A. A. Marakushev* [12], it can be assumed that variations in the relationship of Mn with alkalis are due to different fluid composition — aqueous, carbon dioxide, chlorine or fluorine. For example, the sometimes observed direct correlation of MnO–Na₂O in diabase-picrite complexes and kimberlites may be due to the aqueous composition of the fluid.

Although the data available to us are still single, it can be assumed that in the process of silicate-sulfide liquation of basalt magmas, manganese is separated from iron.

(e) Statistical analysis of the basalts of different regions reveals two groups of values of the manganese modulus: 0.013–0.017 and 0.017–0.020. It can be assumed that these values correspond to two genotypes of basalts: crustal, more ferruginous and femic (calcareous-alkaline) and mantle, less ferruginous (tholeiitic). If this assumption is correct, Clarke values of MnM can serve as indicators of the basaltoid genotype.

(f) In calcareous-alkaline rocks of acidic and medium composition, as well as in basites and hyperbasites, as SiO₂ content increases and femicity decreases, the Mn and Fe contents decrease, and the MnM value usually increases. The antagonism of manganese with silicon and potassium is very clearly manifested here (with variable ratios with sodium) and with the agpaicity coefficient [31] — the modulus of normalized alkalinity $NaKM = (Na_2O + K_2O) / Al_2O_3$. In alkaline granites (especially fluoride), manganese, as in alkaline basites–hyperbasites, usually accumulates, and the MnM value is abnormally elevated.

(g) The strange absence of manganese correlations in S-type collisional granites in the Circumpolar Urals is probably natural and reflects their nature — the formation on substrates of different composition.

(h) In the volcanic-plutonic associations “rhyolites–granites”, effusive rocks are richer in manganese than intrusive ones. At the same time, the existence of a paradoxical relationship of manganese mineralization with rhyolites (i.e. rocks with a low manganese Clarke), apparently, is peculiar only to rhyolites of deep origin, whose magma underwent *variolite differentiation* [12] — with the transition of Mn into a glassy matrix, where Mn is in a mobile form, easily extracted by hydrothermal fluid.

4. Hydrothermalites There have been no previous attempts to estimate the Clarke of manganese in hydrothermal formations. In the data we collected, the variance of the MnO contents is so large that it required the use of a logarithmic scale of the frequency graph.

At the same time, the set of MnO values is clearly heterogeneous: it splits into a background (up to 1.0%) with a clearly pronounced mode in the range of 0.10–0.32% MnO and a chaotic “ore” (more than 1.0% MnO). As a result, the total median content of MnO ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is defined as $0.285 \pm 0.008\%$, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = $0.22 \pm 0.01\%$. Due to the extreme heterogeneity of the aggregate, this figure cannot be considered as a Clarke of hydrothermalites, of course, but nevertheless it shows that ***these formations as a whole are undoubtedly enriched in manganese***. With a median Fe content of $8.94 \pm 1.29\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.025 \pm 0.025$, which is higher than in most igneous rocks.

The analysis of the obtained data on hydrothermalites allows us to draw the following conclusions [28].

(a) In accordance with the most complete review of manganese geochemistry made by G. N. Baturin in 1986 [3], it is confirmed that hydrotherms of any genesis are, as a rule, enriched in manganese compared to the cold waters of the hydrosphere. At the same time, the manganese module, a sensitive geochemical indicator of the separation of siderophilic manganese from its rock-forming companion, iron, is also increased in them.

(b) The behavior of manganese in hydrothermal systems is characterized by great complexity due to the influence of several factors on these systems. Therefore, when typifying hydrothermal manifestations of manganese, different approaches are possible — with the allocation of different features as the main ones. Three such typifications are considered: classical mineralogical-geochemical [35], modern geological [8] and purely tectonic. Although it is the latter that is closer to us (with the allocation of the two largest genotypes of Mn mineralization — *marine* and *continental*), it is necessary to keep in mind the presence of a number of manganese ores that are poorly compatible with any of these typifications. This “classification problem” may be, in particular, a consequence of the multistage (polychronous) mineralization caused by the geological evolution of the hydrothermal system.

(c) In the continental Cheleken hydrotherms, an inverse correlation was established between the magnitude of the manganese module and the mineralization of brines and a direct correlation with their pH.

(d) In submarine hydrothermal plumes, as follows from the data of A. V. Dubinin¹, the concentrations and correlations of suspended manganese depend on

¹ Dubinin A. V. Geochemistry of Rare Earth Elements in the Ocean — M.: Nauka, 2006. 360 pp.

the evolution of the plume. In the *young* pop-up Rainbow plume in the Atlantic, the MnM values are significantly lowered against the Clarke plume, and Mn is negatively correlated with Ca and P. Apparently, the accumulation of phosphates in the hydrothermal suspension is accompanied by a decrease in the separation of hydrothermal manganese and iron. In a *more mature* (with neutral buoyancy) plume on the East Pacific uplift, the concentration of suspended manganese is much higher, and the MnM value is sharply increased, which indicates the process of Mn separation from Fe occurring before the observer's eyes as the plume cools and the Fe(II) and Mn(II) contained therein are oxidized.

(e) The *geochemical indicators* of modern submarine hydrotherms include the composition of iron-manganese nodules (FMN) and FM-crusts: high values of the manganese modulus; positive cerium anomaly; high contents of Li, Zn and Ba; the presence of nano-inclusions of rare earth element oxides, native metals and alloys. An important *mineralogical indicator* of hydrothermal metalliferous sediments is the presence of specific autigenic smectites enriched with Mn, Fe or Mg.

(f) Characteristic formations of ancient (Devonian) submarine hydrothermalites can be considered *jaspers*, *jasperites*, *umbrites* and *gossanites*, studied in detail by V. V. Maslennikov [13] and his followers [2], as well as St. Petersburg geologists A. I. Brusnitsyn [4] and E. V. Starikova [18] in manganese and pyrite deposits of the Southern Urals.

With comparable iron contents in jasperites and jaspers, the manganese modulus of the former has a completely "sedimentary" value, whereas in jaspers it is abnormally high (and the MnO content is three times higher), which reflects the relative accumulation of manganese in siliceous hydrotherms.

However, in carbonated and carbonate jasperites, the manganese content increases sharply, which, with commensurate iron contents, leads to an increase in the manganese modulus to values of 0.021–0.024. The average manganese content in low-carbonate umbrites with a very high iron modulus is seven times higher than in high-carbonate ones with a lower iron modulus.

In general, according to the totality of all data, it is established that the hydrothermal ore process was accompanied by a strong separation of manganese from iron; in "real" ores it is manifested 15 times more strongly than in "rudimentary" ones. It is assumed that even a small proportion of alkalis in the hydrothermal solution led to a decrease in the manganese content in it.

(g) During the formation of polymetal continental ores of the Sikhote-Alin in thermal halos of granite intrusions [8; 28], Mn concentrations in hydrothermally altered rocks apparently increased with increasing pH of ore-bearing solutions.

(h) The example of catagenetic (?) Mn ores in the Ordovician of Arkansas deserves special attention among continental hydrothermalites, which, in all probability, are generated by *manganese-bearing brines* and in this respect are similar to the

Mississippian type of concentrations of Zn, Pb, Ba and F. The example of Arkansas ores [28] shows the importance of distinguishing *primary hydrothermal ores* and *secondary* — hypergenetic ores formed due to the weathering of the formers.

5. Metamorphites

In the data set collected by us, the distribution MnO is right-symmetric, resembling a logarithmic normal. Modal MnO contents fall within a wide range of 0.05–0.15%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is $0.12\pm 0.01\%$, which corresponds to the average median content of Mn = $0.09\pm 0.01\%$. This content can be considered as Clarke's estimate of manganese in metamorphites, although due to the heterogeneity of the protolith, this does not make much sense.

However, K. Wedepohl [40] calculated the average composition of metamorphites of the upper continental crust (including gneiss and mica shales, granulites, greenstone rocks and spilites, amphibolites and eclogites) and obtained the figure Mn = 750 ppm. With a median content of Fe = $5.41\pm 0.39\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese module is $MnM = 0.017\pm 0.001$, which coincides with the Clarke MnM for the "upper continental crust", according to Y. Li and with N. A. Grigoriev's weighted (by rock mass) Clarke [6] — 0.017.

Such a coincidence simply confirms the isochemistry of metamorphites in the studied population.

The empirical patterns of manganese distribution in metamorphites are as follows:

(a) During the formation of isochemical metamorphites, all the correlations of manganese that existed in the protolith were preserved, regardless of the stage of metamorphism. In particular, the metabasites are characterized by the bonds of manganese with iron and titanium (as well as with the corresponding petrochemical modules [31] — femic, iron and titanium), and for metapelites — with the hydrolysate module HM, which reflects the connection of Mn with the clay substance of the protolith.

(b) In meta-terrigenous rocks, in the presence of carbonate, the bond of manganese with calcium is always manifested, reflecting the carbonate form of manganese. The presence of such a bond in carbonate-free rocks means that manganese was in the carbonate form in the protolith.

(c) Abnormal decreases in MnM values in metapelites can be attributed to the presence in the protolith some products of redeposition of ancient weathering crusts, during the formation of which selective removal of manganese occurred. This is (among other things) proved by the low MnM values in the chloritoid shales of the Circumpolar Urals.

(d) Strong fluctuations of MnM in the aporiolite shales of the Maldynyrd region in the Circumpolar Urals are explained by the presence of manganese mineralization in them.

(e) The accumulation of Mn in Precambrian ferruginous quartzites means that during most of the Precambrian there was either enhanced chemical weathering of the continents (with Mn^{2+} supplied to the ocean), or there were reduced bottom waters in the ocean in which Mn^{2+} could accumulate. Both of these causes are possible — and both could be the result of low pO_2 in the Precambrian atmosphere.

6. Metasomatites (allochemical metamorphites)

The above figures ($\text{Mn} = 0.09 \pm 0.01\%$, $\text{MnM} = 0.017 \pm 0.001$) concerned isochemical regional metamorphism, in which there is no significant change in the chemical composition of the protolith — except, of course, the loss of volatile components.

However, in reality, the isochemistry of regional metamorphism can only be discussed at the “small-scale” level — that is, when considering the regional metamorphism of entire sedimentary strata of multi-hundred-meter thickness or large bodies of igneous rocks. At the “large-scale” level, i.e. at the level of individual layers of sedimentary strata (or small bodies, dikes or formation intrusions), local processes of introduction and removal of components, most often alkalis, are always manifested.

The largest arena for the development of allochemical metamorphism is the processes of ultra-metamorphism, in which selective melting of protolith occurs with the formation of migmatites.

It has been established that ultra-metamorphism has always been preceded by the processes of alkaline or silica metasomatism — “granitization”.

The processes of *contact metamorphism* in hot contacts of intrusions (especially dikes of hyperbasites or basites), where contact corneas are formed, are also allochemical in nature.

Finally, the processes of allochemical metamorphism (metasomatism) in most *ore deposits* are manifested in the widest way.

In all these cases, more or less intensive migrations of manganese occur. According to the data processed by us, the variance of the MnO contents turned out to be so large that it required the use of a logarithmic scale of the frequency graph. Modal MnO contents fall into a wide range of 0.05–0.22%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{\text{Mc}}$) is $0.10 \pm 0.01\%$, which corresponds to the average content of Mn = $0.077 \pm 0.01\%$. With a median content of Fe = $4.28 \pm 0.85\%$, the average value of the manganese modulus is $\text{MnM} = 0.018 \pm 0.001$, which coincides with Clarke's estimate of MnM for granites in Y.Li's Compendium.

The following main trends can be observed in the geochemistry of manganese in allochemical metamorphites (metasomatites).

(a) In the processes of ultra-metamorphism-granitization of any protolith, there is a decrease in fericity (due to the removal of iron and magnesium) and a decrease

in manganese contents. In general, there is no noticeable separation of manganese and iron in such processes. However, in detail, this trend is complicated by fluctuations in MnM values, reflecting the relatively high mobility of manganese.

For example, during granitization of ancient gneisses of the Aldan shield, against the background of an increase in alkalinity and a decrease in femicity with the removal of Mn and Fe, nonlinear changes occur in the magnitude of the manganese modulus: at first it decreases from 0.019 to 0.012–0.009, but in the leukosome of migmatites it jumps again to abnormal values reaching 0.059 (on average — 0.030). This suggests that migmatization occurred in an oxidizing environment in which manganese was significantly more mobile than iron and went into smelting more intensively than iron.

b) Regional and local processes of *alkaline metasomatism* have different effects on manganese content: potassium metasomatism (microclinization and especially muscovitization) is usually accompanied by a sharp removal of manganese, whereas sodium (albitization) is by no means always, and in some cases, apparently, it is possible to talk about the introduction of manganese, an example of which can be Na-metasomatites in the strata of ferruginous quartzites. At the same time, the MnM value in Na-metasomatites is usually much higher than in potassium ones.

(c) The behavior of manganese in the processes of *near-ore metasomatism* looks much more complex than in the allochemical processes of regional metamorphism: here, along with the removal of manganese, there is undoubtedly an introduction, especially if there is a carbon dioxide process with the formation of hydrothermal carbonates. In such processes, manganese may correlate with calcium, which is completely uncharacteristic for regional isochemical metamorphism, where manganese is closely related to iron.

(d) The behavior of manganese in the processes of *contact metamorphism* is no less complicated, which is expressed in the absence of any general trends in the distribution of MnO and the manganese module.

(e) ***It can be assumed that the main factor determining the magnitude of the manganese modulus in metasomatic processes was the redox regime:*** in reducing media, the mobility of manganese differed little from that of iron (and the MnM value fluctuated little), whereas in an oxidizing medium, iron was fixed, and manganese remained capable to migration, which led to significant fluctuations in the magnitude of the manganese module.

7. The Biosphere

The fundamental essay on the geochemistry of manganese was published by V.I. Vernadsky in 1934 — in “Essays on Geochemistry” [5]. The entire development of geochemistry in the 20th and early 21st centuries confirmed Vernadsky’s

brilliant conclusion about the powerful influence of living matter on the geochemistry of manganese in the hypergenesis zone [22; 26].

Due to the extreme randomness of the available information (especially on living matter and soils), we have not evaluated manganese Clarkes in biosphere objects, but *the study of the collected data allows us to draw a number of conclusions* [26].

(a) The main process in the biospheric geochemistry of manganese is its oxidation with oxygen

As a result, hypergenic Mn(II) minerals are formed — *manganates*, with the general formula MnO_x ($1 < x < 2$). Manganates are characterized by dispersion; some of them contain a significant amount of X-ray amorphous phase and are metastable — with tendencies to transform into more stable crystalline phases

The non-integer value of x leads to the appearance of a *negative charge of the structure of manganates*, so they greedily absorb cations from the environment — Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , etc. As a result, accumulations of manganates can be ore not only for manganese, but also for non-ferrous metals, which, as is known, is inherent in oceanic FMN — iron-manganese nodules and FM-crusts [3; 35]

(b) Despite the thermodynamic resolution of abiogenic manganese oxidation, this process has strong kinetic limitations. *Therefore, the process of biogenic manganese oxidation prevails in the modern biosphere* [26]. The reality of the biogenic process (which some lithologists and mineralogists still doubt!) has already been reliably established both indirectly and directly by laboratory experiments with bacterial cultures (more often mixed and symbiotic — bacterial-fungal), in which almost all members of the natural parageneses of manganates were obtained.

Although the biological feasibility of the Mn(II) oxidation process by bacteria, usually in symbiosis with fungal microflora, is not always clear, it is very likely that this process (mainly extracellular) can: (a) provide electrons for metabolism and/or (b) protect microbial cells from toxicants released in metabolism (for example, from hydrogen peroxide H_2O_2).

(c) Some features and physico-chemical parameters of the biogenic oxidation of manganese have been established [26]: dependence on the concentration of the substrate, pH and Eh values of the medium, close connection with the oppositely directed biogenic process of manganese reduction (with the possible formation of MnCO_3). In recent years, *new data have been obtained on the stable existence of an “intermediate” form of Mn(III) in aqueous solutions* — in complexes with phosphates and/or with organic ligands, including some enzymes and “siderophores” — bacterial products capable of complexing with Fe(III). It was found that although an increase in Eh (i. e., an increase in the concentration of dissolved

O₂) is always favorable for bacterial oxidation of Mn(II), this process proceeds most intensively not in the oxic, but in the suboxic zone above the redox interface (H₂S/O₂) in stratified basins, i.e. at very low concentrations of dissolved O₂.

Among the enzymes involved in the bacterial oxidation of manganese, the exceptional role of “*multicopper*” oxidases containing four copper atoms is revealed.

(d) In the biospheric geochemistry of manganese, the formation of weathering crusts (WC) of two climatic types is of crucial importance: *acidic humid* and *alkaline arid*. In the first, Mn is mobilized and partially removed, in the second, it accumulates. At the same time, the limitation of the actualism method in relation to the currently observed continental hypergenic Mn ore genesis is obvious: under conditions of high Precambrian pCO₂, both Mn(II) and Fe(II) had to be removed from the WC without oxidation — without creating secondary ore concentrations in landscapes. The formation of manganese mineral paragenesis in ancient WC strongly depended on the nature of the primary substrate: essentially carbonate, silicate, oxide or mixed. In particular, during the formation of WC on a carbonate substrate, the presence of relics of primary Mn carbonates in Mn-oxide products is often noted, and if siderites were the substrate, then the formation of manganese-bearing siderites-2 is also noted.

In all cases, there is an intensive separation of manganese from iron, the sensitive indicator of which is a sharp change in the manganese modulus Mn/Fe: most often growth, less often (during oxidation of siderites) — decrease.

(e) In *modern soils*, due to the absorption of manganese by the soil-forming biota, there is some accumulation of manganese compared to the soil-forming substrate. However, the initial assessment by A. P. Vinogradov of the soil Clarke of manganese was, apparently, significantly overestimated.

At the same time, due to the greater mobility of manganese compared to iron, soils are characterized by a decrease in the manganese modulus compared to the substrate. Despite the extreme heterogeneity of figures in the soil science literature, **two empirical patterns can be traced**: (a) the dependence of Mn concentration on the type of soil-forming substrate and (b) dependence on moisture conditions.

Fossil soils [39], in particular Carboniferous, Triassic and Permian soils, are characterized by the same feature as for modern ones — a noticeable decrease in the value of the manganese modulus, which (all other things being equal) can serve as an indicator of paleosols.

Along with the removal of manganese from soils (with entry into groundwater), the second important process is the accumulation of Mn in the illuvial horizon of podzolic soils in the form of soil iron-manganese nodules. The product of such accumulation of Mn and Fe are ore horizons composed of oxides and hydroxides of manganese and iron (mainly, apparently, bacterial — ferrihydrite and vernadite) — is the so-called ortsteins. As shown in his review by the prisoner

of Vorkuta, the outstanding Soviet lithologist and literary critic A. V. Makedonov [11], ***ortsteins are developed over a huge area of the humid zone of the northern hemisphere*** and, with an average Mn content of about 10%, represent a planetary resource of manganese weighing several billion tons.

(f) Manganese is an essential bioelement, as it is part of enzymes that provide redox processes. The biophilicity of Mn is due to its ability to produce complexes with organic ligands, which ensures the *concentration function* of the biota — the extraction of manganese from soil by terrestrial plants and from water by aquatic plants.

In modern terrestrial vegetation, the most manganese species include pine, fir, birch, foxglove and sedge. In woody plants, the manganese concentrator is the bark and, to a lesser extent, the leaves. Herbaceous vegetation has a lower ability to absorb Mn than woody and shrubby vegetation, and the minimum ability is in mosses and lichens.

In landscapes, the increase in moisture leads to an increase in the intensity of Mn absorption by woody and shrubby vegetation, which is probably due to the greater mobility of this element in semi-hydromorphic conditions.

Among aquatic vegetation, the coefficients of manganese uptake by macrophyte algae and ocean plankton are 10^4 – 10^5 , freshwater plankton — 10^3 – 10^4 .

Despite the biophilicity of manganese, most of its complexes with organic ligands are soluble in water, which (as shown above) prevents the accumulation of Mn in carbonaceous bioliths — peats, coals and black shales. Therefore, the organic substance does not exhibit a *barrier function*, but exhibits a *transport function* — a carrier of manganese in soluble humate and fulvate complexes.

(g) As proved by Russian oceanologists, ***ocean essentially biogenic suspensions are an important planetary concentrator of manganese*** [10]. The accumulation of Mn in them creates a prerequisite for the accumulation of Mn in the upper layer of pelagic ocean sediments and for the formation of FMN and FM-crusts — the largest planetary resource of manganese and non-ferrous metals [3;16].

(h) As can be seen from the extensive lithochemical data in the monograph by A. S. Astakhov [1], the climatic zonality of the manganese distribution is manifested in marine sediments, since the climate largely determines the proportion of biogenic components in sediments — carbonates, opal silica and organic matter. Carbonates of reduced sediments can be carriers of manganese, whereas silica is sterile for manganese and always serves as a diluent of Mn concentrations in sediments.

In addition, the climate determines the degree of “maturity” of the terrigenous clastic material entering the sediment (for example, hydromicas in cold climates and kaolinite in tropical climates).

However, climate is not the only factor in the manganese content of marine sediments, there are four other factors at work here: petrofund, topography, diagenesis and submarine hydrotherms.

This factor system has a complex hierarchical structure: some (high-ranking) factors act as independent (or almost independent) of each other, while others (low-ranking) are more or less correlated (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Factor scheme for the system “Manganese in sediments of marginal seas of East Asia”.

It was built based on the materials of A. S. Astakhov, 2001 [1]

(i) Following G. N. Baturin [3], it is confirmed that the manganese contents in *river waters* are very variable; the dispersion of dissolved manganese contents is determined mainly by the climate and rock composition of the catchment areas. In particular, extremely high concentrations of manganese are generated by the drainage of ore territories by rivers.

The accumulation of manganese in brines has been established, which creates a prerequisite for the formation of katagenetic manganese deposits, such as the Arkansas ones, and serves as an explanation for the well-known attraction of manganese concentrations to evaporite strata.

The manganese content in *ocean waters* is highly variable [3, 16]. At the same time, in the literature, the Clarke estimate of manganese in ocean water has steadily decreased due to the improvement of analytical methods and currently stands at 0.0-0.0n micrograms per liter [3].

The maximum concentrations of manganese in marine waters are known in stagnant basins: in the euxine (hydrogen sulfide) waters of the Black Sea, shelf depressions (Baltic, trench Cariaco), and fjords (Framvaren, Saanich, etc.). Despite the difference in details, the picture turned out to be similar everywhere: a sharp rise in the concentration of dissolved Mn below the O_2/H_2S boundary and a drop in

the concentration of Mn to almost zero above this boundary — with the transition of dissolved manganese into suspension.

8. The sedimentary shell

The distribution of manganese by the main types of sedimentary rocks is considered.

Terrigenous and volcanic-terrigenous (tuffoid) sedimentary rocks. In *sand-siltstone* rocks, the dispersion of MnO contents is so large that it required the use of a logarithmic scale of the frequency histogram. The pronounced modal content of MnO falls within the range of 0.032–0.10%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is 0.070 ± 0.006 , which corresponds to the average content of Mn = $0.054\pm 0.005\%$. This figure has nothing to do with Clarke value by Y. Li for “sandstones” (850 ppm), below the figure K. Wedepohl’s for “greywacke”, but its figures are higher for “sandstones”. This is to be expected, since in our calculation these varieties are not differentiated.

With a median Fe content of $2.57\pm 0.14\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.021\pm 0.002$, which does not differ much from Clarke’s estimates of MnM by Y. Li and the Ronov’s team, as well as from the evaluation by K. Wedepohl: for greywackes these figures were 0.024, 0.019 and 0.020, respectively.

In *siltstone rocks*, the high dispersion of MnO contents also required the use of a logarithmic scale of the frequency graph. The modal content of MnO falls within the same range (0.032–0.10%) as for sandy-siltstone rocks, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is slightly higher and is 0.080 ± 0.009 , which corresponds to a higher average content of Mn = $0.062\pm 0.007\%$. The latter is lower than Clarke’s estimate of Y. Li for “shale” (730 ppm), but coincides with the figure by K. Wedepohl for non-carbonaceous clay shales (600 ppm). With a median content of Fe = $4.00\pm 0.20\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.016\pm 0.002$; this value is within the margin of error ($\pm 1-2\sigma_{Me}$) practically coincides with the figures by Y. Li (0.015) and K. Wedepohl (0.013).

The following basic patterns of manganese distribution in terrigenous and volcanic-terrigenous (tuffoid) rocks are established.

(a) The most common pattern is the correlation of manganese with the carbonate content of rocks (with CaO or CO₂), which is not sedimentogenic, but newly formed — the result of the appearance of diagenetic carbonate cements in rocks. In this case, the initial (magmatic) close bond of Mn with Fe weakens or disappears. The values of the manganese modulus increase and become comparable with the MnM values typical for carbonate rocks.

(b) If concretion processes develop at the same time, they are expressed in the most abrupt separation of manganese from iron, which is recognized by an abnormally high value of the manganese modulus, often exceeding even the Clarke

MnM values for carbonate rocks. *An additional indicator of nodule processes may be the correlation of manganese with phosphorus.*

(c) Volcanogenic sedimentary rocks (tuffoids) are recognized by the characteristic “magmatic” positive correlations of manganese with iron, titanium and negative — with the coefficient of appaicity NaKM.

For albite tuffoids, the connection of manganese with sodium, which is completely unusual for normal sedimentary rocks, can be diagnostic. In combination with other signs, the correlation of manganese with phosphorus is sometimes diagnostic.

(d) Therefore, only in petrogenic sandstones (arkoses and greywackes) that have not undergone a strong diagenetic transformation, the initial magmatic correlations of manganese can be preserved — positive with Fe (sometimes also with Mg and P) and with minor elements of its group (V, Cr, Ni, Co), and negative with normalized alkalinity NaKM.

The sometimes observed unusual positive correlation of manganese with alkalis in sandstones may be a consequence (and, accordingly, an indicator?) epigenetic *zeolization* of sediments.

The superimposition of diagenesis on petrogenic sediments complicates all the above-mentioned correlations; for example, while maintaining the primary Mn–Fe bond, a new Mn–Ca bond appears, etc.

(e) In normal (non-recycled) carbonate-free clay rocks, manganese is usually found in the clay substance, which is indicated by its correlations with the hydrolysate module HM and alkalis. Carbonate clays (as well as carbonate sandstones) are always enriched with manganese, and in them, as in sandstones, the manganese modulus is increased.

(f) Lithogenic (recycled) terrigenous deposits can be recognized by abnormal values of the manganese modulus: in sandy rocks it is abnormally high (similar to how it is characteristic of a titanium modulus — the so-called “Migdisov’s regularities” [31]), and in clay, on the contrary, it is abnormally low. The first is explained by the accumulation of manganese in black ore minerals concentrated in the processes of washing and dressing, and the second due to the removal of manganese during the formation of former weathering crusts.

Siliceous rocks. Modal MnO contents fall within a wide range of 0.032–0.32%, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is $0.100\pm 0.002\%$, which corresponds to the average content of $Mn = 0.077\pm 0.017\%$. As noted above, this is much lower than the figures of the Ronov’s team.

With a median content of $Fe = 4.28\pm 1.24\%$, the average value of the manganese modulus turned out to be 0.018 ± 0.002 , which is also much lower than their figures for continental and oceanic silicites (0.071 and 0.083, respectively).

Unfortunately, our “magmatic” estimate of the Clarke value of the manganese modulus (0.018) in silicites forces us to abandon the previously expressed

beautiful idea (based on the Ronov's figure $MnM = 0.071$) of determining the proportion of autigenic components in sedimentary rocks [21], in which it was assumed that such a proportion in the formation of clastic rocks with a value of $MnM = 0.019$ was zero %, and in the formation of silicites with $MnM = 0.070$ was 100 %. Now we have to admit that during the formation of biogenic silicites, there is no noticeable separation of manganese and iron.

The main patterns of manganese geochemistry in siliceous rocks are as follows.

a) In normal biogenic silicites without noticeable influence of volcanism, the correlations of manganese are generally the same as in normal terrigenous rocks: with components of a clay substance (for example, with silicate Al and Fe) in carbonate-free rocks, and with carbonate — in carbonate-containing ones. In both cases, manganese-sterile silica serves as a diluent of the clay or carbonate carrier of manganese. The manganese modulus in silicites with a terrigenous manganese carrier also retains values characteristic for terrigenous clay rocks.

(b) In volcanogenic-sedimentary (exhalative-sedimentary) silicites, the picture is different: manganese can correlate with sodium, with hydrothermal iron, and sometimes with magnesium, and the manganese module is characterized by strong dispersion: from poor values in rocks highly enriched with hydrothermal iron (such as jasperites) to sharply increased in formations such as manganese-rich jaspers or umbrites. At the same time, the Mn–Ca antagonism in umbrites shows that the carbonate in these rocks acts as a diluent for manganese oxides. The distribution of manganese in the distal and proximal *graydites* of the South Ural pyrite and manganese deposits indicates that when the hydrotherms were discharged to the bottom of the Devonian Backwater Sea, the manganese transported in siliceous hydrotherms went further than iron.

(c) In carbonaceous silicites (i. e., in siliceous black shales), the diagenetic removal of manganese, characteristic of all black shales in general, manifests itself, leading to a decrease in the values of the manganese modulus MnM .

(d) Data are available (few so far) that in addition to terrigenous and volcanogenic manganese, a fraction of *biogenic manganese* Mn_{bio} may also be present in silicites, as a result of the realization of the *concentration function* (i. e., lifetime accumulation of manganese) by siliceous organisms-hydrobionts.

Carbonate rocks. The significant variance of the MnO contents required the use of the logarithmic scale of the frequency graph. Modal MnO contents fall within a wide range of 0.032–0.32 %, and the total median content ($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is 0.110 ± 0.002 %, which corresponds to the average content of $Mn = 0.085 \pm 0.017$ %.

This estimate has nothing to do with the figure Y. Li for “limestones” (420 ppm), is significantly higher than the figure by K. Wedepohl (550 ppm), and is quite close to the figure of A. B. Ronov et al. [15] for sedimentary rocks of the continental

block ($0.092\% \text{ MnO} = 0.071\% \text{ Mn}$). With a median content of $\text{Fe} = 0.89 \pm 0.12\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $\text{MnM} = 0.092 \pm 0.002$, which is also much higher than the by Y. Li figure for limestones (0.044) and by the Ronov's team (0.071), whose collection was significantly richer in iron ($\text{Fe} = 3.21\%$).

In carbonate rocks, manganese is one of the few trace elements associated primarily with their carbonate part.

Several empirical patterns are established here.

(a) From the Archean to the Mesozoic, the content of manganese and iron in carbonate rocks decreases. This global trend is explained by the decrease in volcanic manganese supply to sedimentation basins over time.

b) The study of primary (evaporite) and secondary (dia- and catagenetic) *dolomites* shows that they do not differ in average manganese contents, but they differ significantly in the correlations of manganese with other trace elements. At the same time, in secondary dolomites Mn, apparently, is inherited from primary substituted limestones, since it shows antagonism with the dolomite index MgO/CaO .

(c) The general global pattern is the Ronov-Ermishkina climatic pattern [14]: enrichment of humid limestones with manganese compared to arid ones. It can be assumed that the preservation of the “magmatic” Mn–Fe bond in carbonates and, accordingly, the low value of the manganese modulus MnM is evidence of the predominantly terrigenous nature of manganese and the arid climate in the demolition areas. The weakening (or disappearance) of this connection with an increase in the manganese modulus is a sign of climate humidification and/or a hydrogenic source of manganese. The climatic pattern can also determine the regional geochemical background of manganese, in particular, the lower Clarke background reflects the dominance of arid carbonates in the stratigraphic column [23].

(d) In carbonates with near-Clarke manganese contents, the antagonism of manganese with the normalized alkalinity NaKM means that the more feldspar (and less clay) the non-carbonate impurity is, the lower the manganese content.

e) Strong enrichment of carbonate rocks with manganese and sharply increased values of the manganese modulus, as a rule, are due to the supply of manganese to the carbonate sediment from a volcanic source [23].

(f) The increased manganese content of carbonates in sections of the terrigenous-carbonate type is explained by the diagenetic flow of a part of manganese from terrigenous interlayers to carbonate ones.

(g) Deep-water carbonate (and siliceous-carbonate) strata typical, for example, for the Lemva structural-facies zone of the North of the Urals, are usually much richer in manganese than shallow-water ones [23].

Concretions (= nodules). The significant variance of the MnO contents required the use of the logarithmic scale of the frequency graph. Modal MnO contents fall within the range of 0.32–1.00%, and the total median content

($\pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) is $0.46 \pm 0.08\%$, which corresponds to a high average content of Mn = $0.354 \pm 0.062\%$.

Due to the predominance of carbonate nodules in the studied population (and in other nodules, it is carbonate manganese), this figure can be considered a preliminary Clarke estimate of manganese in carbonate nodules. There is nothing to compare it with, since no one has calculated such an estimate before.

With a median content of Fe = $11.98 \pm 2.88\%$, the Clarke value of the manganese modulus is $MnM = 0.029 \pm 0.009$, which corresponds to some intermediate value of MnM in river and sea water. This similarity simply reflects the diagenetic hydrogenic nature of manganese in nodules (entering the solid phase from pore and above-bottom waters).

With regard to nodules (in which the manganese carrier is usually a carbonate substance), the following conclusions can be drawn.

a) Consideration of the geochemistry of manganese in carbonate and carbonate-containing nodules with Mn-carbonates belonging to two structural types: calcite (Mn-calcite, rhodochrosite, siderite, oligonite) and dolomite (Mn-dolomite and Mn-ankerite) confirms the idea that the ***formation of one or another structural type of Mn-carbonates is due to the terms of the diagenesis.*** The latter, in turn, were predetermined by factors of sediment genesis: the amount of organic matter in sediments and the rate of sedimentation.

b) Analysis of the calculated formulas of dolomite-type carbonates shows that the general rule is ***to colonize with manganese only Mg (Fe) positions, but not Ca positions,*** so that the general formula looks like $Ca_{0.50}(Mg, Fe, Mn)_{0.50}[CO_3]$. Deviations from this usual rule (i.e. $Ca < 0.50$) are rare and may not always be reliable.

During the formation of nodular Fe carbonates, the values of the manganese modulus MnM remained at the near-Clarke level for the Earth's crust, but increased sharply during the formation of Ca carbonates, indicating the strongest diagenetic separation of Mn from Fe.

(c) In most other types of nodules (siliceous, silicate, phosphate, sulfate, etc.), the manganese content is determined by the carbonate content in them.

Salt rocks. Evaporite carbonate strata are often enriched with manganese, which is explained by the accumulation of manganese in brines. However, the phenomenon of manganese brine enrichment itself hardly has a purely physico-chemical interpretation. A more likely explanation is in facies terms: the evaporite brines were stratified with the formation of an anoxic environment and the corresponding accumulation of manganese.

Coals. The most modern outline of the geochemistry of manganese in coals is given in the book "Toxic Trace Elements in Coals" [32, pp. 531–550]. According to this essay, the average Mn contents in brown and hard coals are: 100 ± 5

and 70 ± 6 ppm, and in ash, respectively, 520 ± 30 and 490 ± 30 ppm. Low ash Clarkes of Mn indicate its low average *coal-affinity value*. (The *coal-affinity* index is defined as a quotient of the Clarke manganese in coal ash into Clarke manganese in sedimentary rocks [30]). Nevertheless, the Clarke distribution of Mn is characterized by high contrast: there are coals both highly depleted (5–10 times against Clarke) and highly enriched in manganese. In many coals, Mn contents are directly correlated with its contents in the host rocks. Therefore, the coals of platform coal-bearing strata composed of quartz sands and kaolinite clays are usually depleted of manganese, and the coals of molasses strata in piedmont depressions and intermountain depressions are enriched.

Despite the low coal affinity of manganese, all virtual (genetic) manganese fractions can be present in coals: biogenic Mn_{bio} , sorption Mn_{sorb} , nodular Mn_{concr} , terrigenous Mn_{ter} (and less often epigenetic infiltration fraction Mn_{inf}) — in real forms of Mn-containing humates, carbonates, sulfides and silicates. In coals where manganese has low coal-affinity, the proportion of the Mn_{ter} fraction prevails, in coals with high coal-affinity, the autigenic forms of manganese dominate: Mn_{org} and the products of its diagenetic transformation — Mn_{carb} and (or) Mn_{pyr} .

Accordingly, **two types of syngenetic accumulation of Mn in coals can be distinguished**: a) with relative enrichment of only coal, but not coal ash — manganese has low coal-affinity and contained mainly in manganese-bearing terrigenous ash; b) with ash enrichment — manganese has high coal-affinity and also contained in sorption ash. The formation of the second type requires the presence of Mn in peat waters, from where it could be sorbed by peat or brown coal. The most realistic source of Mn in peat waters was the erosion of Fe-Mn laterite weathering crusts along the basite substrate. In this case, the accumulation of Mn in coals should be accompanied by the accumulation of Fe, V, Cr and other elements of the iron group.

The condition for the formation of the Mn_{org} form (and, as a result, the enrichment of coal ash with manganese in comparison with the host rocks) was the alkalization of the environment of coal-forming peatlands, usually associated with an increase in their ash content (facies of flowing peatlands). On the contrary, in very acidic environments (marshy lowland or sphagnum upland peat), manganese did not accumulate. That is why very low-ash coals, as a rule, are very poor in manganese. pH changes in the diagenesis associated with the squeezing of acidic peat waters towards the roof (or soil) of the layers led to the removal of manganese from the central part of the layers towards the roof or bottom. **This is mainly due to the phenomenon of manganese depletion of near-contact margins of coal seams**. It can be thought that the general rule in the diagenesis of the peat formation was the migration of manganese towards the nearest alkaline barrier.

Such a process could be especially effective in the presence of carbonate-containing sediments in the soil or the roof of the coal seam, or in the presence of carbonates in partings (rock layers in coals).

Black shales. The main research on the geochemistry of black shales (including the geochemistry of manganese) was summarized in two of our books: 1988 [27] and 1994 [34]. In 1997, as part of the International IGCP 254 project, we published a brief English-language summary of these books called “*Geochemistry of Black Shales*” [41] accompanied by a specially compiled bibliography of 4931 titles with descriptor keys that allow the reader to find the necessary literature on 11 divisions of the *Black shale* subject. Unfortunately, there were no estimates of the manganese module in our work of the last Millennium. This gap is partially filled by the estimates shown on the new frequency charts.

The main conclusions are as follows.

(a) The Clarke Mn content in the black shales of the world, estimated in two ways, is 440–800 ppm. The contents of >800 ppm can be considered abnormal. Most Mn is in carbonate, somewhat less in terrigenous and volcanogenic, and much less in siliceous black shales. This distribution reflects, on the one hand, the carbonate-affinity of Mn, and, on the other, the role of a relatively manganese-enriched basite clastical material.

(b) In the sedimentary shell section, Precambrian black shales are significantly richer in manganese than Phanerozoic ones. Mn accumulations are particularly strong in the Middle Precambrian (2400 ppm). Fluctuations in the average Mn contents in black shales along the Phanerozoic section are relatively small (200–500 ppm).

(c) The study of manganese correlations in black shales of different ages shows that in the vast majority of cases manganese behaves as a siderophilic element, showing a significant correlation with iron, as well as with petrochemical modules [31], including iron in the numerator of their formulas: iron (FM) and femic (FemM). Manganese usually shows a negative correlation with alkalinity, which can usually be interpreted as an antagonism of manganese and feldspar content. As a rule, a negative correlation of Mn with C_{org} is also manifested, generated by the removal of manganese in the diagenesis of carbonaceous sediments. The same factor (the predominant removal of Mn in comparison with Fe) explains the often observed phenomenon: the value of the Mn/Fe manganese modulus lowered by 2–3 times against the Clarke of the Earth’s crust.

(d) Manganese is not an organophilic element, there is no reliable data on its Mn_{org} form in black shales. The predominant proportion of gross Mn is present in black shales in carbonate form, phosphates (?) and sulfides of Mn are very rare. A wide range of silicates containing manganese appears in graphite-containing metamorphic black shales, but the initial form for them was carbonate.

(e) Syngenetic accumulation of Mn in carbonaceous sediments can be divided into two types: non-specific and specific.

The first type is the accumulation of Mn in most Precambrian black shales, which has a volcanogenic nature. Such accumulations were formed when fields of carbonaceous sediments and areas of discharge of volcanogenic manganese-bearing hydrotherms combined in space. Consequently, ***the accumulation of C_{org} and Mn in sediments is not genetically related, but only paragenetically.***

The second type includes Mn accumulations in some Phanerozoic black shales of the depression type and in carbonaceous sludges of modern stagnant basins. Such concentrations are facially determined; they are due to the preliminary accumulation of dissolved Mn^{2+} in stagnant waters. An example is the Black Sea, in whose waters 100 million tons of dissolved manganese have accumulated, which corresponds to a large deposit [19]. The specific accumulation of Mn in carbonaceous sediments of stagnant sediments is capable of providing geochemical anomalies of Mn by itself. However, it is clear that it proceeded more intensively if increased amounts of terrigenous or volcanogenic manganese entered the “facies trap”. Therefore, the humid climate on the adjacent continent [7; 15] and synchronous basaltic volcanism [23, p. 143] undoubtedly increased the accumulation of Mn^{2+} in stagnant waters, and then in carbonaceous sediments.

9. Manganese as an indicator of lithogenesis

The ability of manganese to oxidize and reduce in a hypergene environment makes it possible to use it as an indicator of environments and processes of lithogenesis: climate, facies, diagenesis, as well as volcanogenic-sedimentary lithogenesis.

(a) The indicator of the climatic situation of sedimentation is the distribution of manganese in carbonate rocks (“*Ronov–Ermishkina pattern*”): All other things being equal, the Mn content in humid carbonates is always significantly higher (on average by an order of magnitude) than in arid carbonates.

(b) In addition to the Mn content in carbonate rocks, for terrigenous rocks, the value of the Mn/Fe manganese modulus can serve as an indicator of climate — higher in humid strata than in arid ones.

(c) In a series of topographic (bathymetric) facies, “continental — coastal-marine — basin” manganese concentrations in sediments and sedimentary rocks tend to increase.

(d) In the series of “freshwater — brackish — saltwater (marine)” hydro-facies, manganese concentrations in waters tend to increase.

(e) In a series of hydro-facies “oxidative — suboxic — anoxic — euxine” manganese concentrations in waters are significantly increasing.

(f) The combined effect of topographic and hydrochemical factors is realized in the strong accumulation of manganese in anoxic depression facies. ***This accumulation gave rise to a grandiose phenomenon in the geochemistry of manganese — the South European Oligocene manganese-bearing basin of the former ParaThetis.***

(g) The formation of manganese deposits from the resource of dissolved manganese accumulated in depressed euxine facies required the movement and uploading of manganese-bearing waters into local areas of shallow sea. Therefore, the very existence of such concentrations of manganese is an indicator of peculiar dynamic facies — the former “*manganese upwelling*”.

(h) The accumulation of carbonate manganese Mn(II) and oxide Mn (III, IV) in sediments and sedimentary rocks is a consequence of the diagenetic redistribution of manganese, and, therefore, is an indicator of diagenesis — reducing and oxidative, respectively.

(i) The process of reductive diagenesis leads to the concentration of Mn^{2+} in the pore waters of sediments and generates a globally manifested phenomenon in the modern ocean — the flow of dissolved manganese from sediment into the bottom waters — a kind of “*manganese respiration*” of sediment. This flow is an important entry point for manganese in the ocean balance. The process of oxidative diagenesis generates the globally manifested phenomenon of FMN in the modern ocean — the largest planetary resource of manganese and non-ferrous metals. Both processes (as shown in Part 3 of the reviewed monograph) are implemented with the decisive participation of the microbiota.

(k) In the diagenesis of *carbonate fossils*, their enrichment with manganese occurs in comparison with the lifetime state of carbonate shells.

(l) In the *freshwater diagenesis* of carbonate sediments, the newly formed calcite-2 is enriched with manganese compared with primary calcite-1.

(m) Other things being equal (climatic, facies, diagenetic), the accumulation of manganese in sedimentary rocks was controlled by subsynchronous volcanism. Such ***volcanism gave rise to a globally manifested phenomenon — manganese-bearing geochemical horizons found in the stratigraphic column in a wide stratigraphic range from the Archean to the Holocene.*** Therefore, the presence of manganese geochemical horizons in most cases can serve as a reliable indicator of the manifestation of volcanism, subsynchronous with sedimentation.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Dr. D.R. Khismatullin for inviting to publish this article.

References

1. **Astakhov A.S.** *Lithochemistry of sediments of the continental margin of East Asia*. – Vladivostok: Dalnauka, 2001. 240 p.
2. **Ayupova N.R., Maslennikov V.V.** *Galmyrolites of the Uzelginsky pyrite-bearing field (Southern Urals)*. – Miass: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2005. 199 p.
3. **Baturin G.N.** *Geochemistry of ferromanganese nodules of the ocean*. – M.: Nauka, 1986, 328 p.
4. **Brusnitsyn A.I.** *Mineralogy of manganese-bearing meta-sediments of the Southern Urals*. – St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University, 2013. 160 p.
5. **Vernadsky V.I.** 2. *Geochemical history of manganese // Essays of geochemistry*. 7th (4th Russian) edition. – M.: Nauka, 1983, pp. 82–100.
6. **Grigoriev N.A.** *Average content of chemical elements in rocks composing the upper part of the continental crust // Geochemistry*, 2003, No. 7. pp. 785–792.
7. **Yemelyanov E.M.** *Barrier zones in the ocean: Sedimentation and ore formation, geo-ecology*. – Kaliningrad: Yantarny skaz, 1998. 416 p.
8. **Kazachenko V.T.** *Petrology and mineralogy of hydrothermal manganese rocks of the East of Russia*. – Vladivostok: Dalnauka, 2002, 250 p.
9. **Kotlyar I.N., Bely V.F., Milov A.P.** *Petrochemistry of magmatic formations of the Okhotsk-Chukotsk volcanic belt*. – M.: Nauka, 1981. 224 p.
10. **Lisitsyn A.P.** *Processes of ocean sedimentation. Lithology and Geochemistry*. – M.: Nauka, 1978, 392 p.
11. **Makedonov A.V.** *Modern nodules in sediments and soils and the patterns of their geographical distribution*. – M.: Nauka, 1966, 284 p. (Tr. of the Moscow Institute of Nature Testers. Vol. XIX. The department is geographical. Sec. sediment. rocks).
12. **Marakushev A.A.** *Petrogenesis*. – M.: Nedra, 1988. 293 p.
13. **Maslennikov V.V.** *Sedimentogenesis, galmyrolysis and ecology of pyrite-bearing paleohydrothermal fields*. – Miass: Geotour, 1999. 348 p.
14. **Ronov A.B., Ermishkina A.I.** *Distribution of manganese in sedimentary rocks // Geochemistry*, 1959, No. 3, pp. 206–225.
15. **Ronov A.B., Yaroshevsky A.A., Migdisov A.A.** *The chemical structure of the Earth's crust and the geochemical balance of the main elements*. – M.: Nauka, 1990. 182 p.
16. **Savenko V.S.** *Physico-chemical analysis of the formation of iron-manganese nodules in the ocean*. – M.: GEOS, 2004. 156 p.
17. **Sitnikov T.A.** *Several utilities to simplify work with geological and geochemical graphs in Microsoft Excel // Bulletin of the Institute of Geology of Komi NC Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences*, 2013, August No. 8 (224). pp. 22–25.

18. **Starikova E.V., Brusnitsyn A.I., Zhukov I.G.** Paleohydrothermal construction of the Kyzyl-Tash manganese deposit, Southern Urals. - St. Petersburg: Nauka, 2004, 230 p.
19. **Strakhov N.M., Shterenberg L.E., Kalinenko V.V., Tikhomirova E.S.** Geochemistry of the sedimentary manganese ore process. – M.: Nauka, 1968, 495 p. (GIN of the USSR Academy of Sciences. Tr. Issue 185).
20. **Tkachev Yu.A., Yudovich Ya.E.** Statistical processing of geochemical data: Methods and problems. – L.: Nauka, 1975. 233 p.
21. **Yudovich Ya.E.** The indicator value of the Mn/Fe ratio in sedimentary rocks // DAN RAS, 2000. – Vol. 375, No. 2. Pp. 233–234.
22. **Yudovich Ya.E.** Paradoxes of manganese geochemistry // Bulletin of the Institute of Geology of Komi NC UrO RAS, 2012, May, No. 5(209). Pp. 19–24.
23. **Yudovich Ya.E.** Regional geochemistry of sedimentary strata. – L.: Nauka, 1981. 276 p.
24. **Yudovich Ya.E., Efanova L.I., Shvetsova I.V., Kozyreva I.V., Kotelnikova E.A.** The zone of interformational contact in the lake square. Rude people. Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 1998. 96 p.
25. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Geochemical indicators of lithogenesis (lithological geochemistry). Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 2011, 740 p.
26. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Geochemistry of manganese in the processes of hypergenesis // Biosphere, 2013. Vol. 5, No. 1. Pp. 21–36.
27. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Geochemistry of black shales. – L.: Nauka, 1988. 272 p.
28. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Hydrothermal geochemistry of manganese. 1. // Bulletin of the Institute of Geology of Komi NC UrO RAS, 2013, January, No. 1 (217). pp. 10-13. 2. Bulletin of the Institute of Geology of Komi NC UrO RAS, 2013, February, No. 2 (218). Pp. 10–16.
29. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Igneous geochemistry of manganese // Bulletin of the Institute of Geology of Komi NC UrO RAS, 2012, December, No. 12 (216). pp. 9-13.
30. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** The inorganic substance of coals. – Yekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2002. 422 p.
31. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Fundamentals of lithochemistry. – St. Petersburg: Nauka, 2000. 479 p.
32. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Toxic elements-impurities in fossil coals. – Yekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2005. 655 p.
33. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Valuable elements-impurities in coals. – Yekaterinburg: Nauka, 2006. 538 p.
34. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** Impurity elements in black shales. – Yekaterinburg: UIF Nauka, 1994. 304 p.

35. **Crerar D.A., Cormick R.K., Barnes H.L.** *Geochemistry of manganese: an overview* // *Geol. Geochem. Manganese. Vol. 1.* (Eds. I.M. Varentsov, Gy. Grasselly). – Budapest, 1980, p. 293–334.

36. **Ketris M. P., Yudovich Ya. E.** *Estimations of Clarkes for carbonaceous biolithes: world averages for trace element contents in black shales and coals* // *Int. J. Coal. Geol.*, 2009, vol. 78, № 1. P. 135–148.

37. **Le Maitre R.W.** *The chemical variability of some common igneous rocks* // *J. Petrol.*, 1976, vol. 17, № 4. P. 589–598.

38. **Li Y.-H.** *A Compendium of Geochemistry. From Solar Nebula to the Human Brain.* – Princeton, NJ: Princeton Univ. Press, 2000. 440 pp.

39. **Maynard J.B.** 7.11. *Manganiferous Sediments, Rocks, and Ores* // *Treatise on Geochemistry* (H.D. Holland, K.K. Turekian, eds.). – Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2003. P. 289–308.

40. **Wedepohl K.H.** *Geochemical behaviour of manganese* // *Geology and Geochemistry of Manganese. Vol. 1.* – Budapest, 1980. P. 335–351. (*Proc. Int. Symp.: Sydney, Australia, 1976*).

41. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M.P.** *Geochemistry of Black Shales. 1. Outline. 2. Bibliography and Index.* – Syktyvkar: Prolog, 1997. 212 pp.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2025.18.45.118

THE MAIN PATTERNS OF TITANIUM GEOCHEMISTRY¹

Yudovich Yakov Elievich

Ketris Marine Petrovna

Russian Academy of Sciences

Ural Branch

Komi Scientific Center

Abstract. *The article presents the main conclusions of the Russian monograph “Geochemistry of Titanium”, published in 2018. The monograph summarizes the data of 43 published Russian works*

Based on statistical processing of ~3500 sample averages (from ~125,000 analyses), new estimations of World averages (Clarke values) for TiO_2 , % (and Ti, %), titanium module ($TM = TiO_2/Al_2O_3$) and phosphor-titanium module ($PTM = P_2O_5/TiO_2$) have been calculated for main rock groups. These include hyperbasites, basites, mesites, acidites and alkaline igneous rocks; hydrothermalites, metamorphites and metasomatites, and some lithologies, such as terrigenous, cherty, carbonates, concretions, phosphates and carbonaceous biolithes — coals and black shales. The calculations allow to perform some new conclusions in Ti-geochemistry.

The purpose of this article is to introduce the foreign reader to the geochemistry of titanium developed in Russia, which is largely unknown to scientists of the Free World.

Key words: titanium, titanium module (TiO_2/Al_2O_3), phosphor-titanium module ($PTM = P_2O_5/TiO_2$), geochemistry, igneous rocks, sedimentary rocks, biosphere, frequency diagrams, average content (= Clarke value), correlations of titanium

¹ Funding: This research was carried out within the framework of the state assignment of the Institute of Geology (Syktyvkar), Russian Academy of Sciences, Ural Branch, Komi Scientific Center

Preface

Russia has huge reserves of titanium and produces the metal in such quantities that it allows for very profitable exports. According to various estimates, Russia supplies the largest American aircraft companies Boeing and Airbus with 40 to 60% of the titanium they need.

As is known, the Komi Republic has large deposits of titanium of at least three genetic types.

Firstly, these are leucoxene sandstones, developed partly in the Southern, but mainly in the Middle Timan. They contain significant reserves of titanium; moreover, technological schemes for the industrial use of these sandstones have long been worked out to produce both titanium whitewash and metallic titanium.

Secondly, the Komi Republic has significant reserves of bauxite in the Middle Timan, an aluminum raw material in which, as is known, titanium concentration can occur (if the initial substrate of bauxite was igneous or metamorphic rocks with a high titanium Clarke, for example, such as basalts).

Finally, thirdly, it was in our Republic that a hitherto unknown genetic type of titanium concentrations was discovered — in *hydrothermal sericitolites*. This type was discovered during the study of the largest industrial deposit of vein quartz and rock crystal in Europe, Zhelannoe (in the Intinsky district of the Circumpolar Urals).

In contrast to these concentrations of titanium, the lack of attention to the problems of titanium geochemistry is striking. In fact, for many years of studying leucoxene sandstones, bauxites or quartz deposits, not a single serious work on the geochemistry of titanium has appeared. As for foreign research, the situation there is no better than ours: we do not know of any serious monographs on the geochemistry of titanium.

From what has been said, it is quite obvious that the fundamental development of the problem of titanium geochemistry is very relevant and is an urgent need. Responding to this need, in 2018, a large monograph “Geochemistry of Titanium” was published in the Laboratory of Lithology and Geochemistry of Sedimentary Formations of the Institute of Geology of the Komi Scientific Center of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

There are four parts in this book: (1) titanium in endogenous formations (igneous rocks, hydrothermalites, metamorphites and metasomatites); (2) titanium in the biosphere (in living and organic matter, in soils, waters and sediments); (3) titanium in rocks of the sedimentary shell (terrigenous and volcanogenic, siliceous, carbonate, phosphate, evaporite, as well as in carbonaceous bioliths — coals and black shales); (4) titanium as an indicator of lithogenesis processes (topo-, dynamo- and hydro-facies in sedimento-genesis).

The fourth part of the monograph is not original — it briefly reviews the results previously published by the authors (in particular, in the book “Geochemical

Indicators of Lithogenesis” [31]), but the results of the first three parts are mostly new — the result of statistical processing of more than 125 thousand complete chemical analyses of rocks. ***This article presents only the main conclusions of the monograph***, in order to familiarize the foreign reader with the results obtained.

1. STAGES AND METHODS OF THE WORK

Titanium is one of the three “minor” elements (Ti, Mn, P), which is included in the standard list of complete chemical analysis of rock — the so-called *silicate analysis*.

This book, based on the lithochemical statistical processing of about 3,500 samples covering about 125,000 silicate analyses of rocks, is similar in structure to our monograph “Geochemistry of Manganese” [32]. Of course, there cannot be a complete analogy of structures, because there are significant differences in the geochemistry of these metals. Manganese is characterized by its participation in redox processes with a change in valence — $\text{Mn (II, III)} \rightleftharpoons \text{Mn (IV)}$ and a very large role of biospheric processes in its geochemistry. Titanium has a sharply predominant basic valence of 4, biospheric influences on its geochemistry are very small, but the property of titanium as a hydrolysate element is decisive in its hypergenic geochemistry.

The consequence of these differences was the difference in the silicate analysis arrays we used. On the one hand, these are the same 1400 samples (about 93 thousand analyses) that were processed in the “Geochemistry of Manganese”. But on the other hand, more than 2,000 samples were added, which were not considered in the “Geochemistry of Manganese”. Therefore, in general, this book is based on much more extensive statistical material than the monograph [32].

The book was created in 2016–2018 in several stages, through consistent work.

At the first stage, our faithful laboratory assistant, **Natalia Valerievna Rybina**, was engaged in the most painful work: she introduced thousands of silicate analyses from published articles and monographs into computer forms of Excel spreadsheet programs. Thus, she prepared many hundreds of primary excel tables.

At the second stage, **Marina Petrovna Ketris** was engaged in special processing of these tables, which consisted of the following.

(a) The primary excel tables have been transformed into the form of our standard excel tables. This means that the digital data of the silicate analysis were supplemented by the calculation of petrochemical modules [36]. For this book, the set of modules was supplemented with the phosphorus-titanium module $\text{PTM} = \text{P}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$, which we had not previously used.

(b) The analyses entered into standard excel forms were, if necessary, divided into homogeneous samples (clusters). This procedure was described at one time both in the “Fundamentals of Lithochemistry” [36] and later in more detail on the

website *Lithology.ru* in the document “*Standard-UK*”, supplemented by useful utilities created by T.A. Sitnikov [23]. It should be emphasized that clustering of analytical data is a creative, and by no means a formal procedure; any attempts to “automate” this process, as our experience shows, cannot do anything good¹.

(c) In the formed sample clusters, the average values (arithmetic and geometric) of all components and modules, as well as the corresponding variances, were calculated.

(d) Paired correlation coefficients of TiO₂ contents with all components and modules were calculated in the cluster samples. Correlation coefficients for TM and PTM were also calculated, but in the future we hardly needed them (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. An example of correlation graphs. The compositions of Pai-Khoi diabbases are shown. The monograph contains about 150 such graphs constructed for one, two, or three to four samples of analyses.

Note that everything described (standard excel tables, clustering and the correlation analysis procedure) is quite similar to those that we used in the “*Geochemistry of Manganese*” [32]. In particular, as there, we considered geochemically significant only the values of correlation coefficients with no worse than with 5% significance level: $r \geq r_{0.05}$. All values of $r < r_{0.05}$ were not taken into account.

(e) For some significant titanium bonds identified in this way, graphs were plotted where the values of components or modules were plotted on the abscissa, and the TiO₂ content, %, was plotted on the ordinate.

(f) Sample averages by rock types (for example, basites, metabasites, sandy, clay, siliceous, etc.) were used to construct frequency histograms necessary for calculating *Clarkes* — similar to how we did it earlier when calculating Clarkes of coal, black shale or manganese [32, 38, 39] — fig. 2.

¹For example, to isolate clusters in the 10-dimensional space of oxides — components of silicate analysis, using the method of multidimensional statistics.

Fig. 2. An example of a frequency graph. The distribution of TiO_2 , TM and PTM for basites is shown. The monograph contains about 20 such graphs constructed for the main types of rocks — igneous, metamorphic and sedimentary.

The standard Excel tables and corresponding graphs processed in this way were sent to the first author to compose the text. This work was carried out in two stages.

Table 1. An example of a summary table — the basis for composing a text. The table for the Kuril basaltoids is given. The monograph contains about 70 such tables constructed for the main types of rocks — igneous, metamorphic and sedimentary.

Table 1. Some average characteristics of the Kuril basaltoids and their comagmatic differentiates. Compiled according to data from the book by V. K. Gavrilov and N.A.Solovyova, 1973.

Volcanites (lithochemical certification)	n	SiO ₂ , %	TiO ₂ , %	MgO, %	Na ₂ O+K ₂ O, %	HM	TM
The Upper Cretaceous of the Small Kuriles. Malokatan formation							
Basalts (pseudohydrolysates)	7	48.72	0.67	4.17	4.21	0.61	0.039
Basalts in fragments of volcanic breccias (alkaline pseudohydrolysates)	4	49.64	0.29	3.88	5.08	0.58	0.015
The same, high-magnesian (pseudosiallites)	2	50.70	0.26	8.83	4.32	0.49	0.016
The Upper Cretaceous of the Small Kuriles. The Malokuril flyschoid formation							
Andesitic alkaline tuffs, little changed (alkalites)	2	63.86	0.44	1.08	12.03	0.48	0.026
Andesibasalt tuffs are slightly modified (pseudosiallites are alkaline)	3	53.55	0.60	3.94	5.47	0.48	0.043
Basalt tuffs are intensively modified (pseudosiallites are alkaline)	6	50.48	0.56	4.85	5.90	0.50	0.034
Volcanic-terrigeneous rocks (pseudohydrolysates)	6	49.19	0.83	6.66	5.11	0.56	0.052
The same, more acidic (pseudosiallites)	3	57.91	0.51	4.05	4.92	0.40	0.038
Paleogene (presumably). Zelenovskaya formation							
Basalts (pseudosiallites)	12	50.18	0.39	6.63	4.83	0.54	0.023
Andesibasalts (pseudosiallites)	2	55.71	0.36	3.93	4.97	0.46	0.020
The Lower–Middle Miocene. The Middle Paramushir formation on Paramushir Island							
Basalts (pseudohydrolysates)	19	49.55	0.49	5.46	4.07	0.55	0.028
Andesibasalts (pseudosiallites)	9	54.00	0.47	4.34	3.77	0.47	0.028
The same, ferruginous (FeM = 0.83, pseudosiferlites are alkaline)	2	53.04	0.59	3.09	5.75	0.52	0.041
Titanium andesibasalts (pseudosiallites)	2	53.29	1.64	3.86	2.69	0.31	0.084
Andesites from volcanic breccias (normosiallites)	11	60.37	0.50	2.29	4.90	0.39	0.028
Rhyodacites and dacites (alkaline myosilites)	3	67.53	0.35	1.92	5.38	0.27	0.025
The Upper Miocene–the Pliocene. The Okhotsk formation on Paramushir Island							

Volcanites (lithochemical certification)	n	SiO ₂ , %	TiO ₂ , %	MgO, %	Na ₂ O+K ₂ O, %	HM	TM
Calcium-enriched basaltoids (pseudohydrolysates)	6	47.94	0.49	5.03	2.91	0.61	0.026
Basalts in fragments of volcanic breccias (pseudohydrolysates)	16	49.87	0.54	5.21	4.52	0.55	0.031
Andesibasalts in fragments of volcanic breccias (pseudosiallites)	25	54.70	0.51	3.73	4.25	0.46	0.029
The same, more titanic (pseudosiallites)	5	54.07	1.32	4.40	3.08	0.50	0.072
Andesites in fragments of volcanic breccias (normosiallites)	8	62.49	0.53	1.91	4.64	0.36	0.031
Dacites (alkaline hyposilites)	4	70.44	0.33	1.46	5.48	0.22	0.025
The Pliocene. The Ocean formation on Paramushir Island							
Basalts in fragments of volcanic breccias (pseudohydrolysates)	15	49.60	0.49	4.00	3.07	0.60	0.025
Andesibasalts in fragments of volcanic breccias (pseudosiallites)	7	56.54	0.54	3.03	4.21	0.47	0.030
The same, more titanic (pseudosiallites)	6	53.46	1.20	3.82	4.18	0.53	0.068

n is the number of analyses, TM (titanium module) = TiO_2/Al_2O_3 , HM (hydrolysate module) = $(TiO_2+Al_2O_3+Fe_2O_3+FeO+MnO)/SiO_2$, FeM (iron module) = $(Fe_2O_3+FeO+MnO)/(TiO_2+Al_2O_3)$.

In the contents of MgO and Na₂O+K₂O, the values taken into account in the lithochemical classification of rocks as “pseudo-sedimentary” (MgO > 3.0%) and “alkaline” or even “alkalites” [(Na₂O+K₂O) > 5 or > 8%] are **highlighted** [36].

(g) The interpretation of these tables — that is, the compilation of the final text of the book.

At first, this final stage seemed to first author not only pleasant, but also quite simple... It would seem: what is difficult for a geochemist with half a century of experience [35] in describing the tables and ready — made graphs compiled by him? Unexpectedly, however, a very serious difficulty arose. The reason for this difficulty was the *enormous amount of primary materials prepared by M. P. Ket-ris!* It was necessary to select only a very few from thousands of average figures and hundreds of graphs, “cruelly” discarding the description of the rest, obtained by the hard work of the second author.

2. SOME GENERAL INFORMATION

In our literature, an essay on the geochemistry of titanium was given by A. E. Fersman in the 4th volume of his “Geochemistry” [25], then in a more modern summary-handbook by V. V. Ivanov [8]. In addition, data on the distribution of titanium in magmatic differentiation processes can be found in A. A. Marakushev’s book “Petrogenesis” [17], and some information on the mantle geochemistry of

titanium is given in B. G. Lutz's book [16]. Unfortunately, we do not know reports or reviews regarding the hypergenic geochemistry of titanium.

A. E. Fersman [25, pp. 127–128] emphasized the amphotericity of titanium, which brings it closer to aluminum. Among the cations and anions of the 4th group of the Periodic Table, the opposite attitude to the change in the pH of the medium is observed.

“Depending on the pH (with its increase and especially with an increase in temperature), the second row becomes important, starting from left to right; with a decrease in pH, the value of the first row increases, from left to right. Therefore, in an acidic environment, for example, in acidic volatile eruptions of magmas and ore emanations, we find minerals of the TiO_2 type in abundance, whereas in alkaline pegmatites salts of complex acids — $[\text{ZrO}_4]^{4-}$ and $[\text{ThO}_4]^{4-}$ will more often form and accumulate.”

Noting the similarity of titanium with elements of its group, Fersman points out that due to its amphotericity, the picture of titanium's geochemistry is more complex than that of its neighbors in the group [25, p. 128].

According to the summary-handbook of V. V. Ivanov [8, p. 16], titanium belongs to the main d-elements. Being in the IV group of the Periodic Table, in nature titanium associates with its neighbors vertically (Si, Zr), horizontally (Sc, V, Fe) and diagonally (Al, P, Nb, Y). Of the listed elements, *“widespread (Fe, Al, Si) determine its behavior, and it, in turn, determines the geochemistry of rare d-metals (Sc, Zr, Nb, Y)”* [8, p. 16].

Although titanium is considered amphoteric (that is, it can form both cations and anions), in the most common valence Ti(IV) it forms a stable cation $[\text{TiO}]^{2+}$, forming positively charged complexes with F and organic additives that stabilize colloidal systems.

In 1950, A. N. Zavaritsky empirically identified 11 groups of elements in the Periodic Table that form stable association groups in igneous rocks. Among them there is the *“iron family”* (which partly includes Goldschmidt's *“siderophilic elements”*): Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni. It is obvious that the ingress of elements into the *“iron family”* has a crystallochemical reason — the proximity of ionic radii in the most common degrees of oxidation.

The frequent presence of titanium in rock-forming minerals is explained by the fact that the Ti(IV) atom has the highest valence among common metals; this *“makes it the best compensator for the excess of negative valences in rock-forming minerals with heterovalent isomorphism <...>”* [8, p. 18].

The isomorphic entry of titanium into minerals can occur according to the schemes of isovalent and heterovalent isomorphism (M – ion):

Summarizing these schemes, V. A. Kopeikin writes in his textbook for Ukhta students [10, p. 79]:

“The Ti^{3+} ion is replaced in the lattice of minerals by the type of imperfect isovalent isomorphism into Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} ions. The Ti^{4+} ion is replaced by imperfect isovalent isomorphism into Si^{4+} , Sn^{4+} , and Zr^{4+} ions. According to the type of perfect heterovalent isomorphism, it is replaced by Cr^{3+} and V^{3+} , and according to the type of imperfect heterovalent — by Fe^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Nb^{5+} and Ta^{5+} .”

Since the entry of titanium into silicates usually occurs by the mechanism of heterovalent isomorphism, this process depends on the availability of ions such as Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} and Al^{3+} . For this reason, for example, the entry of Ti into augite (where there is Al^{3+}) is easy, and into diopside is very limited.

According to V. V. Ivanov’s summary, in endogenous processes titanium forms both its own minerals and impurities in rock-forming oxides and oxosols, and in exogenous processes it mainly forms its own minerals. As of 1990, more than 150 titanium minerals were known, with silicates (72) and oxides (55, including 21 titanates) dominating among them. The most common titanium minerals are only 5–7:

ilmeneite $\text{Fe}[\text{TiO}_3]$, perovskite $\text{Ca}[\text{TiO}_3]$, rutile TiO_2 (with anatase and brookite polymorphs), ilmenorutyl FeTiNbO_6 , sphen $\text{CaTi}[\text{SiO}_5]$ (now called titanite), titanomagnetite $\text{Fe}^{2+}(\text{Fe}^{3+}, \text{Ti})_2\text{O}_4$, leucoxene $\text{TiO}_2 \cdot \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

As you can see, among the most common are only one silicate (titanite), and the others are oxides and oxosols (including two titanates). Leucoxene is formed in exogenous processes due to the oxidation of Fe(II), which is part of titanium minerals, occupying a place in the series of decomposition and subsequent crystallization-dehydration:

These processes are actually very complex; many researchers have devoted their efforts to studying them, and in particular the role of members of this generalized series as indicators of lithogenesis processes [34].

In addition to its own minerals, titanium impurities are found in significant quantities in ferrous and iron-magnesian minerals: titanomagnetite (especially in differentiated low-magnesian basalts), as well as in olivines, pyroxenes, amphiboles and micas.

3. TITANIUM IN IGNEOUS ROCKS

In his book “Petrogenesis”, A. A. Marakushev gave a table of 82 compositions of varioles (balls) and a matrix of layered intrusions, in which 5 different differentiation trends are distinguished: norite-orthopyroxenite, komatiite, basalt-phonolite-trachyte, basalt-andesite-rhyolite and ferribasalt-icelandite [17, pp. 222–224]. This table shows the atomic quantities of 12 elements, converted into 50 oxygen atoms: Si, Ti, Al, Fe (II), Fe (III), Mn, Mg, Ca, Na, K, P, and the minor element — Cr.

If we do not take into account the differences in trends, then the correlation analysis performed by us can only give the most generalized characteristic of the behavior of titanium during the differentiation of the initial “pyrolyte” — a certain average mantle magma of approximately picrite composition. Such an analysis showed significant correlations of titanium with a number of elements (for this population $r_{0.01} = 0.28$). It turned out that titanium is negatively correlated with silicon and magnesium, which selectively accumulate in varioles, and positively with iron, calcium, phosphorus, and most of all with manganese.

If we now perform a correlation analysis separately according to these trends, we will get a more detailed picture. It turns out that the *correlations of titanium may differ in the five trends of magmatic differentiation*.

1. **In the sample of analyses of the Bushveld pluto**, titanium has no significant correlations with other elements, although the matrix is noticeably richer in titanium than the variole balls: 0.116 atomic quantities versus 0.075. It is known that the Bushveld Pluto has a platinum-bearing layer — the so-called “Merensky reef”. As A. A. Marakushev notes [17, p. 225], the magmatic splitting manifested here

“undoubtedly played an important role in its formation. It reflects the mafic-ultramafic trend of stratification of massifs associated with the impact of water-hydrogen fluids on intermediate (picrite, etc.) magmas. This trend is fundamentally different from the trends of the later stratification of residual basaltic magmas, representing ferribasalt–icelandite <...>, basalt–andesite <...> and alkaline basalt–trachyte <...> trends in the magmatic (liquation) differentiation of magmas proper”.

2. **In the sample of analyses of the komatiite trend**, the matrix is also richer in titanium than varioles: 0.223 atomic quantities versus 0.195. Here titanium is clearly negatively correlated with aluminum and calcium, and positively with divalent iron.

3. **In the sample of analyses of the alkaline trend** (basalt–phonolite–trachyte), the matrix and varioles practically do not differ in titanium contents. Here, titanium is negatively correlated with silicon, and as a result, positively with a number of other elements, most strongly with divalent iron and calcium.

4. **In the sample of analyses of the usual homodromic trend** of magmatic differentiation (basalt–andesite–rhyolite), titanium is sharply negatively correlated with silicon, and positively with divalent iron and manganese, and most strongly

with phosphorus! But at the same time, titanium enriches not the matrix here, but the varioles (atomic amounts 0.19 and 0.40, respectively).

In the aggregate (n = 16) analyses of the stratified Skaergaard intrusion [17, p. 53], we estimated the average characteristics for two groups of alternating rock layers — variolites (more acidic) and residual matrix (more basic). As a result of the liquation of magma of initially medium composition, the residual matrix is enriched with titanium, manganese and phosphorus.

The residual matrix (n = 8): $\text{TiO}_2 = 4.38\%$ (3.22–7.66), $\text{TM} = 0.720$ (0.405–1.724), and $\text{PTM} = 0.86$ (0.08–2.22), while the content of P_2O_5 reaches 7.75%. Rocks are certified as hydrolysates ($\text{HM} = 0.90$, $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO} = 28.42\%$).

Variolites (n = 8): $\text{TiO}_2 = 1.20\%$ (0.21–2.75), $\text{TM} = 0.02$ (0.016–0.260), and $\text{PTM} = 0.66$ (0.19–0.85), while the content of P_2O_5 reaches 1.70%. The breeds are certified as myosilites ($\text{HM} = 0.27\%$)

In total, titanium is negatively correlated with silicon and alkalis, and, accordingly, positively correlated with a number of other components, especially manganese.

5. Finally, **in the sample of the “oceanic” ferribasalt–icelandite trend**, we again see the enrichment of the matrix with titanium compared to the varioles (1.01 vs. 0.43), and the negative correlation of titanium not only with silicon, but also with aluminum, which is unusual. Titanium is positively correlated with ferrous oxide and calcium, but even more strongly with manganese.

All these correlations may have “practical significance” for us: by establishing certain correlations of titanium in aggregates of magmatites differentiated by their basicity and alkalinity, we can assume that these rocks have undergone one or another type of magmatic differentiation. Such (non-obvious) information is important because, as A. A. Marakushev points out, primary varioles are very poorly preserved in real rocks, and therefore the magmatic differentiation that actually took place can often be judged only by indirect signs.

3.1. Hyperbasites

As is known, titanicity in petrology has long been used for the purposes of classification of ultrabasic volcanites. According to the Petrographic Code of 1995 and its second edition in 2000, hyperbasic effusions are called, according to the proposal of Chermak (1866), picrites, which are divided into two groups according to the magnitude of titanicity. E. A. Landa and B. A. Markovsky [13, p. 52] believe that in order to maintain the petrochemical principle when naming ultrabasic volcanites, their structural variety, komatiites, should not be given an independent taxonomic rank of the family; in their opinion, it is simply a low-titanic variety of picrites. If we replace the value $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ (i. e. $1/\text{TM}$) used by them with the much more familiar value $\text{TM} = \text{TiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, we get two gradations of picrites in

terms of titanicity: high-titanic, $TM > 0.333$ (for example, meimechites); low-titanic, $TM < 0.333$ (for example, komatiites).

These most general empirical patterns can be detailed by considering analytical data on the USSR or Russia, which can also be divided into two groups by titanicity.

Rocks of the first group (with reduced titanicity) can be called “normal”, since TiO_2 contents less than 1.0% correspond to the Clarkes of titanium in hyperbasites accepted in the literature. It can be assumed that during the basite-hyperbasite stratification of the mantle “pyrolyte” (3 parts of hyperbasite + 1 part of basite), titanium predominantly goes into basite smelting, which provides a much higher Clarke Ti in basites than in hyperbasites. The latter, therefore, will correspond on average to the “depleted mantle”. Obviously, in such a process, one can expect a negative correlation of titanium with magnesium, and a positive correlation with calcium and even, perhaps, with silicon.

Rocks of the second group (with increased titanicity) can be conditionally called abnormal. Such enrichment occurs in parallel with the increase in the alkalinity of rocks. This has a simple chemical explanation: titanium turns out to be very mobile in alkaline media, which is clearly manifested in powerful Ti concentrations in some hydrothermal sericitolites [20]. Apparently, when the mantle was “purged” with deep alkaline fluids (an idea that was vigorously developed by academician A. A. Marakushev [17]), Ti did not go into basite smelting, but titanium-enriched alkaline hyperbasites were formed directly through the “pyrolytic” matrix. A similar process is very likely for carbonatites, which are closely related to alkaline hyperbasites.

The results we have obtained are as follows.

1. The average median values ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) for hyperbasites, calculated on the basis of 72, 72 and 42 samples, are $0.31 \pm 0.06\%$ for TiO_2 (or $0.17 \pm 0.03\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.067 ± 0.007 and 0.35 ± 0.04 for TM and PTM, respectively. These figures can be considered our estimates of the Clarkes of hyperbasites.

2. Most hyperbasites are depleted of titanium. This can be considered an indirect indication that such hyperbasites are “residual” — the product of “depletion” of the mantle, with the departure of a significant part of titanium into basite smelting. A reliable sign of such a process can be the negative correlation of titanium with magnesium.

3. Titanium-enriched hyperbasites are much less common. As a rule, such rocks are relatively enriched with alkalis (primarily potassium). This enrichment can be associated with primary basite/hyperbasite stratification under the influence of alkaline fluids. A sign of such a process can be a positive correlation of titanium with aluminum and/or with alkalis.

3.2. Basites

The geochemistry of titanium in basites (igneous rocks of basic composition containing 45–53 % SiO_2) is similar in many respects to that in hyperbasites due to the close genetic relationship of basites with hyperbasites. During the basite/hyperbasite stratification of the mantle (which in petrographic terms is often called *mafic/ultramafic*), basitic magma is formed, which forms gabbroids during intrusions, and basaltoids during volcanic eruptions. The latter are so abundant in the lower part of the earth's crust that they gave it its own name — the “basalt layer”.

According to the extent to which basite/hyperbasite stratification occurred in the initial substance of the mantle, that is, it was depleted of its basite component, it is customary in Western literature to speak of a strongly or weakly depleted mantle. As is commonly believed in modern petrology, the degree of such “depletion” depends, in turn, on the intensity of the fluid effect on the mantle substance [17].

The results obtained by us are as follows.

1. The average median value for basites ($\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}}$), calculated on basis 363, 344 and 256 samples, are $1.24 \pm 0.03\%$ (or $0.74 \pm 0.02\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.078 ± 0.002 and 0.15 ± 0.004 for TiO_2 , TM and PTM, respectively.

These figures can be considered our estimates of the Clarke value for basites.

2. In terms of titanicity, basites can be divided into 2 groups: (a) low-titanium ($\text{TiO}_2 < 1.00\%$, TM < 0.070) and (b) normal- and high-titanium ($\text{TiO}_2 > 1.00\%$, TM > 0.070). As has long been established in petrology, most of the low-titanic basites are island-arc. The most striking Russian example of low-titanium basites is the so-called *Kuril titanium phenomenon*. In Upper Cretaceous and Neogene basaltoids (and in comagmatic more acidic differentiates) the sample average TiO_2 contents of the Small Kuriles and Paramushir Islands are 0.26–0.83 %, and TM = 0.015–0.041. In accordance with the hypothesis of prof. G. S. Gorshkov, put forward by him back in 1967, the cause of the Kuril phenomenon is the generation of basaltoids not in the crust, but directly in the mantle — from mantle “tongues”, raised to a depth of about 60 km from the daytime surface.

3. We assume that the basite/hyperbasite stratification of the mantle with the formation of low-titanium basites could lead to titanium enrichment of the residual hyperbasite matrix. Perhaps it will still be found in the area of the Kuril Island Arc or its more mature analogues — Kamchatka and Japan.

4. The most characteristic correlations of titanium in basites form two types: (a) negative correlation of Ti–Mg and positive Ti–Fe, Ti–P; (b) negative correlation of Ti–Si and positive Ti–(Na+K) and a number of others, including again Ti–Fe, Ti–P. The first type of bonds most likely reflects the primary basite-hyperbasite stratification of the mantle, whereas the second is a later process of normal homodromic differentiation of basalt magma in the basalt–andesibasalt–andesite series.

5. The correlation of titanium with phosphorus, already known in petrology, has been confirmed on a large statistical material. Apparently, the initial “primary mantle” value of the phosphorus-titanium module in basites ($PTM = P_2O_5/TiO_2$) is in the range 0.10–0.25. Any deviation from these values to a greater or lesser extent provides information about the processes of selective introduction/removal of either titanium or phosphorus and thus can be used for deciphering the genesis of the basites themselves.

3.3 Mesites

As noted in the “Geochemistry of Manganese” [32], igneous rocks of medium composition containing 54–64% SiO_2 , which can be called *mesites* based on the sample of *basites*, are very unpleasant for the purposes of strict classification. The fact is that they seem to be independent, occupying an intermediate position between gabbro and granodiorite among intrusive rocks (diorites and tonalites), and between basalt and rhyolite among effusive rocks (andesites and dacites). Due to this intermediate position, they can be closely related to both basic rocks (such as andesi-basalts) and acidic ones (such as rhyo-dacites). This always creates uncertainty when grouping data for calculating average compositions: where should this sample be attributed?

Due to the “intermediate”, non-independent position of mesites in the petroge- netic series of igneous rocks, they are often present in close association with either basites (rocks more titanic) or acidites (rocks less titanic). For this reason (heteroge- neity of analytical aggregates), the estimates of mesite Clarkes are not completely reliable. However, the more alkaline varieties of mesites tend to be more titanic.

The situation is further aggravated by the fact that among rocks of medium composition, alkaline varieties are found much more often than among others, which also give quite gradual transitions to rocks of normal alkalinity. For this reason, many alkali-enriched andesites are certified in lithochemistry as *alkalites* rather than as *siallites*, which is typical for mesites of normal alkalinity.

The results we have obtained are as follows.

1. The average median value for mesites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 93, 93 and 56 samples, are $0.73 \pm 0.01\%$ (or $0.44 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.045 ± 0.001 and 0.29 ± 0.01 for TiO_2 , TM and FTM, respectively. These figures can be considered our estimates of the Clarke value for mesites.

Thus, the titanium Clarke in mesites is significantly lower than in basites. For the same reason, the value of the phosphorus-titanium PTM module in mesites is twice as high as in basites.

2. Titanium in mesites is usually positively correlated with iron (indicating the predominance of the accessory mineral form) and less often with aluminum (indi- cating the predominance of the silicate form). In normal (non-alkaline) varieties of

mesites, the negative correlation of titanium with potassium is quite characteristic, reflecting the process of normal homodromic magmatic differentiation.

3.4. Acidites

The geochemistry of titanium in acidites (igneous rocks of acidic composition containing 65–78% SiO_2) is determined almost exclusively by the content of dark-colored silicates-carriers of titanium in them: first of all biotite, then amphiboles and some pyroxenes. Titanium is also present in many muscovites. As for the accessory carriers of titanium (ilmenite, rutile, leucoxene, titanomagnetite, sphene-titanite, as well as such exotic accessories as perovskite), they are most often inferior to silicates as titanium carriers. It is possible to make a plausible judgment about the predominant form of titanium in acidic magmatites based on the correlations of titanium. With the dominance of silicate titanium, a positive correlation of $\text{TiO}_2\text{--Al}_2\text{O}_3$ can be expected, and with the dominance of accessory titanium, a positive correlation of $\text{TiO}_2\text{--}(\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3+\text{FeO})$.

In lithochemical systematics, acidic magmatites are most often certified as *alkaline myosilites*, that is, compositions with HM 0.20–0.30 and the amount of alkalis $>5\%$. In the case of an abundance of quartz, they become *normosilites* (HM 0.10–0.20), and alkaline differences are often certified as *alkalites* ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}+\text{K}_2\text{O} > 8\%$).

The TiO_2 content in acidites is significantly lower than in mesites (and even more so in basites), and is usually in the range of 0.20–0.50% with a median value of about 0.25%, with an obvious increase in rocks such as granodiorites and dacites. Similarly, TM values are significantly lower than in mesites (and even more so in basites); the typical range of values is 0.020–0.030, with a median value of about 0.025, but in some rhyolites (for example, in our North Ural ones), TM values fall even below 0.010, which allows (without having petrographic information) to accurately distinguish rhyolites from acidic sedimentary rocks such as silicites or quartz sandstones.

As for the phosphorus-titanium PTM module, despite the frequent preservation of the “mantle” correlation of $\text{TiO}_2 - \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ in rocks, the PTM values are usually higher than in mesites and even more so in basites; the typical range of PTM values is 0.20–0.50 with a median value of about 0.25. However, in especially phosphorus-poor rocks (such as some ultra-acid granitoids) PTM can drop to 0.10 and even lower. Of course, it would be interesting to find some systematic differences in the titanicity of the two main genotypes of granitoids — ancient metamorphogenic (products of palingenesis), closely related to gneiss and migmatites, and younger (products of differentiation), genetically related to the original basitic magmas. It can be thought that ancient metamorphogenic granitoids formed on various substrates with different titanicity should at least

have a greater dispersion of titanium contents and, accordingly, a greater spread of TM and PTM values.

The results we have obtained are as follows.

1. Estimates of Clarke values of TiO_2 , TM and PTM calculated on a huge analytical base are $0.32 \pm 0.01\%$ (or $0.19 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.024 ± 0.001 and 0.27 ± 0.01 , respectively.

2. As a rule, rocks of the granodiorite type turn out to be more titanitic, and more acidic granitoids are less titanitic, enriched with alkalis. As expected, the most titanitic are granitoids with noticeable contents of dark-colored minerals — amphiboles and biotite. At the same time, ancient metamorphogenic acidites-charnokitoids, closely related to basites, turn out to be the richest in titanium.

3. Most acidites are characterized by a negative relationship of titanium contents with SiO_2 , and the resulting (due to the closed nature of the percentage system) “artificial” positive relationship with most of the other components and modules derived from them, especially with the femicity of FemM. However, negative correlations of titanium with sodium (i.e., with the albite component of plagioclases), and often also with the alpaicity — $(\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O})/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, are quite natural. Equally reliable are the positive bonds of titanium with minor components of acidites — not only with iron or magnesium (meaning the entry of titanium into ore accessories or biotite), but often with phosphorus. The latter, as we saw in sections 2.1 and 2.2, is characteristic of the behavior of titanium in hyperbasites and basites, therefore it may indirectly indicate the mantle character of such acidites.

3.5. Alkaline rocks

Alkaline varieties of magmatites are closely related to rocks of normal alkalinity, therefore it is undesirable to separate them from each other. For this reason, we often included in the tables typical representatives of magmatites and some samples of analyses of rocks with increased alkalinity — for example, melanocratic syenites of the Avashli complex in the South Urals. At the same time, alkaline rocks deserve separate consideration, as was done in the “Geochemistry of Manganese” on the basis of more than 500 analyses [32, pp. 73–76].

The materials reviewed allow us to draw several conclusions.

1. The average median ($\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}}$) values for the totality of all alkaline magmatites obtained on the basis of 154, 154 and 124 samples are $1.19 \pm 0.07\%$ (or 0.71 ± 0.04 for elementary Ti), 0.074 ± 0.006 and 0.30 ± 0.01 for TiO_2 , TM and PTM, respectively.

2. It is clear that these figures are of purely “academic” interest, since the titanicity of alkaline rocks of different silicic acids is also completely different; in Table. 2 approximate estimates of the average titanicity of alkaline rocks are given in comparison with similar estimates for rocks of normal alkalinity:

Table 2 Titanicity of magmatites of different alkalinity

Rocks	Normal			Alcaline		
	TiO ₂ %	TM	PTM	TiO ₂ %	TM	PTM
Hyperbasites	0.31±0.06	0.067±0.007	0.36±0.04	2.39±0.20	0.269±0.023	0.21±0.02
Basites	1.24±0.03	0.078±0.002	0.15±0.01	1.82±0.11	0.111±0.007	0.31±0.02
Mesites	0.75±0.01	0.046±0.001	0.028±0.01	0.74±0.04	0.043±0.003	0.34±0.02
Acidites	0.32±0.01	0.024±0.001	0.27±0.01	0.38±0.03	0.028±0.002	0.29±0.03

Thus, alkaline magmatites turn out to be richer in titanium than their normal differences; at the same time, for hyperbasites this difference is very significant (7.7 times), and for others it is relatively small (1.2–1.5 times).

At the same time, in the normal petrogenetic series, the TiO₂ content and the values of the titanium module TM pass through a maximum in basites, and the values of the phosphorus-titanium module PTM generally decrease, whereas in alkaline rocks, as we see, the picture is different — with a maximum in hyperbasites.

3. The correlations of titanium in alkaline rocks are characterized by amazing variability; for example, in some rocks there is a negative relationship with sodium, and in others, on the contrary, it is positive; in some rocks there is a seemingly understandable increase in titanicity with an increase in femicity FemM, but in others the opposite is observed. Nevertheless, the positive correlation of titanium with potassium and iron can be attributed to the most frequent links. It is obvious that the complex nature of the observed correlations is due to the undoubted mobility of titanium during the formation of alkaline rocks.

4. TITANIUM IN HYDROTHERMALITES

As for rocks containing a variety of hydrothermal mineralization, titanium in them is mainly inherited from primary rocks — unchanged by hydrothermal processes and can only be introduced or removed by hydrotherms to the smallest extent. Therefore, for example, in the manganese and pyrite deposits of the South Urals, the titanium content in rocks can vary from noticeable to completely poor — typical of siliceous rocks.

The results we have obtained are as follows.

1. Indicators of titanicity of hydrothermalites, meaning a variety of veins, including ore veins, as well as hydrothermally altered rocks containing these veins, are very variable. This variability was generated both by the different composition of the host rocks and by variations in the parameters of the hydrothermal process — temperature, concentrations, Eh and pH of hydrothermal fluids. A characteristic feature of hydrothermalites can be considered as a very significant dispersion of titanicity parameters, as well as unusually high values of the phosphorus-titanium

module PTM, averaging 0.86 ± 0.09 for 128 samples, which is explained by frequent phosphorus anomalies.

2. The most remarkable phenomenon identified by S. A. Repina and practically not covered in the geochemical literature is the ***Circumpolar-Ural phenomenon*** — a powerful accumulation of titanium in hydrothermal sericitolites underlying quartz veins and crystal-bearing nests in Europe's largest quartz and rock crystal deposit, Zhelannoe. In these formations, titanium (in the form of rutile) accumulated together with phosphorus and rare earths (in the form of monazite), boron (in the form of tourmaline) and zirconium (in the form of zircon). This phenomenon (which has undoubted analogues in other regions) indicates the high mobility of titanium (together with B, P, Zr, TR) in potassium alkaline hydrotherms.

3. In pyrite and manganese deposits of the Southern Urals, studied by Miass and St. Petersburg geologists [1; 3; 18; 24], various correlations of titanium are revealed, indicating the presence of accessories in ores and host rocks, as well as in the composition of silicates. These mineral forms underwent changes in the oxidation processes of primary sulfides.

5. TITANIUM IN METAMORPHITES

This section examines the distribution of titanicity indices (TiO_2 , TM, and PTM) in metamorphic rocks, the protolith of which is either igneous rocks (for example, meta-basites) or sedimentary rocks (for example, meta-psammites or meta-pelites).

5.1. Metabasites. This group contains products of metamorphism of igneous rocks of basic composition. However, it should be noted immediately that the boundaries of the compositions of such rocks are unclear; it is no coincidence that petrographers in recent years have stopped dividing basites into groups of paleotypic and kainotypic varieties that have long been familiar to us, and can call both fresh rock and rock that has undergone metamorphism in the green shale facies as *diabase*.

The reason for this is that in the vast majority of cases, it is possible to ignore the manifestations of allochemical metamorphism (with the introduction and removal of matter), so that the chemical composition of the basites remains approximately stable — both in primary rocks with pyroxenes and in greenstone-modified ones, where pyroxenes have not been present for a long time, only chlorite and amphibole are typical minerals, and calcium of the primary basic plagioclase often gives carbonate. For this reason (the absence of strict boundaries of basites and meta-basites), when calculating Clarkes, a number of analyses of meta-basites could well be in the group of basites.

The results we have obtained are as follows.

1. Median ($\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}}$) values for the totality of all metabasites were obtained based on 235, 233 and 182 samples covering more than 1000 analyses. It is

interesting to compare the obtained figures with estimates for non-metamorphosed basites (Table 3).

Table 3 Comparison of basites and metabasites

Basites			Metabasites		
TiO ₂ , %	TM	PTM	TiO ₂ , %	TM	PTM
1.24 ± 0.03	0.078 ± 0.002	0.15 ± 0.01	1.28 ± 0.03	0.093 ± 0.002	0.14 ± 0.01

As you can see, the estimates for TiO₂ and PTM turned out to be the same, whereas the titanium modulus of metabasites is much higher than basites, which we do not find a reasonable explanation for.

2. Despite the equality of the mean-median titanium contents, the revealed diversity of its correlations seems to reflect the influence of allochemical processes in which titanium could exhibit local mobility.

5.2. Meta-acidites

In his section of the monograph contains data on the average titanicity characteristics of meta-acidites, i.e. metamorphites on the substrate of igneous rocks of acid composition.

The results we have obtained are as follows.

1. The average median value for meta-acidites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 201, 201 and 169 samples, are $0.44 \pm 0.01\%$ (or $0.26 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.028 ± 0.001 and 0.24 ± 0.01 for TiO₂, TM and PTM, respectively.

2. In most of the processed samples, the predominant silica contents are in antagonism with titanium contents, which creates an artificial positive correlation of titanium with most other components. Nevertheless, the positive correlations of titanium with the “femic” components iron or magnesium (and the FeM and FemM modules derived from them) can be considered quite reliable. They indicate the entry of titanium into biotite (if there is a correlation with potassium at the same time) or into ore accessories (if there is no such correlation). Equally reliable are the negative correlations of TiO₂ — CaO or positive TiO₂ — Na₂O, indicating the mobility of titanium in metamorphic albitization processes.

5.3. Meta-psammites

Meta-psammites are metamorphites whose protolith was sandy rocks. If quartz sandstones metamorphosed, they turned into quartzites, which are usually certified as normosilites (HM 0.10–0.20), and with the metamorphism of feldspar-quartz and polymictic sandstones, myosilites (HM 0.20–0.30) are obtained, sometimes (with the metamorphism of arkoses) even hyposiallites (HM 0.30–0.34). There is often some uncertainty associated with such HM values, since they can characterize both metaarkoses and silt-clay shales. The question of whether to classify such “intermediate” rocks as sandy or clay is usually decided more or less arbitrarily.

However, in the “Fundamentals of Lithochemistry” [36] it was shown that the gravitation of siltstones to clastic or clay rocks depends on the climate: in arid environments, siltstones are closer to clays, and in humid ones — to sands.

The materials reviewed allow us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for Precambrian meta-psammites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 151, 151 and 125 samples. Despite the completely different volumes and geological characteristics of the aggregates, it is interesting to compare the data obtained with the general characteristics of non-metamorphosed psammites (mainly Phanerozoic) — tab. 4.

Table 4 Comparison of psammites and metapsammites

Psammites			Metapsammites		
TiO ₂	TM	PTM	TiO ₂	TM	PTM
0.50± 0.01 %	0.050±0.001	0.23±0.01	0.49 ± 0.02 %	0.042 ± 0.001	0.19 ± 0.01

As we can see, the titanicity indices of Precambrian meta-psammites almost do not differ from those of non-metamorphosed sandy rocks: the average TiO₂ contents are the same, but the values of TM and PTM are lower. The reasons for this difference are not clear enough.

2. As for Phanerozoic psammites, the titanicity of Precambrian meta-psammites was crucially dependent on the composition of the petrofund; therefore, the titanicity of meta-greywacks (in the primary composition of which there were products of erosion of basites or andesites) as a rule, it is higher than acidic meta-psammites, for example, meta-arcoses (in the primary composition of which the products of erosion of granites or acidic gneisses prevailed).

3. At the same time, judging by the often reduced values of the titanium modulus TM, it can be thought that among the protolith of ancient meta-psammites, petrogenic rocks of the first site type could occur much more often than among Phanerozoic ones — i.e., products of a single deposition of the material of erosion of the parent petrofund.

4. In addition to the difference in sedimentation conditions (that is, the differences between petrogenic and lithogenic sedimentites), the titanicity of meta-psammites (and especially titanium correlations) could be influenced by superimposed processes of allochemical metamorphism, in which usually inert titanium could acquire mobility.

5. Finally, a remarkable feature of the meta-psammites of the Alkesvozh strata (Є₃-O₁al) studied by us in the Maldynyrd region of the Circumpolar Urals was the presence of erosion products of the Pre-Ordovician weathering crusts in the protolith. The metamorphism of such a protolith gave rise to specific quarcites with

hematite, chloritoid, pyrophyllite and even diaspore, which was reflected in the alumina and titanicity of these metamorphites.

5.4. Meta-pelites

The term “meta-pelite” means that clay rocks served as the protolith of this metamorphite. As for most metamorphites, it has a probabilistic nature: it is not always certain that the original rock was clay. In the vast majority of cases, meta-pelites, like other metamorphites, are of Precambrian age.

The materials reviewed allow us to draw several conclusions.

The average median value for meta-pelites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$) were obtained on the basis 126, 126 and 96 samples. Despite the completely different volumes and geological characteristics of the aggregates, it is possible to compare the data obtained with the general characteristics of non-metamorphosed pelitoids (mainly Phanerozoic) — Table 5.

Table 5 Comparison of pelites and meta-pelites

Pelites			Metapelites		
TiO ₂ , %	TM	PTM	TiO ₂ , %	TM	PTM
0.81 ± 0.01	0.049 ± 0.001	0.18 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.02	0.049 ± 0.001	0.13 ± 0.01

1. As we can see, the titanicity indicators of Precambrian meta-pelites are the same in terms of TM value with Phanerozoic clay rocks, the TiO₂ content is noticeably higher, and the PTM value is, on the contrary, lower. The increase in TiO₂ can be explained by a greater proportion of basite pyroclastics in the composition of meta-pelites, and the decrease in PTM is due to the possible loss of phosphorus during metamorphism.

2. Unlike psammites, the composition of pelites (including titanicity) no longer depends on the petrofund, but on the previous weathering sedimentation; the same is true for meta-pelites. However, among them, magnesian rocks with increased hydrolysis can be found more often than for non-metamorphosed Phanerozoic clay rocks. This phenomenon has been established by us for a long time [36] and is explained by the low mobility of magnesium in Precambrian weathering. Therefore, in such meta-pelites, not only the usual positive correlation of Al₂O₃ — TiO₂ can manifest itself, but also a positive correlation of MgO — TiO₂.

3. At the same time, the appearance of biotite in meta-pelites often generates a combination of positive correlations of titanium with both potassium and iron.

5.5. Meta-silicites

Meta-silicites are metamorphosed siliceous rocks (silicites). Almost all of them are Precambrian, since Phanerozoic silicites (phthanites-radiolarites, spongolites, diatomites, etc.) are usually non-metamorphosed. The bulk of

Precambrian silicites are represented by Archean or Lower Proterozoic ferruginous quartzites.

The materials reviewed allow us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for metasilicites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 40, 40 and 26 samples, are $0.15 \pm 0.02\%$ (or $0.09 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.051 ± 0.004 and 0.72 ± 0.20 for TiO_2 , TM and PTM, respectively.

Compare these estimates with those for Phanerozoic silicites do not make sense, since the Precambrian ones are mostly represented by ferruginous quartzites — “extinct” rocks that, due to the evolution of sedimentogenesis in the history of the Earth, are no longer found in the Phanerozoic.

2. Since high-iron quartzites (rich ores) are practically two-component systems (iron + others) and since magnetite or martite are usually low-titanium, the often observed negative correlation of titanium with iron oxide is quite understandable. Of the positive correlations, $TiO_2 - K_2O$ or $TiO_2 - MgO$ bonds are characteristic, indicating the entry of titanium into the former clay admixture of protolith transformed into biotite or chlorite.

5.6. Meta-hydrolysate products

Among the metamorphites, hydrolysate formations can be considered separately, which are metamorphosed products of ancient weathering crusts (WC) on various substrates. In rare cases, a geologist may allow the preservation in situ of some WC zones on rocks (for example, granites or metabasalts), which can be considered a substrate of these WC. But much more often, of course, we can only talk about metamorphosed redeposited products of ancient WC. They give themselves away by increased hydrolysis: accumulation of aluminum or iron (or both).

As a rule, titanium accumulation is also noted in such metamorphites. But if the development of ancient WC on a basite substrate led, in general, to a monotonous increase in the titanicity of products as WC developed, then during the formation of WC on an acidic substrate, titanium was initially removed (apparently in an alkaline medium) and only in the final stages of the process titanium was concentrated again, so that the content of TiO_2 increased 2–3 times compared to the initial one.

The materials considered are summarized as follows.

The average median value for metamorphosed hydrolysate ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 79, 82 and 54 samples, are $0.63 \pm 0.04\%$ (or $0.38 \pm 0.02\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.034 ± 0.002 and 0.15 ± 0.01 for TiO_2 , TM and PTM, respectively.

By themselves, these averages do not make much sense; the variance of the data only reflects the difference in the substrate of ancient WC: more titanic WC developed for basic rocks, and less titanic WC — for acidic ones.

2. One can think that during the formation of such ancient rocks as the Archean and Lower Proterozoic, titanium could not only accumulate together with aluminum and iron, but also be carried out.

5.7. Metha-carbonates

Usually, no noticeable allochemical processes occur during the metamorphism of carbonate rocks, therefore, in a number of works, metamorphosed rocks receive the same names as non-metamorphosed ones. Nevertheless, metamorphosed carbonates, represented by crystalline rocks — *calcifyres* and *marbles*, are known and much stronger in the Baltic and Aldan shields.

The materials reviewed allow us to conclude the following.

1. The average median value for for Precambrian metamorphosed carbonates ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 20 samples, are $0.15 \pm 0.02\%$ ($0.09 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.046 ± 0.001 and 0.49 ± 0.04 for TiO_2 , TM and PTM, respectively.

At the same time, titanium in substantially carbonate metamorphites (marbles) is significantly less than in silicate-carbonate rocks (calcifyres and *ophicalcites*), respectively, the average TiO_2 contents are 0.05–15 and 0.30–0.50%.

2. Since titanium is a component of only the silicate part of ancient carbonates, there are negative correlations of titanium with carbonate content and, accordingly, positive correlations with silicate components, for example, with aluminum or alkalis.

6. TITANIUM IN METASOMATITES

Unlike predominantly isochemical regional metamorphism, where titanium usually behaves inertly, with allochemical metamorphism, especially with the addition of alkalis, titanium can exhibit significant mobility. The text of the monograph repeatedly indicates certain manifestations of allochemical metamorphism, which have the character of single anomalies on a common “isochemical background”. In this section, the phenomena of the introduction and removal of matter (including titanium) are considered on a more extensive basis, which allowed us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. In the processes of allochemical metamorphism, especially with the introduction of alkalis (in particular, during albitization of gabbroids), titanium exhibits mobility and can be strongly concentrated in some apobasitic metasomatites.

2. As was shown by D. I. Pavlov [19] back in the middle of the last century on the example of magnetite deposits in the East Sayan, an important factor in titanium migrations in the allochemical processes was the ***introduction of chlorine from the Cambrian evaporite strata*** at the base of the sedimentary cover of the Siberian Platform. The predominant mineral form of titanium in the processes of basite change was sphene, which, apparently, is generally characteristic of various processes of contact change of basites.

3. Allochemical processes (the introduction of alkalis and silicon) during the ultra-metamorphism of the basement rocks of the continents of Gondwana also affected titanium. In particular, significant mobility of titanium was found during the formation of such remarkable metamorphites as the Archean *charnockite*

granites of Antarctica. Ilmenite was the predominant mineral form of titanium during migmatization-granitization of granulites, which explains the positive correlation of TiO_2 –FeO.

7. TITANIUM IN THE BIOSPHERE

As already mentioned in the Preface, the presentation in the monograph is conducted mainly according to the plan tested in the monograph “Geochemistry of Manganese” [32]. However, due to the huge difference in the geochemistry of these elements, the content of individual headings turns out to be completely different. When describing the geochemistry of manganese, an element that is biophilic and highly mobile in conditions of hypergenesis, there was so much material on the biosphere that even a separate part of the book had to be allocated for it. The situation with titan is completely different. Ti is not biophilic, and in conditions of hypergenesis is almost motionless. Therefore, there are much fewer materials on the biospheric geochemistry of titanium. The little that we have managed to collect is distributed only under three headings: soils, sediments and living matter. Sedimentation is best provided with silicate analyses (or at least titanium definitions), less soil and very weakly living matter.

7.1. Soils and paleosoils

It is known [41, p. 72] that the Ti content in soils differs little from the content in the soil-forming substrate and falls within the range of 0.1–1.0%, sometimes reaching 2%. In slightly acidic soils, there is practically no mobile soluble titanium; nevertheless, in some podzolic soils, titanium accumulations in horizon B were noted, which indicates the migration of titanium, apparently in the form of complexes with humic acids. Regarding the titanium content in subsurface sedimentary rocks, A. P. Vinogradov emphasized the crucial importance of their primary petrofund:

“Sedimentary rocks formed during the destruction of basalt lavas and other basic rocks contain large amounts of titanium. This is especially true for the tropical and subtropical laterites of Africa and Asia <...> many Pacific islands, etc. The soils on them are exceptionally rich in titanium, for example, the soils of Kenya containing 35% TiO_2 ” [6, p. 107].

In a book on soil geochemistry, A. P. Vinogradov estimated the average titanium content in 7 types of soils of the USSR; these estimates were made on the basis of 84 soil analyses tested in four dozen sections. The average titanium content “in ordinary soils” of the whole world, A. P. Vinogradov estimated by 3000 definitions as about 0.46% (i.e. about 0.77% TiO_2), noting that

“this figure is equal to the average titanium content in the earth’s crust (0.5%) or slightly lower than it <...>” [6, p. 115]. According to individual sections, it was possible to notice a difference in the titanicity of soil horizons. Thus, in tundra

soils of Khibiny, in podzolic soils of different regions, in grey forest soils, titanium was least in humus horizons, and the maximum was in subsurface.

Both in the least titanitic grey soils and in other types of soils, a correlation of Ti and Fe contents is observed, and

“the Ti content increases with depth. This seems to indicate a noticeable migration of titanium in the direction of the flow of soil solutions (together with Fe)” [6, p. 112].

After a thorough discussion of not entirely reliable data on the possible mobility of titanium in soils, A. P. Vinogradov was inclined to believe that, in general, titanium in soils is poorly mobile, which the laterite process especially convinced him:

“The laterite process indicates that Ti is generally poorly mobile. In the tropics and subtropics, where there is intense weathering, during this process huge amounts of free $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (and $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$) are removed from the upper horizons; the content of TiO_2 to the upper horizons of this profile is clearly increasing. This means that TiO_2 remains in place” [6, p. 114].

As a result, A. P. Vinogradov concludes that

“the main, and perhaps the only factor determining the presence of Ti in soils is the rock on which the soil is created. Only deep soil-forming processes, similar to the laterite process in the tropics and much less in other soils — grey soils — give some originality to the distribution of titanium in these soils and its migration. The form in which Ti moves along the soil profile (obviously, together with iron) is unknown” [6, p. 121].

A review of the data at our disposal allowed us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for soils ($\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}}$), obtained on the basis of 61, 61 and 60 samples, are $0.58 \pm 0.02\%$ (or $0.35 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.053 ± 0.002 and 0.19 ± 0.01 for TiO_2 , TM and PTM, respectively.

Although due to a relatively small number of analyses, these figures are noticeably lower than the world soil Clarke according to A. P. Vinogradov, they are still quite indicative. In particular, we see that the indicators of soil titaniticity have no specificity: the TiO_2 content and the TM value in soils turn out to be the same as in soil-forming rocks, that is, lower in sandy and higher in clay soils.

2. At the same time, a surprisingly small dispersion of titaniticity indicators was revealed for a number of soil profiles; this means that, at least in some soils, titanium is practically stationary.

3. Another (unexpected) feature turned out to be the unusual correlations of titanium. Along with the “normal” bonds (negative with silicon and positive with aluminum, potassium or iron, that is, with clay matter), strange negative correlations of TiO_2 — P_2O_5 and positive TiO_2 — CaO (with carbonate content?) were found in some soils and even TiO_2 — SiO_2 . These connections may mean that the conclusion about the inertia of titanium in soils may be true only for some of them, whereas in others, titanium migrations in the soil profile did occur.

4. Thus, a new consideration of the geochemistry of titanium in a limited set of silicate analyses of soils leads to exactly the same conclusions that A. P. Vinogradov came to in 1957 [6]: **titanium is inert in most soils, but mobile in some soils.**

5. In the Permian and Triassic *paleo-soils* of the North Urals, discovered and studied by V. I. Chalyshev [27], judging by the characteristic correlations, titanium is associated with a clay substance.

7.2. Sediments

Sediments are called “analogues” of sedimentary rocks [22]. They are not lithified, and the young sediments are also characterized by strong waterlogging. Since titanium behaves as an inert component in lithogenesis processes, it can be expected that the distribution of titanium in sediments should not have fundamental differences from that in sedimentary rocks. In particular, two main forms of titanium finding can be expected — clastic (as part of accessories and dark-colored silicates) and clay. In modern lithology, the geochemistry of titanium is used to judge the mechanism of precipitation formation. For example, V. I. Koporulin, who studied ocean sediments, estimated the degree of sedimentary differentiation of terrigenous material “*during weathering of rocks of the feeding provinces, transfer and accumulation of terrigenous material*” [11, pp. 10–37]. To do this, he calculated the ratios of rock-forming elements (as well as TR_2O_3) to TiO_2 :

“*Titanium is very inactive during rock weathering, therefore <...> the values of the ratios of various elements to titanium oxide <...> in river water and source rocks, they can serve as an indicator of the enrichment or depletion of these elements relative to titanium oxide*” [11, p. 19].

As a result of a thorough review of the materials, the author comes to the conclusion about

“*large-scale differentiation of elements, which leads to the generation of significant masses of solid and dissolved in water material. The solid component of the latter, the terrigenous sediments themselves, are enriched in comparison with the initial rocks of Si, Al, Ti, LTR, i. e. chemically relatively inactive elements. The component part of this material transferred in dissolved form includes primarily Na, Ca, Mg, REE, i. e. chemically mobile elements, as well as a significant amount of Fe present in the form of organo-element compounds*” [11, p. 21].

According to 706 analyses, Moscow oceanologists determined the average Ti content in ocean suspension: 0.018%, which is much lower than the Ti content in ocean plankton (per dry matter), equal to 0.46% with a ratio of $\text{Ti}/\text{Al} = 0.21$ [15, p. 125]. At the same time, it turned out that in the ocean suspension this ratio is increased compared to the average in the lithosphere, from which it was concluded that planktonic titanium made a significant contribution:

“*We observe a sharper shift in titanium concentrations relative to aluminum in water than that which was observed in the suspension of lowland rivers and in*

atmospheric. This ratio, which should have decreased due to mechanical differentiation (removal of heavy Ti concentrator minerals from the suspension), actually increases due to some addition of titanium with organic matter" [15, pp. 125–126].

As for ocean sediments, as established by Moscow oceanologists led by academician A. P. Lisitsyn [15, pp. 135–137], the distribution of titanium in ocean sediments is primarily affected by climatic zonality (in humid sedimentation of titanium is greater than in arid sedimentation), as well as circumcontinental (titanium content decreases with distance from the coast into the ocean) and vertical. The latter is determined by the depth and topography of the bottom, which controls the granulometry of sediment, and therefore the content of titanium in them:

"In the shelf areas and on the upper parts of the continental slope, an increase in titanium concentrations is observed due to the reduced content of the pelite fraction here, containing minimal concentrations of titanium in the equatorial and temperate humid zones, in the arid zone <...>. On the shelves, where there is a sufficient number of grains of accessory minerals enriched in titanium, on uplifts and in places with high water energy, natural shading processes occur, which lead to very high concentrations of titanium. These are magnetite and titanomagnetite deposits, which are widely used for industrial purposes (especially in Australia, Japan)" [15, pp. 136–137]

As can be seen in the table given by them [15, pp. 134–136], volcanogenic and volcanic-terrigenous ocean sediments have the maximum titanium contents, where TiO_2 contents reach 6% (!), and strongly siliceous and calcareous sediments have the minimum, where TiO_2 concentrations can drop to trace ones.

A review of the materials available to us allowed us to draw several conclusions.

The average median value for sediments ($\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}}$), calculated on basis 19, 19 and 16 samples, are $0.60 \pm 0.01\%$ for TiO_2 (or $0.36 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.046 ± 0.001 and 0.31 ± 0.04 for TM and PTM, respectively.

Due to the limited materials, these figures are insufficient to estimate the titanium Clarkes in different sediments. As is known, the most titanitic are the shelf volcanic-terrigenous sediments associated with nearby sources of demolition on the bottom uplifts, which were deposited with increased environmental dynamics.

2. Both in continental (alluvial), marine and deep ocean sediments, the distribution of titanium is of the same type: the carrier of titanium is a terrigenous material, and the diluent is a carbonate material, which is established by the negative relationship of titanium with carbonate¹.

¹ According to our data, it is not possible to identify the possible occurrence of titanium in the carbonate material of deep ocean sediments, most likely simply due to the limited number of silicate analyses we used.

3. In terrigenous material, in turn, the main carrier of titanium is usually a clay substance, and the diluent is a clastic substance, primarily quartz and feldspar, which is expressed in a negative correlation of titanium with silicon and/or sodium and in a positive correlation with aluminum. Less often (in highly dynamic offshore sediments), the accessory ore form of titanium (correlation with iron) is manifested.

7.3. Living and biogenic matter

It was stated above that the material on the exogenous geochemistry of titanium, including the titanicity of the living matter of the biosphere, is mainly borrowed from our corresponding essays in the geochemistry of coal and the geochemistry of black shales [39; 40]. Therefore, for brevity, in the text of the monograph, most of the literary references are omitted and replaced with angle brackets (<...>).

Titanium is contained in the ash of terrestrial vegetation, more in bryophytes (0.2%) than in vascular (0.03%) <...>, and on average, it is believed <...>, in the content of 0.1%. Plants on peat-bog soils of Belarus contain an average of 100 ppm Ti, on soils of all species average 240 ppm, which gives a low BAC¹ from 0.10 to 0.36 [12 p. 120]. These data show that the possible contribution of primary vegetable Ti_{bio} in coals should be regarded as very insignificant. Ti accumulates relatively more strongly in marine biota: dry total plankton contains 25 ppm of Ti, which gives a very high BAC = 2.5·10⁴ <...>.

It has already been said above that in marine sedimentation titanium acts as an inert element—an indicator of clastic material — either terrigenous or volcanogenic. Thus, A. P. Vinogradov, noting that the Ti content in seawater is extremely low (~10⁻⁷%), wrote: “Ti is in the solid phase of suspension, obviously in the form of its usual compounds — oxides, titanates or titanosilicates, insoluble in seawater.”

At the same time,

“in some organisms titanium accumulates (algae, shellfish) 1000 times compared to the average content of it in oceanic water. They indicate the concentration of Ti Dinoflagellatae (Gymnodinium bravis)” [5, p. 115].

Let’s add that thermophilic algae (cyanea?) from lake Beowave (Nevada, USA) contains 520 ppm of Ti <...>. This paradoxical feature of titanium — low migration ability and at the same time a certain biophilicity — was once noticed by V. I. Vernadsky, who in 1937 emphasized two facts in the geochemistry of Ti:

- most titanium minerals in the biosphere it does not form;
- living matter concentrates Ti from aqueous solutions.

He made the last conclusion based on the analyses of his employee Sh. E. Kaminskaya, published in the same issue (No. 4) of the Proceedings of the Biogeochemical Laboratory. Vernadsky assumed that

¹ biological absorption coefficient

“organisms <...> It's like pumping titanium atoms out of aqueous solutions and introducing them into the metabolism of chemical elements in living matter.”

However, it remained unclear why organisms needed titanium:

“The concentration of titanium in living organisms clearly indicates that titanium is necessary for the body, must have certain vital functions. These functions are almost unknown to us” [4, p. 298].

Nevertheless, Vernadsky was confident in the biogenic nature of such mineral species of titanium as leucoxenes and *xanthanes* (aluminotitane gels); therefore, he recommended

“paying attention to some bacteria, especially ferrobacteria and their differences that secrete aluminum” [4, p. 299].

Later, data appeared in the literature on the accumulation of Ti not so much in living matter as in an *orthobiogenic* (A. V. Lapo's term [14]) *mineral substance* — in the shells of flint plankton. Also in the summary of E. Kressman on siliceous rocks <...>, data on abnormally high values of the titanium modulus TM in some types of siliceous rocks were presented, which was associated with the accumulation of Ti by flint sponges. The possibility of significant accumulation of Ti by siliceous plankton is also evidenced by the data of J. Martin and G. Knaurer <...>. In the most sterile plankton with rapid generational change (as a result of which impurity elements do not accumulate in it), the OS¹ practically does not contain Ti; but the siliceous substance carries 115 ppm of Ti, completely concentrating in itself the whole titan. In other samples, the OS of which contains an average of 27 ppm Ti per dry mass, the Ti content in the siliceous substance is even higher — 400 ppm.

If, based on the above data, we calculate the TM of the siliceous substance of plankton, we get values of ~ 0.140 and ~ 0.120, which is much higher than the stable average TM value for platform clays (0.040–0.060, according to A. A. Migdisov). These calculations show that the increased TM of siliceous rocks can be created not only by benthos (siliceous sponges), but partly by phytoplankton (for example, diatoms). Moscow oceanologists have revealed a paradoxical enrichment of pelagic ocean sediments with titanium, which can have only one explanation, namely, ***the addition of autigenic titanium to terrigenous titanium:***

“Apparently, the enrichment of sediments with titanium is due to processes characteristic only of oceanic sedimentogenesis, its extraction from a solution of ocean water by sorption processes, the formation of titanium hydroxides during hydrolysis of organic matter in deep horizons of the water column and on the surface of the sedimentary layer” [15, p. 137].

This assumption was confirmed by experiments on the stepwise leaching of sediments in the South Pacific Ocean. Leaching was performed with 25% acetic

¹Organic substance

acid, 1M hydroxylamine hydrochloric acid solution and chlorinated alcohol. During this procedure, forms of autigenic titanium were leached — sorbed, carbonate, and forms composed of iron and manganese hydroxides. As a result, remarkable results were obtained — the contribution of autigenic forms of titanium to sediment almost everywhere exceeded 50%, reaching an amazing figure of 80% of the gross content in sediment!

Note that these amazing data (unfortunately, not mastered by us in a timely manner) provided an answer to the reason for the long-established by A. A. Migdisov and then by us — the increased value of the titanium module ($TM = TiO_2 / Al_2O_3$) in most carbonate rocks [29; 42]. We only cautiously assumed that the increase in TM was due to additives of a certain (unknown to us) carbonate form of titanium. But now, in the light of the data of academician A. P. Lisitsyn and his team, this assumption can be considered fully confirmed. Nevertheless, the estimate of the average contribution of biogenic titanium (i. e., the *concentration function*, according to Vernadsky) in black shales turns out to be negligible. According to our calculations [40, p. 11], the average Ti content in dry total plankton is 25 ± 6 ppm. This means that even with the complete inheritance of biogenic titanium (which is unlikely) in a model black shale with a clay base (Clarke Ti = 4500 ppm) and 10% of planktonogenic organic matter, the contribution of the genetic fraction of Ti_{bio} will not exceed 0.06%.

A more realistic contribution to the hypergenic geochemistry of titanium could be provided by the *barrier function* of organic matter, for the assessment of which it makes sense to consider in more detail the interaction of titanium with continental (humus) organic matter [39, p. 259].

Humic acid in relation to titanium can perform both a transport and a barrier function. In the first case, soluble Ti–FA or Ti–HA complexes capable of migration are formed, in the second case, insoluble Ti–HA complexes. It was found that in a slightly acidic medium Ti reacts with carboxyl groups, and in an alkaline medium it reacts with HA oxygroups. In the experiments of Belarusian geochemists [202], the interaction of titanium (15% $TiCl_4$) with HA (1 g/l) was studied. In accordance with the data of other studies, it was found that the maximum absorption of titanium from the solution corresponds to a strongly acidic medium (pH = 2) and is 5.3 mg-eq Ti/1g C. Under conditions close to natural (pH 4–7), titanium forms soluble organo-metallic complexes with HA containing 2.1 mg-eq Ti/1g C [12, p. 123]. In terms of HC (assuming that HC contains about 50% C), we get about 3.2% and 1.3% Ti, respectively. **Thus, humic acid is capable of a powerful concentration of titanium.**

The fact that Ti is capable of migration in peat waters was also evidenced by the well-known experiments of A. P. Vinogradov [7], conducted by him in order to clarify the genesis of bauxites. The experiments were carried out by washing

a mixture of freshly precipitated Si, Al, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Ti⁴⁺ hydroxides on a filter during the day with solutions of humic acids in the presence of a reducing agent (SO₂). The determination of Ti in the filtrate showed that up to 7.4% of Ti passed into the solution. **Thus, humic acid is able to effectively perform a transport function in relation to titanium.** Naturally, for the geochemistry of titanium in coals, the main importance is not the transport function, but the *barrier function* of humus. Back in 1956, V. V. Shcherbina confidently admitted the reality of Ti humate complexes, based on the fact of extreme accumulation of Ti in the ash of English coal inclusions. Later, he directly pointed to phenolic hydroxyls as a factor of Ti accumulation in coals [28, p. 85].

A series of experiments Gr. Eskenazi [43] showed the ability of HA, peat and brown coal macerals to absorb Ti from solution. For example, peat extracted up to 60% of the total Ti from a solution with a Ti concentration of 54.7 mg/l, and the Ti concentration in peat reached 0.33%. However, due to hydrolysis, the experiments were carried out only in a very acidic environment at a pH not higher than 2. According to a number of signs, the absorption had the character of not very strong chemisorption, which noticeably increased with increasing duration of the experiment:

“This shows that Ti slowly forms stable chemical bonds” [43, p. 223]. However, in another work, a conclusion was made about stable complex compounds of Ti with organic ligands <...>.

This difference in estimates is not accidental and is caused by the fact that the experimental conditions are very far from natural — both in pH and Ti concentrations in solution. In such a situation, one should rely more not on experiment, but on geological data that reliably indicate the real presence of the Ti_{org} form in the coals.

8. TITAN IN THE STRATISPHERE

The stratisphere is understood as the shell of the Earth, composed of sedimentary rocks. Note that in Western geology, the term “stratisphere” does not exist; its full semantic analogue is the English-language term “*sedimentary shell*”.

In this section of the monograph, the distribution of titanicity indicators (TiO₂, %, TM and PTM) is considered both in the main types of sedimentary rocks (terrigenous, carbonate and siliceous) and in rarer but important minerals (alumina, phosphate, sulfate and zeolite). To complete the coverage of the topic, long-published essays on the geochemistry of Ti in carbonaceous bioliths — coals and black shales are reviewed here [38, 39; 40]. In addition, volcanogenic sedimentary rocks are an important component of the stratisphere, in the genesis of which endogenous processes (formation of the source material) are closely intertwined with the exogenous sedimentation mechanism. The term *tuffoids* is used for such rocks [36].

8.1. Psammites

Psammites are understood to be clastic rocks, both loose (gravels, sands, siltstones) and lithified (gravelites, sandstones, siltstones).

The materials reviewed allow us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for psammites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 269, 268 and 226 samples, are $0.50 \pm 0.01\%$ for TiO_2 (or $0.30 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.050 ± 0.001 and 0.23 ± 0.01 for TM and PTM, respectively. These figures can be considered our estimates of the general Clarkes of psammites, although due to the heterogeneity of psammites, such estimates do not make much sense. Separate estimates of the averages for sandstones of essentially quartz, feldspar-quartz and greywacke would be more useful.

2. For essentially quartz lithogenic psammites, the so-called *Migdisov pattern* is extremely characteristic — increased values of the titanium modulus TM caused by the dressing of alumina clay admixture and concentrations in the sediments of natural sludge — heavy titanium-containing accessories. The absence of this pattern (low TM values) in substantially quartz psammites may indicate their petrogenic nature (sedimentation of the *first site type*).

3. The high titanicity of some greywacke rocks, characteristic of the flysch strata, indicates an admixture of basitic pyro- or volcano-clastic in their clastic material.

4. The most characteristic correlations of titanium in psammites are negative correlations with the predominant silica and the resulting positive correlations with most other components. Despite the artificial nature of such correlations (as if a two-component closed system), positive correlations with iron and/or aluminum, and often with phosphorus are quite reliable and reflect the presence of titanium in a clay substance and/or in titanium-containing accessories. The affinity of titanium to a clay substance is also confirmed by the greater titanicity of siltstones compared to sandstones.

5. Carbonate cements, which are very characteristic of many sandstones, serve as diluents of titanium contents, which is usually indicated by a negative correlation of $CaO - TiO_2$ or $CO_2 - TiO_2$.

8.2. Pelites

The term pelites can be used to designate clay rocks, both loose (clays) and lithified (mudstones). Clay rocks (always combined with siltstone), as well as their isochemically metamorphosed lithotypes, called “clay shales”, make up most of the sedimentary shell. For example, according to A. B. Ronov [21], they account for 44% of the sedimentary shell. Most clay rocks are composed of the four most common clay minerals: kaolinite, montmorillonite, hydromica and chlorite. The first two are characteristic of the initial stages of lithogenesis, and the second — for catagenesis and initial metamorphism.

Lithochemical recognition of clay rock types is possible using the NaKM — FemM modular diagram, which identifies 6 fields (with overlaps) [36, pp. 128–131]. The figurative points falling into fields IV (NaKM = 0.20–0.35, FemM = 0.25–0.45) and V (NaKM = 0.20–0.38, FemM = 0.10–0.24) correspond to the most common clay rocks, in which either two components predominate (field IV: chlorite + hydromica) or three (field V: montmorillonite + hydromica + chlorite).

Since kaolinites are formations of weathering crusts, they are very often titanitic. Therefore, a priori (without detailed consideration of the materials), it can be assumed that *clay rocks with a noticeable participation of kaolinite* (field I in the NaKM — FemM diagram) *should be more titanitic than others*. Since titanium can also be contained in chlorites (and more in alumina and ferruginous than in magnesian ones), then substantially chlorite clays and shales should be more titanitic than substantially montmorillonite and hydromica rocks.

The materials reviewed allow us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. Average median value for pelites ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 248, 246 and 202 samples, are $81 \pm 0.01\%$ for TiO_2 (or 0.49 ± 0.01 for elementary Ti), 0.050 ± 0.001 and 0.18 ± 0.01 for TM and PTM, respectively. These figures can be considered our estimates of Clarkes of clay deposits.

2. The least titanitic are essentially montmorillonite clays, in particular, bentonites — products of acid pyroclastic degeneration, and the most titanitic are essentially kaolinite clays — formations of humid weathering crusts in which titanium accumulates together with alumina (sometimes with iron oxide).

3. In ordinary humid clay strata, titanium is concentrated in the clay part of the rocks, whereas the clastic part acts as a diluent. This explains the frequently observed correlations: positive TiO_2 — Al_2O_3 and negative TiO_2 — SiO_2 or TiO_2 — Na_2O , enhanced in derivative modules: $NaKM = (Na_2O + K_2O)/Al_2O_3$ and $AM = Al_2O_3/SiO_2$.

4. However, in arid clays, which are characterized by the accumulation of potassium in the form of orthoclase, unusual correlations of titanium can be observed, for example, the antagonism of titanium with potassium.

8.3. Carbonate rocks and nodules

Anticipating the consideration of analytical data, it can be assumed in advance that the geochemistry of titanium in carbonate and carbonate-containing rocks (marls) should be determined not by the carbonate, but by the silicate component of these rocks. Therefore, generally speaking, the purest limestones or dolomites should have a poor titaniticity, whereas all kinds of marls should contain more titanium. When analyzing materials, these obvious assumptions are mostly confirmed, but in specific cases, sometimes there are various kinds of “subtleties” in the distribution of titanium or in the values of titanium and phosphorus-titanium modules. Although diagenetic nodule formations have significant specificity (and

are often ores), most nodules are carbonate; therefore, it makes sense to consider them together with carbonate rocks

The materials reviewed allow us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for the aggregate of carbonate and nodules ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 153, 153 and 142 samples, are $0.15 \pm 0.01\%$ for TiO_2 (or $0.09 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.059 ± 0.001 and 0.40 ± 0.02 for TM and PTM, respectively.

2. At the same time, it is obvious that the Clarke titanicity of carbonate rocks strongly depends on the proportion of silicate titanium carrier material in these rocks. Due to the lack of a uniform division of rocks into “carbonate” and “non-carbonate” in the literature used, the final estimates of the Clarke may be different. Nevertheless, the figures obtained by us practically coincide with the Ronov’s Clarkes of 1990 [21].

3. The attraction of titanium to the silicate part of carbonate rocks also causes the usually observed correlations of titanium: a negative correlation of TiO_2 — carbonate (CO_2 or CaO) and a positive correlation with non-carbonate components, most often TiO_2 — Al_2O_3 .

4. As repeatedly noted earlier, the values of the titanium modulus TM in carbonate rocks are very often increased, *which is explained by the syngenetic occurrence of small impurities of titanium (but not aluminum!) into the carbonate substance of calcareous sediments.*

8.4. Silicites

Siliceous rocks (silicites) are a heterogeneous group. Firstly, Precambrian silicites, when there were no flint organisms in the biosphere, were chemogenic formations, whereas Phanerozoic ones were practically all biogenic. Secondly, among Phanerozoic silicites such biogenic rocks as radiolarites, spongolites and diatomites are very different formations. Thirdly, silicites can be different facially. In any case, in our the Ural region, siliceous rocks, as a rule, are deep-sea formations. Therefore, they are widespread in the paleobathial (“shale”) Lemva zone and are completely uncharacteristic of the paleoshelf (“carbonate”) Yelets zone.

Finally, silicites can also be hydrothermal volcanogenic, a typical example of which is the well-known jasper.

All this generates variability in the chemical composition of silicites, including their titanicity. Perhaps this is the reason for the lack of reliable estimates of the average compositions of silicites in the literature, because it makes no sense to average the compositions of genetically completely different formations.

The materials reviewed allow us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for siliceous rocks ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 200, 200 and 197 samples, are $0.26 \pm 0.01\%$ for TiO_2 (or 0.15 ± 0.01 for

elementary Ti), 0.053 ± 0.001 and 0.42 ± 0.03 for TM and PTM, respectively. These figures can be considered our estimates of silicite Clarkes.

2. *In the phase distribution of the titanium content of silicites, one can see a complete analogy with carbonate rocks:* the silicate part of the silicites is the carrier of titanium, whereas the siliceous part acts as a diluent. Therefore, the least titanitic are the purest varieties of silicites (radiolarites, diatomites, flakes and trelps), carrying minimal amounts of clay admixture.

3. This distribution of titaniticity also determines the usually observed correlations of titanium: a negative correlation of TiO_2 — SiO_2 and a positive correlation with silicate components, most often TiO_2 — Al_2O_3 .

4. The complete analogy of silicites with carbonate rocks is also visible in the values of the titanium modulus TM, which often turns out to be increased due to the inheritance of silicites by a siliceous substance of small amounts of primary biogenic titanium (Ti_{bio}) from planktonogenic siliceous sediments.

8.5. Weathering crusts and bauxites

Weathering crusts play an absolutely exceptional role in the geochemistry of titan. Being exogenic in the tetravalent Ti(IV) state, titanium forms a very stable TiO_2 oxide, represented by such widespread accessories as rutile and especially leucocoxene ($\text{TiO}_2, \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) $\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Therefore, during the formation of weathering crusts, titanium usually accumulates together with two “older” hydrolysates — aluminum and trivalent iron Fe(III).

However, due to the much smaller Clarke, strong titanium accumulations in hydrolysate products are much less common than concentrations of aluminum and iron. As a rule, the condition for such accumulations is a favorable mineral form of titanium in the substrate (ilmenite) and the primary enrichment of the substrate with it — gabbroids, tuffs or kimberlites.

For example, A. D. Savko and A. D. Dodatko described the Devonian WC according to the tuffs of the Antontaran formation of Donbass, lying under the Fran deposits. This WC is characterized by powerful accumulations of titanium in the form of anatase, reaching 13.38% TiO_2 in hematite-hydromica formations of the II (intermediate) WC zone <...>.

The work of Yu. G. Tsekhovskiy et al. <...> provides data on the increased titaniticity of the Jurassic bauxites of Syria (TiO_2 up to 4.5%, TM up to 0.078) and genetically related iron ores (TM up to 0.120); the substrate of these rocks are basalts and their tuffs.

In the zone of interformational contact between the Riphean-Vendian Pre-Uralid complex and the Caledonian-Hercynian Uralid complex in the Circumpolar Urals, metamorphosed Cambrian weathering crust has been preserved in places. If it developed according to Vendian basalts — rocks markedly enriched in titanium (2–3% TiO_2) and iron (13–15% $\text{FeO} + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), then these components

accumulated strongly in WC: up to 7–9% TiO_2 in the form of leucoxene and up to 25% Fe_2O_3 in the form of hematite [36; 31].

However, the preservation of the weathering crust (WC) with all its zones in the geological section is a much rarer phenomenon than the existence of various derivatives of WC — products of erosion and redeposition of former full-profile WC. Since the basic igneous rocks have a much higher titanicity than acidic ones (the same is true for isochemical metamorphites), the geochemistry of titanium in exogenesis can serve as an important aid — an indicator of the primary substrate of WC [31].

The materials reviewed allow us to draw several conclusions.

1. The average median value for weathering crust (WC) ($\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}}$), calculated on basis 280, 280 and 138 samples, are $1.50 \pm 0.05\%$ for TiO_2 (or $0.90 \pm 0.03\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.054 ± 0.001 and 0.13 ± 0.01 for TM and PTM, respectively.

2. During the formation of weathering crusts, a “residual” concentration of titanium occurs together with the “older” elements-hydrolysates — aluminum and iron. Therefore, typical correlations for titanium are negative with silicon (and/or with alkalis) and positive with aluminum (and/or with iron).

4. At the same time, in the early stages of the formation of WC zones, titanium could be partially removed from the WC substrate.

5. The allochemical processes of titanium introduction and removal in weathering crusts could lead to a complication of titanium correlations with other components.

8.6. Carbonaceous bioliths

In this section of the monograph, our essays on the geochemistry of titanium in carbonaceous bioliths of two types are presented in abstract form — black shales containing organic matter mainly of the “sapropel” type, and coals containing organic matter mainly of the humus type. The reader can find literary references in the works used [39; 40; 41]: here they are replaced by angle brackets (<...>).

8.6.1. Titanium in black shales

In our 1992 book [41, pp. 74–75], estimates of the average titanium contents in the most famous black shale stratons were given, based on statistical processing of about 470 samples, numbering about 18 thousand analyses. Consideration of these data made it possible to calculate the simplest unweighted estimate of the overall average in the form of $\text{Me} \pm 1\sigma_{\text{Me}} = 3000 \pm 100$ ppm. The use of quartiles of the distribution allows to set the following gradations (ppm): 1500–4600 — geochemical background; 4600–6200 — anomalies; 6200–7800 — strong anomalies, > 7800 — sharp anomalies.

The most complete lithochemical characterization of black shales was given in our book “Geochemistry of Black Shales” [33], and this monograph provides estimates for only 12 samples of Precambrian black shales, covering a set of 61 analyses (including 5 averages calculated from 42 separate definitions). Standard

statistical processing of these data with the construction of frequency histograms gives median values (with the standard deviation of the median) for TiO_2 , TM and PTM equal to $0.67 \pm 0.05\%$ (or 0.40 ± 0.01 for elementary Ti), 0.058 ± 0.005 and 0.10 ± 0.01 , respectively. The median obtained for Ti contents turned out to be close to the global Clarke of terrigenous+tuffogenic black shales.

Correlation graphs for TiO_2 have also been constructed for some of these samples of Precambrian black shales. This number includes the Archean graphite-bearing gneisses of the Aldan shield, the Upper Anatolian (Lower Proterozoic) shungite-bearing shales of Karelia and the Sovayarva shales of the Northern Karelia, as well as the metalliferous (including phosphate-bearing) shales of Korea. As these graphs have shown, the most characteristic is the positive correlation of titanium with aluminum and less often with iron.

As a result of generalization of all data on the distribution of titanium in black shales, the following conclusions were made [41, pp. 79–80].

1. Titanium does not belong to the typical elements-impurities of black shales, despite the fact that some flint organisms-titanium concentrators are known. Titanium Clarke in black shales (estimates K_1 and K_2) are 2700–2800 ppm, the content of >4600 ppm can be considered abnormal.

2. The forms of Ti in black shales have not been studied, so the proportion of autigenic forms is unknown. The presence of small amounts of the Ti_{org} form is not excluded, most likely in unmetamorphosed black shales. By analogy with better studied coals, it should be expected that during the metamorphism of black shales, titanium migrates with the formation of mineral autigenic forms of Ti_{min} .

3. All syngenetic anomalies of Ti in black shales are non-specific in the sense that they are not genetically related to the accumulation of organic carbon C_{org} . Among such anomalies, two types can be distinguished: volcanogenic (due to basite or ultrabasite pyroclastics) and terrigenous (due to erosion of the weathering crust along the basites). The second type should probably include shales with a high content of metamorphogenic ilmenite, which are of important industrial importance. On the Timan, Riphean shales of this type served as a substrate for the formation of the richest placers in the Devonian.

8.6.2. Titanium in coals

Probably, the first figure of the Ti content in coals belongs to Ch. White, who discovered 0.41–1.55% Ti in the ashes of five coals in 1896. This was followed by reports of the presence of up to 0.3% Ti in peat ash and increased Ti contents (up to 2.35%) in U.S. coal ash. In the 1930s, there were reports of extraordinary concentrations of Ti in the ashes of English coals. In 1934, the annual report of the British Fuel Research Board published the figure of 15% TiO_2 in ash. However, a special study showed that titanium is concentrated not in coal seams, but in vitrenic coal inclusions (“cauldron”, “horse backs”) lying in the roof of working coal

seams of Northumberland and Durham and folded compressed cow tissue sigillaries <...>. According to 15 analyses, the content of TiO_2 in ash was 7.0–24.3%. These amazing figures characterized light ($<1.35 \text{ g/cm}^3$) fractions with exceptionally low ash content: from 0.09 to 1%, on average no more than 0.3%.

Therefore, in terms of coal, even the maximum Ti content will not exceed 0.01%. However, this is 2–3 times higher than the vitreous from nearby coal seams. The nature of these accumulations has not been established. J. Jones and J. Miller were inclined to believe that this is biogenic titanium, concentrated (together with chromium) due to the selective leaching of more soluble ash components. In those years, it was this idea of V. Goldschmidt that was the “paradigm” of coal geochemistry. However, when in the post-war years it became clear that coal inclusions concentrate not only Ti and Cr, but also many other trace elements that clearly could not accumulate in such high quantities during the life of plants — it became clear that Ti in English vitreous inclusions has a migratory, not relict nature.

The generalization of a significant amount of data made in the monograph [39] allowed us to draw the following conclusions.

1. Clarke Ti in brown and hard coals is 700–900 ppm of coal and 4000–5300 ppm of ash, respectively, and the average ash CI¹ is about 1.2. Thus, Ti is on average a moderately coal-philic element, enriching coal ash by only 20% compared to sedimentary rocks.

2. Nevertheless, some coals are known, the ashes of which are significantly enriched in titanium compared to the host rocks. Particularly high Ti contents were found in light vitreous fractions of coals and some coal inclusions with a “vanadium” association of elements. These and other facts undoubtedly prove the presence of a virtual (genetic) fraction of Ti_{sorb} in coals, most often in the form of Ti_{org} .

3. Due to the high Clarke Ti in clastogenic ash, the proportion of the virtual fraction of Ti_{clast} is always significant, and in many coals it prevails. Therefore, Ti accumulations in coals and in coal ash are not always correlated. The coals lying in titanium-bearing platform formations, genetically related to weathering crusts and in some molasses, are relatively enriched with Ti, but the accumulation of Ti in ashes (compared with the host rocks) is typical only for the former. It is in these coals that the proportion of the virtual fraction of Ti_{sorb} in the titanium balance is increased.

4. Judging by some data, the accumulation of Ti_{sorb} in coals occurs more intensively than the accumulation of Al, therefore the titanium modulus ($\text{TiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) in coals turns out to be higher than in most clay rocks. The systematic study of the distribution of the titanium module seems to be an urgent task of coal geochemistry.

5. An important (but only recently established) feature of titanium geochemistry in coals is its accumulation in bituminous micro-components of the leuconite

¹CI — coal affinity index

group — in spores and crustal tissues. Without excluding the presence of the virtual fraction of Ti_{sofb} in them, we can confidently talk about the real contribution of primary plant titanium — the virtual fraction of Ti_{bio} .

6. An important feature of the geochemistry of Ti in coals is the abundance of autigenic, dispersed micromineral phases in the coal layer — rutile and anatase, less often brookite or ilmenite (?), which are the product of the transformation of Ti_{org} in forms. The question of whether there is a relationship between the number of these phases and the degree of coal metamorphism is unclear and needs to be investigated. It can be assumed that the Ti_{org} form is no longer present in hard coals of medium and high grades: it has completely transformed into micromineral forms (for example, anatase).

7. Actualistic comparisons with modern peatlands allow us to expect anomalies in the distribution of Ti due to syn- and epigenetic oxidation of sulfide-bearing peats and coals.

8. When burning most coals, there is no noticeable fractionation of titanium in ash waste. However, when burning coals with a noticeable fraction of the Ti_{org} form, a partial transition of titanium into the gas phase occurs, followed by condensation in the ash drift.

8.7. Rare lithotypes

In this section of the monograph, materials on rarer varieties of sedimentary rocks, which are usually minerals, are considered. These include phosphate rocks (including industrial phosphorites), sulfate and zeolite. Phosphorites are minerals, and therefore a lot of analyses of these rocks can be found in the specialized literature. However, as with most minerals, these analyses are usually incomplete; among the analyses of industrial phosphorites, there are very few complete silicate analyses in which titanium would be determined. Complete analyses of phosphorites can be found in the book by N. G. Brodskaya [2], which, contrary to the ideas of academician N. M. Strakhov, who denied the connection of phosphorites with volcanism, showed that for some phosphorites such a connection is quite real.

An interesting variety of phosphorites are metasomatic apo-reef ones described by B. I. Chuvashov and his graduate student L. P. Yakovleva in the southern part of the Pre-Ural trough. The analysis of these data showed that the TiO_2 content and TM values in pure or strongly carbonate phosphorites are poor and low, and increase only in phosphate-bearing rocks with a noticeable clay admixture. In general, titanium is negatively correlated with the carbonate content and manganese modulus MnM, and positively correlated, respectively, with the components of the silicate part of the rocks, most strongly with potassium.

A review of all the data we had on phosphate rocks allowed us to conclude the following.

1. Titanium is included in the silicate part of phosphate rocks, whereas the phosphate substance does not contain titanium. This also generates characteristic correlations: negative with a phosphate substance (for example, with calcium phosphate) and positive with some component of the silicate part, most often with aluminum.

2. The unusual positive correlation of titanium with phosphate in some clastic phosphorites is the result not of a geochemical, but of a mechanical process of natural dressing: with the combined accumulation of phosphates and heavy titanium-containing accessories.

It is very rare to find complete silicate analyses of sulfate rocks in the literature. Since gypsum and anhydrites are minerals, in the industrial evaluation of raw materials, the consumer needs only data on the content of a useful component and some “harmful” impurities; the content of such a “minor” component as titanium does not matter. We were able to find only two objects with complete analyses. With regard to data on the Neogene rocks of Ferghana, in the “Fundamentals of Lithochemistry” [36, p. 273] it is noted that

“although modules in which there is no sulfur or sulfate do not provide clear information about the specifics of these rocks, hyper-alkalinity attracts attention: Na/KM from 0.58 to 0.93 in sulfatolites. This fact may “alert” the researcher and make him pay attention to the content of sulfur or sulfate in rocks. In addition, the hyper-titanicity of gypsum and anhydrites (TM = 0.094) is very interesting (although incomprehensible).”

As for the Lower Vilyukan manifestation of aluminum sulfates in the Western Yakutia, with regard to titanium, sulfate-containing rocks are unremarkable $\text{TiO}_2 = 0.14\text{--}0.55\%$, $\text{TM} = 0.016\text{--}0.067$. Obviously, titanium has nothing to do with sulfates.

Zeolites, as a rule, form only a small fraction of the total composition of rocks; researchers prefer to study the monofractions of the minerals themselves—zeolites, which are an industrial “useful component”. Therefore, a complete analysis of zeolite-containing rocks was performed only in isolated cases; several such analyses can be found in two articles by the largest Russian expert on zeolites, Kazan geologist A. S. Mikhailov¹

With regard to titanium, zeolite rocks are unremarkable: TiO_2 content = $0.14\text{--}0.46\%$, $\text{TM} = 0.012\text{--}0.035$, $\text{HM} = 0.19\text{--}0.40$, with a minimum in mordenite rocks and a maximum in clinoptilolite ones. Note that the minimum of HM in mordenite rocks reflects the well-known fact that mordenite is the most siliceous of all zeolites [9].

It seems obvious that titanium is not included in the composition of zeolites, although in fact this is not entirely true: its possible impurities are simply very small. Indeed, titanium can replace silicon in the zeolite framework [9].

¹ You can read about Mikhailov in the Fourth book in the series “Russian Geologists Tell About Themselves” [37, pp. 36–45]

8.8. Tuffoids

In lithology, there are varieties of volcanogenic sedimentary rocks: ash tuffs, tuffites, various kinds of “tuffogenic” rocks (for example, tuff sandstones or tuffo-argillites) and volcanomictic rocks. The first three contain pyroclastic material; in tuffs it predominates, and in others it is more or less an impurity.

The latter group contains an admixture of volcanic debris; sandstones are most often called that, but in principle any sedimentary rocks (even carbonate ones) can be “volcanomictic” if an admixture of volcanic rock fragments got into them at the stage of formation of the initial sediment. It is clear that it is possible to distinguish rocks where hot pyroclastics of the same age with sediment got at the sedimentation stage from rocks with cold volcanoclastic, which may be hundreds of millions of years older than sediment, only in sedimentites that are little changed by secondary processes. In this case, volcanoclastic is easily distinguished from pyroclastic by the granulation of the grains.

However, very often a geologist deals with rocks that have been changed in catagenesis or even in metamorphism. Therefore, accurate diagnosis of volcanogenic sedimentary rocks turns out to be difficult, and often simply impossible.

In order to distinguish tuff from tuffite, tuffogenic or volcanomictic rocks, a geologist requires imagination rather than precise knowledge. It is no coincidence that a number of such diagnoses in V. T. Frolov’s monograph [26] were criticized. A typical example is, for example, the “*volcanomictic and tuffogenic sandstones*” of the Koryak Highlands, which are from the Ordovician to the Permian (and possibly up to the Triassic). The author’s rock names themselves, for example, “*volcanomictic sandstones with transitions to tuff, calcified*”, show the difficulty of an accurate diagnosis.

It should be noted that calcification is one of the characteristic signs of a change in volcanic material, in which Ca is released during the decomposition of the main plagioclase. In this case, sodium goes into albite (therefore, albitization is very often observed in volcanogenic sedimentary rocks), and Ca goes into calcite.

A review of all the data on tuffoids allowed us to draw a number of conclusions.

1. The average median value for tuffoids ($Me \pm 1\sigma_{Me}$), calculated on basis 141, 141 and 101 samples covering 583 analyses, are $0.65 \pm 0.02\%$ for TiO_2 (or $0.39 \pm 0.01\%$ for elementary Ti), 0.044 ± 0.001 and 0.24 ± 0.01 for TM and PTM, respectively.

Of course, these figures have no special geochemical value, since it is obvious that the titanicity of tuffoids depends on at least two completely independent factors: (a) the composition of the host rock in which the volcanogenic impurity was buried and (b) the titanicity of this impurity itself: minimal for acidic ashes and maximum for basite ashes.

2. Due to the complex interaction of these factors, which are further complicated by post-sedimentation changes in pyroclastics (the most striking example of

which is the formation of *bentonites*), the correlations of titanium in tuffoids are also variable.

3. The geochemistry of titanium in deeply metamorphosed strata is particularly difficult, where all the above factors can be superimposed by allochemical processes.

9. TITANIUM AS A GEOCHEMICAL INDICATOR

All the materials used in this section of the monograph have previously been published in our monographs on regional geochemistry [29], black shales [33], fundamentals of lithochemistry [36], mineral [34] and geochemical indicators of lithogenesis [31] and on the diagnosis of volcanic products in sedimentary strata [30].

Here, in the interests of the reader, everything related to titanium or the titanium module has been extracted and put together. This made it possible to omit most of the literary references — if necessary, the reader will find them in these monographs. The limited volume of this article does not allow us to consider the indicator properties of titanium here; the interested reader is referred to the text of the monograph.

10. CONCLUSION

The median contents of TiO₂ (as well as Ti) and the values of TM and PTM for 22 rock groups, including 13 endogenous (igneous, hydrothermal and metamorphic) and 9 sedimentary, including both sediments and sedimentary rocks, were described above and very briefly considered.

These estimates are based on statistical processing of about 350 samples covering about 125,000 silicate assays, and are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6 Median titanicity indices (Me±1σ_{Me}) for the main rock groups

Rocks	Number of samples	Number of analyses	TiO₂, %	Ti, %	TM = TiO₂/Al₂O₃	PTM = P₂O₅/TiO₂
Hyperbasites	72	423	0.31 ± 0.06 %	0.17 ± 0.03	0.067 ± 0.007	0.35 ± 0.04
Basites	363	1986	1.24 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.02	0.078 ± 0.002	0.15 ± 0.004
Mesites	104	795	0.73 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.01	0.045 ± 0.001	0.29 ± 0.01
Acidites	258	1988	0.32 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01	0.024 ± 0.001	0.27 ± 0.01
Alkaline	154	915	1.19 ± 0.07	0.71 ± 0.04	0.074 ± 0.006	0.30 ± 0.01
Metabasites	235	1041	1.28 ± 0.03	0.77 ± 0.02	0.093 ± 0.002	0.14 ± 0.01
Metaacidites	201	1210	0.44 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.01	0.028 ± 0.001	0.24 ± 0.01
Metapsammites	151	950	0.49 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.01	0.042 ± 0.001	0.19 ± 0.01
Metapelites	126	755	0.91±0.02	0.54 ± 0.01	0.049±0.001	0.13±0.01
Metasilicites	26	195	0.15 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.01	0.051 ± 0.004	0.72 ± 0.20

Rocks	Number of samples	Number of analyses	TiO ₂ , %	Ti, %	TM = TiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	PTM = P ₂ O ₅ /TiO ₂
Metahydrolysates	79	269	0.63 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.02	0.034 ± 0.002	15 ± 0.01
Metacarbonates	20	89	0.15 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.01	0.046 ± 0.001	0.49 ± 0.04
Metasomatites	194	786	0.72 ± 0.04	0.43 ± 0.02	0.051 ± 0.002	0.17 ± 0.01
Soils	61	356	0.58 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.01	0.053 ± 0.002	0.19 ± 0.01
Sediments	19	85	0.60 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.01	0.046 ± 0.001	0.31 ± 0.04
Psammites	269	1944	0.50 ± 0.01	or 0.30 ± 0.01	0.050 ± 0.001	0.23 ± 0.01
Pelites	248	7113	0.81 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.01	0.050 ± 0.001	0.18 ± 0.01
Carbonates	153	731	0.15 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.01	0.059 ± 0.001	0.40 ± 0.02
Silicites	200	1026	0.26 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.01	0.053 ± 0.001	0.42 ± 0.03
Weathering crusts and bauxite	280	1113	1.50 ± 0.05	0.90 ± 0.03	0.054 ± 0.001	0.13 ± 0.01
Black Shales	12	61	0.67 ± 0.05	0.40 ± 0.01	0.058 ± 0.005	0.10 ± 0.01
Tuffoids	141	583	0.65 ± 0.02	0.39 ± 0.01	0.044 ± 0.001	0.24 ± 0.01

For a number of rocks (for example, clay or siliceous), the figures in Table 6 can serve as new Clarke estimates — more reliable than those published. For some others, they do not have this quality, but, nevertheless, they give a very useful idea of the distribution of titanium indicators, which was previously generally absent in the literature (for example, for metabasites or metapelites).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Dr. D.R. Khismatullin for inviting to publish this article..

References

1. **Ayupova N. R., Maslennikov V. V.** *Galmyrolites of the Uzelginsky pyrite-bearing field (Southern Urals). — Miass: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2005. 199 p.*
2. **Brodskaia N. G.** *The role of volcanism in the formation of phosphorites. — M.: Nauka. 1974. 198 p. (Tr. GIN of the USSR Academy of Sciences. Issue 258).*
3. **Brusnitsyn A. I.** *Mineralogy of manganese-bearing meta-sediments of the Southern Urals. — St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University, 2013. 160 p.*
4. **Vernadsky V. I.** *Selected works. Vol. 6. Biosphere. Articles on biogeochemistry. Soils. Gases. Meteorites and cosmic dust. Ed. 2th. — M.: USSR Academy of Sciences, 1960. 422 p.*
5. **Vinogradov A. P.** *Introduction to ocean geochemistry. — M.: Nauka, 1967. 213 p.*

6. **Vinogradov A. P.** *Geochemistry of rare and scattered elements in soils. 2nd edition, supplement* — M.: USSR Academy of Sciences, 1957. 237 p.

7. **Vinogradov A. P.** *On the causes of the high titanium content in bauxites (in connection with the question of the genesis of bauxites)* // *Izv. AN USSR. Ser. geol.*, 1957, No. 4. Pp. 98–103.

8. **Ivanov V. V.** *Titan — 22 // Ecological geochemistry of the elements. Guide. Book 4. The main d-elements.* — M.: Ecology, 1996. Pp. 16–62

9. **Ketris M. P., Yudovich Ya. E.** *Lithochemistry of zeolites* // *Uralsk. geol. w.*, 2008, № 4(64). Pp. 31–46.

10. **Kopeikin V. A.** *Geology of deposits of solid minerals: A textbook.* — Ukhta: UTSU, 2000. 102 p.

11. **Koporulin V. I.** *Terrigenous deposits as a source of continental crust material // Vertical accretion of the Earth's crust: factors and mechanisms / Leonov M. G., Artamonov A. V., Vinogradov V. I. et al.* — M.: Nauka, 2002. Pp. 10–37. (Tr. GIN RAS. Issue 542).

12. **Kuznetsov V. A., Generalova V. A.** *Radionuclides and colloidal compounds of titanium in landscapes* // *Lithosphere*, 1999, No. 10–11. Pp. 118–124.

13. **Landa E. A., Markovsky B. A.** *Picrites and komatiites (debatable problems of comparison and classification)* // *Regional geology and metallogeny*, 2014, No. 59. Pp. 52–53.

14. **Lapo A. V.** *Traces of former biospheres. 2nd ed., reprint. and additional* — M.: Znanie, 1987. 208 p.

15. **Lisitsyn A. P., Lukashin V. N., Yemelyanov E. M., Zverinskaya I. B.** *Chapter 4. Titan // Geochemistry of hydrolysate elements.* — M.: Nauka, 1980. Pp. 117–149.

16. **Lutz B. G.** *Chemical composition of the continental crust and upper mantle of the Earth.* — M.: Nauka, 1975.

17. **Marakushev A. A.** *Petrogenesis.* — Moscow: Nedra, 1988. 293 p.

18. **Maslennikov V. V.** *Sedimentogenesis, galmyrolysis and ecology of pyrite-bearing paleohydrothermal fields.* — Miass: Geotour, 1999. 348 p.

19. **Pavlov D. I.** *Anzasskoye magnetite deposit and the participation of chlorine in its formation.* — M.: Nauka, 1964. 128 p.

20. **Repina S. A.** *The deposit of vein quartz and rock crystal Zhelannoe.* — Yekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2016. 287 p.

21. **Ronov A. B., Yaroshevsky A. A., Migdisov A. A.** *The chemical structure of the Earth's crust and the geochemical balance of the main elements.* — M.: Nauka, 1990. 182 p.

22. **Systematics and classification of sedimentary rocks and their analogues / V. N. Shvanov, V. T. Frolov, E. I. Sergeeva, etc.** — St. Petersburg: Nedra, 1998. 352 p.

23. **Sitnikov T. A.** Several utilities to simplify work with geological and geochemical graphs in Microsoft Excel // *Bulletin of the Institute of Geology of the Komi Scientific Research Center of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences*, 2013, August No. 8 (224). Pp. 22–25.

24. **Starikova E. V., Brusnitsyn A. I., Zhukov I. G.** Paleohydrothermal construction of the Kyzyl-Tash manganese deposit, Southern Urals. — St. Petersburg: Nauka, 2004. 230 p.

25. **Fersman A. E.** Titan // *Geochemistry. Volume four.* — M.: USSR Academy of Sciences, 1959. pp. 126–133. (Selected works. Vol. V).

6. **Frolov V. T.** Lithology. Book 1: Textbook. Moscow: Moscow State University, 1992. 336 p.

27. **Chalyshev V. I.** Fossil soils of Permian coal-bearing deposits of the North-East of the European part of the USSR. — Syktyvkar: Komi phil. USSR Academy of Sciences, 1974. 37 p. (Series of preprints “Scientific reports”. Issue 11).

28. **Shcherbina V. V.** Migration of elements and processes of mineral formation. — M.: Nauka, 1980, 284 p.

29. **Yudovich Ya. E.** Regional geochemistry of sedimentary strata. — L.: Nauka, 1981. 276 p.

30. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Geochemical and mineralogical indicators of volcanogenic products in sedimentary strata. — Yekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2010. 412 p.

31. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Geochemical indicators of lithogenesis (lithological geochemistry). — Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 2011. 740 p.

32. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Geochemistry of manganese. — Syktyvkar: IG Komi SC UrO RAS, 2014. 540 p.

33. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Geochemistry of black shales. — L.: Nauka, 1988. 272 p.

34. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Mineral indicators of lithogenesis. — Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 2008. 564 p.

35. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Our half-century in geochemistry. — Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 2016. 190 p.

36. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Fundamentals of lithochemistry. — St. Petersburg: Nauka, 2000. 479 p.

37. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Russian geologists talk about themselves. Texts with comments. Book Four: additional. — Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 2016. 568 p.

38. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Toxic elements-impurities in fossil coals. — Yekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2005. 656 p.

39. **Yudovich Ya. E., Ketris M. P.** Valuable elements-impurities in coals. — Yekaterinburg: Nauka, 2006. 538 p.

40. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M. P.** *Trace elements in black shales.*— Yekaterinburg: UIF Nauka, 1994. 304 p.

41. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M. P., Kozyreva I. V.** *Geochemistry of hydrolysate elements in black shales.*— Syktyvkar: AST LLP, 1992. 137 p.

42. **Yudovich Ya.E., Ketris M. P., Tereshko V. V., Rybina N. V.** *Essays on lithochemistry of the Timan-Ural region.*— Syktyvkar: Geoprint, 2016. 236 p.

43. **Eskenazy G.** *Adsorption of tinanium on peat and coal // Fuel, 1972. Vol. 51, No. 3. P.p 221–223.*

Proceedings of International Science Conference

APPLIED RESEARCH. GLOBAL SOLUTIONS

Part 1

Istanbul, Turkey
December 17, 2025

Scientific Editor — Khismatullin Damir

Signed in print 17.12.2025 60x84/16.
Ed. No. 1. Circulation of 500 copies. Turkey, 2025.
Infinity publishing, 2025

